

Analysing the service quality gaps between traditional hotels and shared accommodation: a study on customer gap in central London

By

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Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Business Administration.

August 2021

Dedication

To my parents:

Md. Nurul Hoque and Jahanara Hoque

For their care, patience, love, sacrifice, and hard work to nourish me.

To my brothers and sisters:

Naznin Hoque

Shamima Hoque

MD Aminul Haque

&

MD Emrul Haque

For their motivation and financial support throughout the study.

To my wife:

Bushra Jannat Lina

For all the support to keep me on track.

&

To my son

Yamin Haque

For enhancing my spirit

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

All tribute to Almighty ALLAH, the Beneficent, the Merciful.

I am very glad to take the opportunity for expressing my gratitude to everyone who has helped me achieve the task.

Firstly, I am deeply indebted to all the University of the West of Scotland officials who paved the opportunity to conduct the research. My PhD journey has immensely benefited from the mentorship and support of my directors of studies, Dr. Khalid Bichou and Dr. Mizan Rahman. I also convey my heartfelt gratitude to them for their time, guidance, suggestion, and feedback throughout the study, which enabled me to remain on track. It would have been difficult for me to remain consistent and focused without their guidance to complete the research.

Secondly, my sincere appreciation to all the hotel and shared accommodation managers who had given me access to the hotel portals and their premises to carry out the primary data collection. In addition, a very special thanks to Nawsher Ahmed Sikder, Post Graduate Researcher of University of Nottingham, Mizan Rashid, Senior data scientist, REPL group) and Tanvir Alom (FCCA) for their specialised support in pilot testing, statistical analysis, and proofreading. Their feedback assisted me to present the thesis in a structured way.

My gratefulness is also extended to all the peer DBA candidates of the University of the West of Scotland and whom I could not mention above for all the support, advice, motivation to keep me mentally strong during the tough time.

I also owe the deepest gratitude to my parents Md. Nurul Hoque and Jahanara Hoque, my wife Bushra Jannat Lina, and my son Yamin Haque for unconditional love and belief are the key sources of my inspiration.

Declaration:

I declare that this research paper is entirely my work. To the best of my knowledge, no section has been submitted for any qualification or publication, and any information taken from any previous research is appropriately referenced. The author retains the rights of this thesis, although properly acknowledged citation is permitted.

Abstract

Analysing the service quality gaps between traditional hotels and shared accommodation: a study on customer gap in central London

This research examined the customer gap in service quality factors between the traditional hotel industry and the shared accommodation in central London. While the study examines the literature and theoretical background of service quality in the hospitality industry, the focus is on practical service quality issues, most notably the gap that exists between customers' perceptions and expectations.

This study used a deductive approach while adhering to the positivist paradigm. This research is designed as quantitative research based on the questionnaire survey. SERVQUAL model was amended as LSQUAL framework according to the industry specification for this research. LSQUAL framework includes the appropriate factors for evaluating service quality gaps between the hotel and shared accommodation in central London.

A total of 298 hotel and shared accommodation guests were surveyed to measure the service quality gap between conventional hotels and shared accommodation. The survey result revealed that there exists a service quality gap between traditional hotels and shared accommodation. This study found that accommodation guests' expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation remains the same; however, the perception towards both type of accommodation differs. Data analysis also revealed that there exists a negative correlation between the service quality gap and satisfaction level.

Furthermore, given the gap in comparing customer gap between the traditional hotel and shared accommodation in the literature, this study added further value to the academic and research community by developing the LSQUAL framework to measure service quality factors and providing insight on the critical factors of service quality in the lodging industry in London.

Keywords: Service Quality, SERVQUAL, LSQUAL, Expectation, Perception, Customer gap.

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CHAPTER 1: RESEARCH BACKGROUND

1.1 Introduction:

Service quality has a significant role in the lodging industry as this sector has been considered to be very highly competitive in recent years. Perceptions and expectations on the level of service qualities are vital factors behind hotel and accommodation choice, and customers tend to evaluate the service quality factors before choosing an accommodation service provider (Ezebilo, 2013). At the same time, accommodation service providers need to understand the drivers and features of services quality to improve their services for the sake of increasing customer base and retaining customer loyalty (Gryszel, 2015). To stay ahead in the competition, the hotel and shared accommodation providers need to keep a high standard of service quality to meet up customers' expectations. The competition among the accommodation providers is growing along with the new hotel rooms and accommodations listings. The completion has got various dimensions, particularly in multicultural cities like London.

London is one of the most visited cities globally, and millions of visitors visit this city every year. The visitors need to depend on hotels and other accommodation service providers to stay overnight during their visit. According to the statistics, the occupancy rate in London has been continuously increasing over the past decade. Each year new hotel rooms and accommodation establishments are added to meet the demand of the increasing occupancy rate (PwC, 2018). In addition to traditional hospitality providers, new types of providers have come to the market owing to the popularity of the shared accommodation concept, which has increased rapidly over the past decade and created a new era of competition in the tourism and hospitality sector (Shabrina, Arcaute and Batty, 2021). As competition intensifies, hotels and shared accommodation providers must achieve high customer service quality levels to balance the customer's expectations and perception and stay ahead of the competition (Chang and Sokol, 2020).

Several researchers have acknowledged the importance of the service quality factors for traditional hotels and shared accommodation. Pervious researchers have also found that there exist gaps in various dimensions of service quality factors. However, the drivers, and

potential differences, of service quality factors between traditional hotels and shared accommodation are yet to be thoroughly investigated and analysed (Rauch *et al.*, 2015).

This research attempts to examine the features and differences of service quality factors between the traditional hotel and the shared accommodation in central London. While the research examines the literature and theoretical background of service quality in the hospitality industry, the focus is on practical service quality issues, most notably customers' perceptions and expectations. The objective is to advance practical knowledge, a core component of the DBA research, by helping traditional hotels and shared accommodation providers gain an enhanced understanding of service quality factors and drivers as viewed and perceived by their customers. Furthermore, this study aims to add further value to the academic and research community by providing insight on the critical factors of service quality in the hospitality industry in central London, and where applicable, the differences and variations in those factors between conventional hotels and shared accommodation services.

1.2: Rationale for this research:

The researcher has almost eight years of experience working in the hospitality industry, serving as a customer service manager in a reputed chain hotel in London. The work experience of the researcher has given me the opportunity to get engaged directly with hotel customers and deal with the hotel service quality factors. Thus, the researcher has experienced customers of the hotels are highly concerned about the service quality factors of the accommodation services and get the inspiration to conduct a research on this field. Moreover, the researcher has also found that the lodging industry is highly competitive, and the competition is gradually increasing. To stay in the competition, hotel and accommodation service providers are concerned about the service quality factors as the overall feedback for the quality standard lies on the service quality factors (Dedeoglu and Demirer, 2015). However, the hotel and accommodation service providers cannot fully satisfy every single customer as the diverse nature of human characteristics (Lu *et al.*, 2015). The hotel and accommodation service providers are very keen to know about the service quality gaps and the influence of the gap on satisfaction (Jade Conroy, 2018).

The researcher has a strong educational background in the field of business management and leadership. To obtain the highest and precious degree in business administration is the

cherished desire of the researcher that will help the researcher a smooth future career path. In addition, the passion for travel and tourism influenced the researcher's decision to go further with academic research.

The researcher has been living in the central part of London for the last eight years to pursue higher education. The multicultural dynamism of the city has created a deep passion for the city. To establish a bridge within the educational background, work experience in the related field and living experience, the researcher was motivated to carry out the research on the service quality factors in the lodging industry.

1.3 Aim of the research:

This research study is primarily intended to analyse the gap of service quality factors between traditional hotels and shared accommodation.

As service quality is the core competence factor for traditional hotels and shared accommodation, the gap in the service quality factors will be measured by amending the SERVQUAL model into an industry-specific LSQUAL framework.

1.4 Research objectives:

To address the key research question along with the sub-questions, the following objective has been undertaken for the proposed research

1. Find out the gaps in the service quality factors between traditional hotels and shared accommodation.
2. To evaluate the expectation for both the traditional hotel and shared accommodation guests.
3. To evaluate the perception for both the traditional hotel and shared accommodation guests.
4. To test the reliability of the LSQUAL model for hotels and shared accommodation.
5. To establish the impact of the satisfaction level on a future recommendation.
6. To establish the correlation between the customer gap and satisfaction level.

1.5 Research questions:

“How does the gap of the service quality gap in the hotels differ from shared accommodations?”

To address the key question of the research mentioned above. Several sub-questions will also arise to answer the key question of the research. The sub-questions are given below

1. How does the service quality differ between conventional hotels and shared accommodation?
2. Do the hotels and shared accommodation have the same level of the customer's expectation?
3. Do the hotels and shared accommodation have the same level of the customer's perception?
4. How does the gap of the service quality factors influence the choice of future accommodation?
5. How does the customer gap influence the satisfaction level?

1.6 Methodology:

This DBA study aims to examine the service quality gap between traditional hotels and shared accommodation. Therefore, this study used a deductive approach while adhering to the positivist paradigm. This research is designed as quantitative research based on the questionnaire survey.

SERVQUAL model was used as a foundation of this research; however, the SERVQUAL model needed to amend as LSQUAL framework according to the industry specification for this research. LSQUAL framework includes the appropriate factors for evaluating service quality gaps between the hotel and shared accommodation in central London.

This DBA study used a multi-methodology approach (triangulation), which combines the collection of both qualitative and quantitative data in one setting. All of the data obtained via different techniques were combined in accordance with the goal of triangulation in the final database, which is to arrive at the same conclusions by utilising data collected through various sources.

During the different phases of this doctoral research, comprehensive preliminary research, i.e., literature reviews, content analysis, was undertaken on a variety of subjects, including the hospitality sector, service efficiency, customer loyalty, the SERVQUAL model, the hospitality industry, and lodging providers.

A modified questionnaire was adapted based on the in-depth content analysis research on the booking channel extranet, like booking.com, TripAdvisor, Expedia Airbnb etc., in addition to the review of the literature on service efficiency and SERVQUAL method itself. The questionnaire was split into three segments; section 1 comprises a few demographic factors and two accommodation related questions. Section 2 contains the 22 Expectation and 22 Perception questions followed by 4 added post-stay feedback queries to identify the satisfaction and likelihood to recommend factors. Based on the SRVQUAL framework, the 22 expectation and perception questions were adapted as per the five dimensions of the service quality framework.

In this study, personal distribution of the questionnaire was deemed the most effective approach, however considering the current pandemic situation and social restrictions measures, online platforms and professional networks have been used to deliver the questionnaire. The questionnaires were distributed to the hotel and shared accommodation guests across central London.

The sample size was calculated as 378 using the online sample size calculator tool. A cluster sampling followed by a simple random sampling method was applied to choose the participants for this research.

Cronbach's Alpha was conducted to test the reliability of the data. Cross tabulation was used to determine the frequency of the guest's perception and expectations response. To analyse the gap of the expectation and mean and analysis was executed. Moreover, one way ANOVA and Spearman's rank correlation was carried out to test the research hypothesis. Finally, based on the spss analysis, the data were presented in graphical and tabular format along with the necessary discussion and interpretation.

1.7 Significance of the study to the research body:

This study on the service quality gap analysis between the hotel and shared accommodation will contribute to the current body of knowledge in the hospitality industry in a variety of ways. Since the aim of the research was to analyse the service quality gap between the traditional hotels and the shared accommodation, this study proposed an industry-specific modified SERVQUAL model named as LSQUAL framework to measure the service quality gap in the lodging industry, which is a contribution to the research body.

The LSQUAL framework developed for this research to undertake a questionnaire survey in the accommodation sector can be used for further research in the service industry; however, the factors need to be amended according to the service sector

The service quality gap between conventional hotels and shared accommodation has been identified in this paper using the LSQUAL framework. Stakeholders in the accommodation industry can use the outcome of this paper to address the service quality gap and take essential steps to balance customers' expectations and perceptions.

To meet the research objectives, this paper measured accommodation guests' expectations and perceptions towards hotels and shared accommodation. To stay ahead in the business, accommodation providers can address the guest's expectation and perceptions gap from this paper and design their promotional campaign addressing the customer gap.

This paper has also measured the correlation between the service quality gap and guest satisfaction level. Accommodation providers need to balance the gap to achieve maximum guest satisfaction levels.

Finally, this paper has established that there exists a perfect negative correlation between the gap of the service quality factors and the satisfaction level of accommodation guests.

1.8 Structure of the thesis:

The study is organised logically and methodically, consisting of six chapters. A brief description of the chapters is given below

The first chapter provides an overview of the study paper. This chapter discusses the study's purpose and goal, as well as the research questions and hypotheses. Additionally, this chapter addresses the study's methodology and relevance to the current body of information.

The second chapter was organised into two parts. The first part is devoted to a comprehensive survey of the literature on hotels and shared housing. This part also discussed the London tourist market and the hotel sector in the United Kingdom. The second part of the literature review focused on the literature on service quality determinants, customer loyalty, service quality frameworks, SERVQUAL model and their application in the hotel sector.

Chapter three discusses in depth the methods utilised to conduct the study. This chapter concentrated on the research strategy, research philosophy, study design, sampling, and the technique of collecting primary and secondary data, questionnaire, and statistical analysis tools.

Chapter four analysed the study findings. The key focuses were on the results about the service quality gap and the hypothesis test.

A detailed discussion on the empirical findings was conducted in chapter five.

Chapter six summarises the paper, as well as the research limitations and future research opportunities and contribution to the research body.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction:

The aim of this chapter is to review the existing literatures on the service quality factors in different sectors with a special focus on the hospitality industry in the UK as the analysis of the related literature is a central aspect of any academic study for providing a solid basis for information advancement. This chapter consists of two parts. The first part emphasis on the features and differences between the traditional hotel industry and the shared accommodation service industry, with particular attention on central London and its tourism market. The second part reviews the literature on the interaction between the quality of service and customer satisfaction and its applications in the hotel and shared accommodations industry.

2.2: Part 1:

2.2.1 Review of the Taxonomy and Segments of the Hospitality Industry:

The hospitality industry includes a wide variety of business segments compared to the other industries. Customer service is the key focus in the hospitality industry. This industry mainly consists of Accommodation, Travel and Tourism, and Food and Beverage and Recreation segments with a common focus of serving the customer with maximum satisfaction. The accommodations' sector covers various lodging businesses like hotels, motels, and other economy accommodations.

In general, the hospitality and tourism industries are often overlapping in different subcategories. There exists a wide confusion through categorising hospitality and tourism as the same industry; however, a clear line should be drawn to identify these industries as two separate sectors (Leiper, 2008). Although these two sectors always overlap, the tourism industry should be limited to the activities of an individual on the go outside the familiar living environment for a limited period for various purposes, while the hospitality industry should be dealing with the accommodation and food services outside the general living environment, in general, the following figure shows out the mapping of the tourism and hospitality industry.

Figure 1: Adapted from (Cooper, 2018)

According to the figure above, it is difficult to distinguish the logging sector from the hospitality industry and the tourism industry. For this research, hotels and shared accommodation was considered as a part of both the tourism industry and the hospitality industry.

2.2 The hospitality industry in the UK:

The UK hotel business is another service area that has recognised the importance of offering both product and service quality, although most of the industry still struggles with the idea of continuously providing high service quality (Kwong D, 2017). The hospitality sector in the United Kingdom encompasses a diverse variety of hotel and catering companies, ranging from luxurious to primary and a diverse range of service offerings ranging from comprehensive to restricted. Historically, service quality has been connected with the market, where high inflation can meet the expenses of high staff-to-customer ratios and various services offered (Crafts, 2015). At the same time, little resources are allocated to the price-sensitive end of the market, where service levels are relatively limited. However, the quick and profitable expansion of economic and regional retail chains demonstrates that customer requirements quality can be delivered at the entry-level and price-sensitive segments of the sector, not only in the current market (Hix, 2018).

The concepts of chain restaurants, where goods are often essential and service levels are frequently restricted, are increasingly adapted to the lodging industry. Accommodation services are being created to suit the requirements of consumers more accurately. Due to a dearth of decent quality lodging accessible at affordable rates in the UK, hotels and shared accommodations are increasingly being constructed to offer guests staying with basic but pleasant overnight housing amenities, complemented with restricted but competent service quality (Gurran and Whitehead, 2011). These specific types of lodging are often referred to as 'serviced apartments,' or shared accommodation, and the growth of this industry in the UK is comparatively modern in contrast to comparable developments in other countries (Neoh, 2018).

A subset of the accommodation sector represents those accommodation units strategically placed across the United Kingdom and intended primarily for short and extended stay guests. Due to its minimal but necessary amenities and services, these businesses may run at a reasonable cost and charge less than most other places providing comparable regular guestrooms. Numerous businesses currently operate shared housing in the United Kingdom, with the majority intending to create a broad infrastructure of shared housing (Lee and Kim, 2017). This degree of expansion indicates that there is still an established and stable competitive pressure for such lodging and that providers' economic possibilities are very compelling, regardless of the level of market demands. If the current rate of development in shared housing in the UK continues, likely, availability may ultimately surpass demand in some areas (Lee and Kim, 2017). Increased supply results in decreased prices, which results in decreased revenue (Razavi and Israeli, 2019). Additionally, several shared house providers have introduced so many amenities and services that they have been forced to increase prices, putting them directly in conflict with the full-service industry, which faces similar levels of competition (Kostkova, 2020).

While it is erroneous to believe that the UK lodge sector would replicate the US lodge sector, many parallels between the two markets indicate that the UK's advances are following a similar path to the US example. If UK providers react to competitive pressures by expanding services and infrastructure or maintaining low rates, they are likely to face similar problems as many US providers (Jones, Hillier and Comfort, 2014). However, one of the largest lodge operators in the United States is attempting to circumvent this issue by conducting extensive

customer interviews to ascertain unaddressed and dissatisfied needs and enhancing information flow with its staff members and distribution partners to ensure that decent products or service quality are performed consistently. The same level of attention is paid to service quality in the United Kingdom. However, the idea of service quality and the execution of high-quality service may remain a challenge for lodge owners to pursue, mainly if they are uncertain of its exact meaning.

2.2.3 London tourism market:

London is one of the most well-known European destinations based on its history, festivals, museums, and heritage. It is renowned for its arts, tradition, heritage, world-class museums, art, nightlife, and Royal Parks (Shengnan and Nedelea, 2018). London hosts a wide range of activities. London can always show its lively city lifestyle to tourists from music and film festivals to big sporting competitions and dazzling flower displays. These include celebrating different day types, cultural events, different races, seminars, conferences, religious events, sporting events, carnivals, etc. London remains busy round the year to organize events where the participants join worldwide (Visit London, 2021). Hospitality is another significant aspect in drawing visitors to London. Attractions are at the heart of the London tourist industry. Nations with thriving economy emphasise appropriate strategies to build hospitality industry and tourism infrastructure (Chowdhury, 2019). The official advertising agency is London & Partners. Their goal is to express London's story to a foreign audience in a brilliant way (London&partners, 2018). To satisfy the demands of global visitors, the tourism industry must develop the appropriate goods. History, nature, fitness, adventure vacations, and business tourism are the key tourism items in London (Maxim, 2019).

In the year 2016, 19.1 million visitors (Jonathan, P. 2017) and almost 20 million in 2017 (CNN, 2017) visited this city; London is the second most visited city in the world and the most visited in Europe (CNN, 2017). Indeed, more than half of all visitors to the United Kingdom come to London (London&partner. 2017). It is vital to the tourism industry in the United Kingdom.

According to statistics from visitbritain.org (2020), the number of foreign visitors, the total nights spent, and the total spending have gradually risen. Since 2010, visitors have increased by 5.21 per cent to 22 million, total nights have increased by 4.16 per cent to 118 million, and

total spending has increased by 1.65 per cent to £28.48 million. Furthermore, according to London&partner (2017), the London tourism sector employs about 700,000 people, accounts for 1/7 of all employment, and generates 11.6 per cent of the city's GDP.

Table 1: London Visit statistics-(Tourism statistics - City of London, 2021)

London Visit statistics by year					
Year	Number of visits (M)	Spending (£bn)	Spending per/visit (Avg)	Nights per visit (AVG)	Overnight stays (M)
2010	14.71	£8.71	£586	7.9	90.33
2011	15.27	£9.41	£595	7.7	91.50
2012	15.5	£10	£614	7.6	94.31
2013	16.81	£11.49	£663	7.6	98.11
2014	17.57	£11.83	£663	7.9	108.11
2015	18.60	£11.92	£648	7.7	108.30
2016	19.10	£11.90	£650	7.7	111.60
2017	19.80	£13.54	£691	7.6	114.10
2018	19.10	£12.33	£658	7.2	110.90
2019	21.71	£15.30	£696	7.1	118.90

In the tourism industry in London, appreciation refers to a sense of welcome and hospitality. According to the London Visitor Survey, customer loyalty is 79 per cent dependent on activities, entertainment, shopping, transportation, and other factors (London Visitor Survey (London&Partners, 2017)). Over 4,000 individuals from 11 different sectors took part in the London Visitor Survey. It reveals that society and activities are the most rewarding facets of life.

London's 2025 strategy is to draw more than 40 million visitors, up from 31.2 million in 2016. To do so, the city's authorities prioritized supplying tourists with accurate statistics, upgrading visitor apps, information centers, maps, and language support, expanding infrastructure capabilities such as airports, subways, hotels, and public Wi-Fi, and forging close partnerships with the rest of the UK cities. Chinese tourists are the fastest-growing

market for London tourism, according to the top 25 overseas markets, with a 103 per cent growth in visitors since 2011 (Statista, 2021).

As per London & Partners (2017), London visitors are categorised as followed

- recreation (43.1%),
- enterprise (21.4%),
- VFR (30.4%),
- Others (5.1 per cent).

Leisure and business tourism will be a focus in the future industry. With 3.6 million commuters, London was rated third in the ICCA (2017) rankings. VFRs typically travel to see friends and family, but they spend less on accommodation. VFR is mostly used to visiting friends and relatives, and because people spend less money on meals, accommodation, and travel, it is classified as a low-cost mode of transportation.

2.2.4 Traditional hotel versus shared accommodation: The business models:

The hotel industry constitutes the commercial establishments providing accommodation services for short term visitors in the hospitality sector Camilleri M.A. (2018). People take the accommodation service to meet the purposes that cannot be done staying at a normal leaving place. The hotel sector has experienced a major escalation in the last century (Jenkins, 2002). The demand for hotels is growing simultaneously with the growth of the tourism industry (British Hospitality Association, 2018). Traditional hotels normally provide bed and breakfast services (Slattery, 2002). Unlike hotels, the concept of shared accommodation lies in sharing unutilised assets for economic benefit (Psarros et al., 2014). Homeowners can share spare accommodation for the short term, not only for monetary benefit but also for utilising idle assets. Airbnb has excelled at the idea of sharing accommodation by creating an online platform for letting spare rooms for commercial uses (Psarros et al., 2014).

The sharing economy is an economic model that enables individuals to pool their resources. It is defined as a peer-to-peer (P2P) business focused on buying, providing, and providing access to goods and services, often facilitated via an online social platform (Chen and Wang, 2019). The sharing economy is an economic or commercial concept. By integrating human

and physical resources, this approach facilitates the exchange of goods and services between consumers and sellers. This entails a group of individuals using products and services that they jointly own and value. The sharing economy, alternatively referred to as peer-to-peer facilities or participatory interchange, has grown in popularity over the past decade, leading to a shift in owning and revenue growth.

Over the last few years, the social economy has developed into an all-encompassing term that refers to various online economic exchanges, including business to business (B2B) experiences (Netter, Pedersen, and Ludeke-Freund, 2019). The below are some of the other networks that have entered the sharing economy:

- Businesses offer collaborative, flexible work environments in major metropolitan areas for freelancers, start-ups, and work-from-home workers.
- Companies enable individuals to lend money to others at reduced interest rates than those provided by conventional credit lending institutions.
- Platforms that enable people to rent or sell their clothing.
- Portals that help freelancers find jobs in a range of areas, from conventional freelance work to resources previously reserved for handypersons. The sharing economy is projected to expand from \$14 billion in 2014 to \$335 billion by 2025, owing largely to the rise of Uber and Airbnb

Airbnb, Fastly, and Couch Surfing are examples of shared economy applications in the hospitality industry (PwC, 2015). The sharing economy's acceleration has fuelled Airbnb's market expansion; in 2015, the company received approximately 800,000 properties in 190 nations and around 20 million online members (Scholdan & Straaten, 2015).

According to a Boston University survey, a 1% rise in Accommodation options could result in a 0.05 per cent reduction in hotel sales (Nguyen, 2014). Furthermore, from around 50,000 in 2011 to 550,000 in 2014, the number of properties had risen by roughly tenfold (Nguyen, 2014). Revenues from the sharing economy increased from €10 bn in 2013 to €28 bn in 2015, according to PwC (2016). In the European zone, the number is projected to increase to €570 billion in 2015. (PwC, 2016).

The revaluation of the internet era has created the opportunity for both accommodation providers and customers to exchange services and values (Chathoth, 2007). According to

Oskam and Boswijk (2015), Airbnb has risen to its peak in the last couple of years with the shared economy concept. Richardson (2015) identified that Airbnb comprises the following three elements.

- Digital platform for connecting service provider and customer
- Peer to peer accommodation
- Access basis instead of ownership

2.2.5 Airbnb as the main provider of shared accommodation hospitality:

Airbnb, the world's largest peer-to-peer sharing service for accommodation, keeps expanding. Certain individuals have proposed that Airbnb accommodations be regulated similarly to hotels and that Airbnb providers be subject to hotel revenue taxes (Roma, Panniello and Lo Nigro, 2019). Airbnb asserts that their business model is straightforward: it links hosts with short-term subleasing that lend out their personal property. While prominent hoteliers such as Marriott, Four Seasons, and Hilton have said that their hotel tourists' main characteristics are drastically different from Airbnb's visitors or because their profits have still not been impacted, many would believe that in this era of the internet revolution, the hospitality business has been adversely impacted by the emergence of Airbnb (Dewan, Kim and Nian, 2019).

The underlying variations between hotel business and Airbnb could be revealed by recognising the pricing model, Airbnb's key market, and a number of other considerations. Since its founding in 2008, Airbnb has experienced exponential growth. Airbnb has developed itself to be the main peer-to-peer accommodation service, with \$2.6 billion in sales in 2018 (Guttentag, 2013). Airbnb's marketing strategy revolves around a platform that allows guests and hosts to swap accommodation for income. Guests and hosts can find feedback and social media links during the procedure, which helps to create loyalty among platform members (Munoz and Cohen, 2017). This strategy is not exclusive to Airbnb, but it is a good one. Via a variety of online outlets, users can determine their perceptions and influence potential customer decisions as a result of the influx of new technologies. Though board rating services are not fully accessible on all web pages, third-party portals like Yelp and Expedia can help (Dec and Masiukiewicz, 2018)

If Airbnb facilitates peer-to-peer transactions, it has no direct influence on the rates of accommodation provided by hosts. While leasing their properties on Airbnb, hosts obey rules close that are used by hotels (Peng, 2020). Guests who stay for less than seven nights are expected to pay more than those who stay for longer periods of time. While advertising their property on Airbnb, homeowners will negotiate rates for single nights, frequent visits, maintenance expenses, weekend rates, and extra visitors. Rooms are more expensive on weekends, vacations, but when the number of visitors exceeds the number of seats, much as in hotels (Roma, Panniello and Lo Nigro, 2019). Hotel stays, on the other hand, may not have a cleaning fee, and also, most properties provide in-house cleaning facilities. Besides that, in high-demand places such as metropolitan areas or around tourist destinations, guest rooms and Airbnb accommodation seem to be more costly (Cui, Orhun and Hu, 2018). It is also uncertain if Airbnb's exponential success has had an impact on the hotel business. Privilege and corporate tourists visit large hotel franchises, including Hilton and Marriott. Airbnb is not in the same league; it features low-cost holiday accommodation and convenient surroundings.

So far, Airbnb has got away with violating a number of rental and accommodation tax rules. For hosts, rules and legal structures may be a major issue. Tenant regulations occur in several jurisdictions, in which guests who remain in a leased room for longer than 30 days are given tenant rights (Zupan, 2018). Furthermore, subletting a residential space is prohibited in some jurisdictions (Li and Srinivasan, 2018). Besides that, subletting a residential space such as a bedroom, studio, or room for less than 30 days is prohibited in some countries if the occupant is exactly alike as the visitor (Rights of tenants to sublet their home, 2021).

Although Airbnb renting and luxury hotels do not mix, both budget and traditional hotels may have suffered challenges due to Airbnb. A typical hotel suite includes a bed, toilet, and wardrobe, all of which are of differing degrees of comfort. On the other hand, a typical apartment contains not only certain luxuries as a hotel suite but also a kitchen and a greater living area. Airbnb has steered out of the high-end lodging market. Visitors who report their expenses to their companies, on the other hand, are increasingly using Airbnb for business travel. The presence of fees and limitations on short-term rentals distinguishes the hotel business from Airbnb.

2.2.6 Airbnb's working platform:

According to Zervas et al. (2015), Airbnb is an interactive online renting site that provides anything from shared rooms to complete assets. According to PwC (2015), Shared accommodation had a total of 425,000 visitors a night in 2015, which was about 22% more than Hilton Worldwide. As a result, the hotels face a significant rivalry in listings from Airbnb (Cui, Orhun and Hu, 2018). Airbnb has been named another very influential peer-to-peer platform in the hospitality business for epitomising the sharing economy. Airbnb has extended its industry to world markets in less than eight years, covering over 191 nations and 65,000 towns and attracting over 60 million people to exclusive travel tips (Airbnb (2016). As per Zervas, Proserpio, and Byers (2016), Airbnb is now a replacement for customers who make hotel reservations, which has hugely affected the conventional hospitality sector.

Furthermore, despite Airbnb is not even owning a single room, it is expected to replace Marriott as the leading hotel network (Carr, 2015). Airbnb was created as a result of the sharing economy, and it ideally exemplifies the sharing economy's most unique characteristics: allowing the community to collectively enable usage underutilised supply through fee-based rental (Zervas et al., 2015). Airbnb's success is fuelled by technology, and it helps the business run and is focused on internet purchases. (Daugherty, 2016). Airbnb mainly interacts with its customers via online platforms like the online site and social networks. (Oskam & Boswijk, 2016).

Furthermore, the rapid expansion of Airbnb can indeed be linked back to the financial crisis, while uncertainty decreased people's bargaining power and they began to save money. New tech and the economic downturn are behind Airbnb's exponential rentals, affecting accommodation sales. (Scholdan & Straaten, 2015).

Airbnb's main business is service fees through reservations, which are credited to both travellers and owners. Customers are asked to pay a prepaid service charge based on the choice of listing and the length of the booking. Since households or organisations with longer stays may save costs on much other travel and accommodation, a more costly booking results in reduced service charges for visitors. In addition, homeowners are paid a 3% fee on each successful reservation to offset the cost of handling guest payments. For Airbnb Plus listings, the fee could be higher. The customer pays the service charge after a booking is

made until the provider cancels or reverses the entry. Airbnb changes service charges to suit guests if the arrangement is changed. According to policymakers and the hospitality industry, long-term rental properties are being turned into de facto hotels, raising rental rates and competitive pressures for hotel chains (Chattopadhyay and Mitra, 2019).

2.2.6 Hotels vs Shared accommodation: competition and rivalry:

Since the last decade, the hotel industry has been facing an increasing threat from the sharing economy accommodation. The online platform Airbnb is one of the best examples of these disruptions to the hotel business model.

Shared accommodation is becoming familiar and popular in the travel and tourism industry, which is becoming the major disrupting competitor for the traditional hotel business. (Scholdan & Straaten, 2015). Due to the growing concept of sharing accommodation, competition has got a new dimension in the accommodation market (Netsiporuk, 2016). Minimising the cost of accommodation along with maximising the value and creating close interaction with the location-based community is the motto of the accommodation seekers in recent years (Panda, Verma, & Mehta, 2015). Airbnb has created this platform to create income opportunities for landlords through the underutilised property (Zervas, Proserpio, & Byers, 2015). Airbnb has also reported the company's exceptional growth in sharing accommodation in the last decade (Airbnb, 2016).

Technological convergence and advancement in the IT sector have helped the shared accommodation concept to grow rapidly. Airbnb has created its strong position in this shared accommodation platform (Gerdeman, 2018). The presence of Airbnb has created a momentous influence to transform the travel and tourism industry. In addition to the individual travellers, local organisations and communities are positively impacted through the Airbnb platform. (Panda et al., 2015). Whether or not Airbnb would pose a challenge to the conventional hotel business is still a matter of debate. According to Quinones and Augustine (2015), conventional hotels may experience competitive pressures from Airbnb that have pushed hotels to cut rates throughout peak demand seasons to ensure efficiency. Zervas, Proserpio, and Byers all agree with this conclusion (2016).

Shared accommodation has the ability to change rates throughout peak seasons, reducing hotels' purchasing capacity. Furthermore, Airbnb is shifting consumers' perceptions about

conventional hotels; for example, according to a survey by the San Francisco Financial Times, visitors have lowered their probability of booking a hotel from 79 per cent to 40 per cent as a result of Airbnb, although the luxury hotel does not have the same issue.

Mark Hoplamazian, the CEO of Hyatt Hotels Corporation, said that a company answer to Airbnb, which offers a separate product within a unique brand category, is unnecessary (Santoli, 2014). According to a Harvard Business School professor, Airbnb lacks the potential to compete with the global hospitality sector due to a number of flaws in its design (Goree, 2016).

Guttentag, D. and Smith, S. (2017) have assessed the traditional hotels and Airbnb accommodation with a view to finding out whether Airbnb is creating an increasing threat for the hotels as a substitute. The researchers have applied a deductive approach for their research and surveyed online with a questionnaire. The research has found that more than 64% of Airbnb guests are using Airbnb accommodation as a substitute for traditional hotels. As a result of increasing popularity and consistency, Airbnb is expected not only to perform better than budget hotels but also to risk upscale hotels performance (Schäfer and Tran, 2020). The researchers suggested that to get a better knowledge of the processes involved in the design of Airbnb accommodation, guests' expectations on accommodation attributes need to be compared.

Zervas, Proserpio and Byers (2017) have researched the impact that the hotels in Texas may face with the launch of Airbnb accommodation. For the research, the researchers have used secondary data from the accommodation and travel industry to collect hotel and Airbnb listing, revenue, price, occupancy rate, and guest reviews. Their quantitative analysis has revealed that the launching of Airbnb would negatively impact hotel revenue while to compete on the market, the viable hotel room pricing would be an added benefit for the customers.

Camilleri, J. and Neuhofer, B. (2017) have researched the sharing economy to find out how Airbnb can co-create and co-destruct value in the accommodation industry. The aim was to uncover the transformation process of the sharing economy and mutual consumption in the hospitality industry. Guest reviews and host feedback was considered for this qualitative research. Co-creation and co-destruction of value in guest-host social practises have been

given a theoretical framework in order to have a better grasp of the situation distinctive value propositions in sharing economy like Airbnb. The key finding was that the value is formulated through the interaction between host and guest by six distinct social norms, which are greeting, expression, evaluation of location and accommodation, interaction, recommendation, and gratitude. Moreover, the study also reveals that both Airbnb and traditional accommodation possess almost the same value; however, guest and host interaction and social norms make a difference in value co-creation.

This chapter summarises the literature on hotel and shared accommodation services, the London tourist market, and the hospitality sector in the United Kingdom. The next chapter will discuss the literature regarding service quality and customer loyalty, as well as its use in the hotel sector.

2.3: Part-2:

2.3.1 Service quality concept and the hospitality industry:

This part provides an overview discussion of service quality factors in the accommodation sector, including gaps in the service quality factor, SERVQUAL model, hotel guests' perception and expectations. It also examines Parasuraman's world-famous SERVQUAL model, including distance study, the model's five dimensions, and related factors, including its validity to different sectors. Other operational efficiency frameworks are also analysed in order to determine if the SERVQUAL instrument is the most suitable for this research. The final section of this review discusses several elements of service performance. The value of service quality in hotels and shared lodging is also discussed. The final segment explains how the SERVQUAL concept can be updated to be more market-specific for the lodging industry. The following section discusses the various service quality concept in the hospitality sector.

2.3.2 Service quality: Background

Quality is an entirely subjective and difficult-to-define concept (Frank and Enkawa, 2009), owing to characteristics such as being quantitative and contextual at the same time; parameters of its variables can be calculated, but some can only be assessed; the quality can refer to a practical level; and, ultimately, it has both perceptible usage implications and consequences that the consumer is not actively aware of. (Prameka, Do and Rofiq, 2016).

Quality was initially associated with tangible goods. The following developments were characterised by an increase in the efficiency of intangible product services. (Becser, 2007).

The term "service", according to (Silvestro and Johnson, 1990), is commonly used to describe an industry that "makes" things for you rather than "making" things. In comparison to the commercial service industry, "service" also refers to companies that address consumer demands (Zhang, 2013).

The majority of research on service quality have concluded that facilities are largely interactive in nature even though they are subjective and impossible to quantify. As (Zeithaml, 1988; Chang, 2008) define service quality as "the consumer's opinion regarding a product's relating to the superiority or dominance," marketing management review looked at quality from the viewpoint of the consumer (Abu Hasan et al. 2008).

The capacity to meet consumer demands is a crucial element of the consistent idea, but it is not the most important. "While interpretations of service quality differ, all concepts are constructed from the consumer perspective: that is, what consumers consider as essential aspects of quality," according to Clemes et al. (2008).

Quality has been defined as a type of complete service evaluation, whereas presumed quality, according to Zeithaml (1987), is the customer's assessment of an entity's professional ability or supremacy. In a dynamic market, service quality is a must to successfully succeed, stay profitable, and prosper (Angelova and Zekiri, 2011). Besides that, they claim that if efficiency exceeds requirements, the anticipated output would be more than adequate, resulting in higher consumer loyalty. Despite its reputation as a nebulous term, service quality assessment has sparked a lot of curiosity and controversy in scholarly papers. This controversy has arisen mainly as a result of the service's dynamic, complex, perishable, and distinct existence (Levy and Hino, 2016)

Simpson et al. (2001) found that implementing a customer-value model has service at the centrepiece of a business's efforts to improve its efficiency. Zeithaml et al. (1990) and Saravanan and Rao (2007) claim that almost all entities would experience significant rivalry for customers. Negi (2009) and Ladhari (2009) found that delivering high-quality service to consumers keeps them, draws new clients, boosts the company identity, promotes good word-of-mouth reviews, and, most importantly, maximize profit. As per Svan Iwaarden and van der

Valk (2013), consumers are believed to be correct as they complain about a business's service level and if they think anything is wrong. According to Parasuraman et al. (1991), maintaining excellent performance in the service sector is perhaps the most successful way to ensure that a firm's services are clearly intended in an industry packed with similar competing brands. Several researchers, including (Lin and Lekhawipat, 2016), Lovelock and Wirtz (2007), found the service quality very difficult to define. Researchers contend that the essence of quality service necessitates a distinct style for identifying and measuring it.

Customer expectations may differ from their actual service experiences, which influence service quality. However, it is unclear yet which of the many variables is the most important in affecting service quality. Hu et al. (2019) established the concept of service quality for consumers and developed techniques to satisfy their needs. Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry were influenced by Lehtinen and Lehtinen's (1982) work to conduct a systematic methodological study to better identify service efficiency (Parasuraman et al. 1985). Parasuraman and his colleagues undertook a detailed approach to create a quantitative framework to measure quality. To generate insights into the study issues they planned, they undertook in-depth interviews with managers at widely renowned service companies as well as a series of focus group discussions with customers. Gap assessment was performed using ten interpretive dimensions or parameters that included a wide range of programmes and the logical service quality framework. The premise would be that the difference within consumers. The expectations people have for a service and the various ways in which they comprehend what they presently get from the service provider are two critical factors when it comes to evaluating the service quality (Tsionas, Assaf, Gillen and Mattila, 2017). Service quality is regarded as a crucial component of service distinction, and it is an area that any company that wants to remain in business must handle. It has an impact on company success while also acting as a factor that boosts corporate core competence (Kim, 2017). The hotel business is a sub-sector of the hospitality industry, and by offering essential and extra services, the hotel sector may fulfil the requirements of tourist participants in the network of lodging places. The hotel business places a premium on adherence to a country's, organization's, or company's established standards for delivering services (Harunar Rashid, Yusof, Misiran and Mahmuddin, 2019). It is also crucial to strike a balance between the customer's and the company's perceptions of quality (PERNSTEINER and GRT, 2000). The

essay is based on more extensive research that looked at the traditional hotel and shared accommodation quality.

2.3.3 Service quality; As a core competence:

The idea of customer satisfaction has sparked a lot of debate and study, particularly in the literature on marketing management. Previous research (Pride and Ferrell, 2010) shows that service quality plays a vital role in the relationship between the company and its consumers. Numerous businesspeople think that the only competitiveness that can be maintained over time is quality of service. Service quality is clearly a basic requirement for any organisation's success, as evidenced by the rising group of books on the subject; it is essential in both measuring service quality and achieving competitive advantage; it influences customer value perceptions, and thus plays an essential part in long-term revenue growth. As per Gap Model, service quality is the distinction between what consumers anticipate from a service and what they actually get. The capacity to provide exceptional quality service to consumers is a critical element in obtaining and sustaining a competitive edge (Zins, 2011). Internal policies, according to research, have an impact on service quality. As a consequence, client happiness and loyalty are increased. Customer loyalty and revenue are also closely related to service quality. Customer experience may be utilised as an expression promotional tool and can assist in attracting new consumers (Pride and Ferrell, 2010). However, according to Shahin and Samea's (2010) study, service quality plans are a collection of rules for all employees in an organisation. The administration must convey these plans, and they must differentiate one company from the other.

It is generally acknowledged that strategic service quality enhancement is critical for outperforming rivals without triggering a rate war (Chaudhary, 2018). It has been claimed that increased awareness of the critical nature of service quality in strategic planning and business performance is spreading (Khairunnisa and Krisnawati, 2015). Several writers examined the degree to which top businesses were emphasizing service. Ha, and Anh (2019), for example, indicate that "a growing number of organizations are taking a serious look at the quality of the customer experience and actively seeking methods to enhance it." According to this line of thought, "quality is the organization's business," Whereas Tuan (2021) asserts that "service excellence is a key corporate goal." Panno (2019) emphasize the importance of

service excellence as a strategic weapon. Almost all businesses compete based on quality to some extent. It is impossible to think of a single sector where service is vital (Szostak, 2018).

Numerous studies have described the benefits of obtaining top products and services, including the following: a foundation for unparalleled service, increased productivity, and an improved human resource environment (Employee Productivity and Revenue-Based Model in Human Resource Accounting: An Empirical Study in Service-Based Industries, 2016); differentiation based on service quality can result in direct financial benefits (Seda Otieno and Govender, 2016); and exceptional service quality results in increased customer loyalty (Rizka Khairuna Tambusai, 2019). Excellent service helps a business recruit and retain exceptional employees and foster a pleasant work atmosphere. The most significant expense of poor service quality is client churn. Additionally, companies with poor service quality spend an inordinate amount of time rectifying mistakes, lose important distributors, and have a high percentage of total staff turnovers. The focus on service quality in strategic planning and as a critical component of competitive strategy is based on the assumption that increasing customer retention rates will result in various advantages (Loyyl and Kumar, 2018).

Additionally, service has been a critical element in establishing a competitive advantage in several service sectors. According to Wu (2019), quality has emerged as a tactical determinant in the fight for intense competition. Prameka, Do and Rofiq (2016) the service quality and management revolutions in the United States of America, as well as the strategic issue of service quality: "all we know about management and strategic planning calls for the inclusion of quality as an essential determinant of purpose and value proposition.

2.3.4 Service Quality Factors in the Shared Accommodation and Hotels Industry:

Service quality is referred to as the measurement of the ability of offered facility. Service quality measures the treatment provided to the consumer during the actual service delivery. Service quality combines the experience of the dealings of the customer with the service providers, employees of the service provider and third party involved in the service exchange (Yoshida and James, 2011). Service quality is being considered as the core competence in the hospitality industry. Accommodation service providers need to provide serious attention to the service quality factors not only to sustain in the accommodation business but also to

create a competitive difference for the organisation for long term business performance. The quality of a service may be defined in terms of its service level. is in accordance with the needs or wishes of customers. The overall image customers have of the service is based on their level of satisfaction with the value of the experience. This thus implies that the main difference among quality service and expectations is the disparity between perception and expectation. To gain success in the accommodation business, service quality needs to be sound and standard.

Service quality factors have become a burning issue for the last couple of decades in the hospitality industry, and researchers are paying attention to identifying the gaps (Mohsin and Lockyer,2010). The business environment in the accommodation industry is highly competitive, and hospitality sectors consider the service qualities as the key factors for competence (Akbaba, 2006; Petrick, 2014).

In evaluating the quality of distant shared accommodations, the study found that characteristics such as comfort and confidence are critical. The findings also showed that tourists staying in shared accommodations were mainly interested in accommodations that are within easy reach of major tourist sites, as well as facilities and services that are accessible at all times and problems that are easily fixed during their stay. When looking into what makes visitors satisfied with their Airbnb stays, they found that guests valued the flexibility and ease of use that Airbnb offers, as well as the kind welcome that shared accommodation provide. Shared accommodation guests anticipate the rooms to be modest and feature light.

The gap analysis of Parasuraman et al. (1985) was adopted by Tsang and Qu (2000) to conduct their research in China using 35 quality attributes, and they found that the service quality in the international hotels in China is below the guest's expectation standard. Their study also identified that tangibility, staff reliability and perceived value was below standard considering tourists expectation. The study by Andreani, Winata and Halim, (2018) has found that the significance of all the attributes does not equally influence the customer's expectation. According to their study, cleanness, value, and customer greetings have a significant influence in determining customer's satisfaction. Min and min (2017) identified that value and reception attributes play a vital role in determining customers perceived value for the international hotels in Korea. Wong et al. (1999) has used a three-dimensional scale

named HOLSERV, which was an extended version of the SERVQUAL scale. Staff attitude, tangibility and dependability consist of these three dimensions, and the summary of the findings is that staff attitudes toward customers significantly influence customer satisfaction in Australia. Another study in Mauritius by Juwaheer and Ross (2003) identified assurance as being an essential dimension in determining service quality.

2.3.5 Assessing service quality:

Hotel and shared accommodation operate in a highly competitive market, forcing them to offer high-quality services to stand out (Danilenko and Suranova, 2019). Several research techniques may be employed to assess the degree of quality. The GAP model, centred on the dimension of service dependability at the selected hotel, was utilized for this study.

The degree of fulfilment of the customers' requirements is the key basis for measuring service quality. Caton (2016) suggested that customers can measure the service quality through assessing the physical components of the facilities, the process involved in the service, personnel engagement to provide the service and the existence of professionalism during the service received. Service providers need to keep the gap as minimum as the possible influence between the expectation and perception of the customer in order to get a constructive outcome on the overall performance of a service provided (Caruana, 2002). Service quality gives a functional value if the satisfaction of the service can be measured (Panno, 2019). Customers assess the service quality through comparing the expectation during the decision making of taking service and perception during the actual service received.

Richard L. Oliver (1977, 1980) has developed the expectation confirmation theory. Expectation disconfirmation theory relates customer satisfaction with perceived service. This theory helps to calculate the satisfaction level of customers. Consumers are going to start being able to reach their goals. The process is called expectancy disconfirmation theory. This theory includes four variables: expectations, actual performance, perceived service of beliefs, and satisfaction.

The expectation is the anticipation of the customer for any product or service; Perceived performance refers to the post-purchase experience of a customer. Disconfirmation is the assessment of the pre and posts purchase experience by a customer for a particular product or

service. Satisfaction is the degree of fulfilment of need measured after the final consumption of a particular product or service (Oliver 1980).

The expectation confirmation theory relies on the basis that the gap between the expectation and actual service measures the customer's satisfaction with an acquired service. Sharma and Dhiman (2019) recommended that the variation that exists within expectation and perception helps to determine the degree of satisfaction. Relying on the concept of the expectancy confirmation theory of Richard Oliver, there is general agreement among Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry that the service quality assessment process is affected by the five primary gaps (Zareinejad, 2014)

- Gap 1- Discrepancy between the service providers perception of customers' expectations.
- Gap 2- Discrepancy between the service providers perception of service quality provision.
- Gap 3- Inconsistency between service quality arrangement and actual delivery.
- Gap 4 - Inconsistency between actual delivery and service offer.
- Gap 5- Inconsistency between customer's expectation and perception.

On the basis of the above discussion, the following hypothesis can be formulated to serve the purpose of the research

Hypothesis 1:

- H1-1: There exists a variation in the service quality gap between hotels and shared accommodation.
- H1-0: There is no variation in the service quality gap between hotels and shared accommodation.

2.3.6 Expectation:

The word "expectations" refers to one of two concepts. The term may refer to an individual's prediction of a desirable or unfavourable event or to an individual's desired outcome, which the individual expects to be fulfilled as a minimum standard. Both types of expectations may be affected by various variables, including the individual's prior experiences, word-of-mouth

communications, and advertising messages sent to the marketplace by businesses (Chaudhary, 2018). However, the first definition does not correctly capture the concept of service quality since it may sometimes suggest that poor service quality is to be expected, predicted, or anticipated. The second definition, in which expectations represent the desired outcome, more properly includes service quality since consumers prefer a service that fulfills their expectations. In the context of service quality, the performance required or desired by a specific customer is referred to as expectations (Caton, 2016).

2.3.7 Perception:

The word 'perceptions' receives little consideration in the academic literature on quality of service but receives much greater attention in the psychological literature. Perception has been described in simple terminology as the process of selective attention, identifying, and evaluating receiving perceptual inputs into a usable cognitive view of the world that allows an individual to interpret fact from their viewpoint (Masoud Karami, 2012). By choosing specific ideas from the enormous array of visual input to which people are continuously exposed, perceptions enable someone to effectively process some information while shutting out others that are just not deemed essential, i.e., to avoid information load. Deliberately chosen or passively absorbed similar events and contents are classified into pre-existing categories, including comparable experiences and communications from prior instances (Caton, 2016).

Remotely familiar events and communications that cannot be kept in current sections are utilized to build new elements that may be preserved in conjunction with future comparable situations and communications. Individuals may then evaluate incoming information based on previously absorbed experiences and instructions via these selecting and classification processes. Each individual's selection, categorization, and interpretation of events and instructions are unique to their life experiences (Siagian, 2019). This implies that each individual will develop their unique portfolio of intellectual storage classes, which will affect how they perceive incoming information. Since their unique experiences shape persons' perceptual mechanisms, they might also have varying expectations for future occurrences and varying views of similar experiences. In terms of service quality, people may readily develop varying expectations for a provider and varying views of the service quality they get (Dogan,

2011). As a term defined by the gaps among a person's level of satisfaction, quality of service may vary significantly amongst customers. As a result, determining whether a service is of high or low quality is a subjective and personal judgement. While individual perceptions and expectations may vary, they may not always imply that they will remain so.

A selection of diverse people may show that they have comparable expectations and perceptions due to their shared desires and judgments. Additionally, a person's perspective on a situation may easily be swayed by others, primarily when the result or repercussions are unimportant, or the person is trying to promote the viewpoints of preferred people or organizations. This common perspective gives rise to the notion of social truth,' which may draw together a group of people's desires and views of what makes excellent or lousy service (Dogan, 2011). In general, the quality-of-service study indicates a pretty widespread agreement that service quality is defined as the difference between consumers' desired expectations for a service and their consequent views of the service received. This may mean that each client has unique or common expectations and unique or shared opinions of the service received (Muka and Cinaj, 2015). Additionally, the research has evaluated a variety of models to aid in clarifying the idea of service quality, and it is now planned to examine a few of these concepts quickly to ascertain their differences with the use of a broader complete model.

From the above discussion on the guest expectation and perception and to answer the research question about the gap on the expectation and perception, the following hypotheses were formulated

Hypothesis 2:

- H2-1- There is a variation in the guest's expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation.
- H2-0: There exists no variation in the guest's expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation.

Hypothesis 3:

- H3-1: There is a variation on the guest's perception towards the hotel and shared accommodation

- H3-0: There exists no variation in the guest's perception towards the hotels and shared accommodation.

2.3.8 Assessing the service quality: Satisfaction and revisit intention:

The degree of fulfilment of the customers' requirements is the key basis for measuring service quality. Na, Bang, and Son, (2018) suggested that customers can measure the service quality through assessing the physical components of the facilities, the process involved in the service, personnel engagement to provide the service and the existence of professionalism during the service received. Service providers need to keep the gap as minimum as the possible influence between the expectation and perception of the customer in order to get a constructive outcome on the overall performance of a service provided (Caruana, 2012). Service quality gives a functional value if the satisfaction of the service can be measured (Yoo, 2017). Customers assess the service quality through comparing the expectation during the decision making of taking service and perception during the actual service received.

Richard L. Oliver (1977, 1980) has developed the expectation confirmation theory. The expectation confirmation theory relies on the basis that the gap between the expectation and actual service measures the customer's satisfaction with an acquired service. Lan (2017) recommended that the variation that exists within expectation and perception helps to determine the degree of satisfaction. Relying on the concept of the expectancy confirmation theory of Richard Oliver, several researchers, including Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1985), have recognised that the assessment process of service quality is affected by the five main gaps identified in the literature.

- Gap 1- Discrepancy between the service providers perception of customers' expectations.
- Gap 2- Discrepancy between the service providers perception of service quality provision.
- Gap 3- Stability between the agreed-upon service quality and the actual service delivered
- Gap 4- there is a discrepancy between the actual delivery and the service promise.
- Gap 5- Inconsistency between customer's expectation and perception.

Zeithamal and Bitner (2003) have indicated the significance of managing the gap 5 that exist customer expectation and perception and suggested in order to manage service quality. According to them, service quality will have a higher positive influence if the gap 5 is lower. They also referred that to keep the gap 5 minimum, service providers have to ensure to minimise the other 4 gaps as all the factors on these 4 gaps have a contribution for customer perception and expectation. The accommodation service providers will experience a positive impact on the reflection on the service quality if they fulfil customers' expectations.

2.3.8.1 Knowledge gap:

When a business doesn't know what customers anticipate, a gap develops. It could be attributable to a shortage of interaction, inappropriate market analysis, a lack of emphasis on customer contacts, and an overabundance of hierarchy within its management pyramid, i.e., too many levels of management. The knowledge gap is the discrepancy between the customer's expectations of the service and the business's ability to provide it. Management is either unaware of or has misinterpreted the customer's expectations in regard to the corporation's services or goods in this instance (Batt and Tong, 2018). If there is a knowledge gap, it may indicate that businesses are attempting to fulfil incorrect or non-existent customer demands. It is critical to have a strong knowledge of the consumer's demand for service in a customer-oriented company (Mastrogiacomo and Franceschini, 2018). An effective market study will be required to bridge the gap between customer expectations for service and management's view of service performance.

2.3.8.2 Standards gap:

It arises when a company understands what its consumers want but is unable to deliver it. When referring to particular kinds of organisations, this gap is often referred to as a "policy gap." Substandard service design, a lack of client-oriented standards, insufficient task standardisation, insufficient goal setting, and unsuitable actual evidence and service atmosphere are all causes for this gap.

As per Kasper et al., this discrepancy stems from management's mistranslation of the service policy into staff norms and instructions. Some businesses struggle to translate customer expectations into precise service quality performance. Poor service design, inability to manage and constantly improve their supply of excellent customer service, or just a lack of

uniformity are all examples of this (Woodall, 2016). Because of this chasm, customers may go for a comparable product with superior service elsewhere.

2.3.8.3 Delivery gap:

A delivery gap occurs when a service fails to satisfy the service standards set forth in the service quality specification. The intended service was not provided, resulting in a delivery gap. Technical failures or malfunctions, poor employee/job fit, bad technology fit, poor supervision, or a lack of appropriate training are the most likely reasons for this gap (Wiid, Cant and Prinsloo, 2015). This discrepancy reveals a flaw in staff performance. Organizations with a Delivery Gap may define the service needed to assist customers, but they have failed to educate their staff and implement effective procedures and standards. As a consequence, workers are ill-equipped to deal with the demands of customers. The following are some of the issues that arise when there is a delivery gap:

- Employees lack product expertise and struggle to deal with client inquiries and problems.
- Organizations' human resource policies are ineffective.
- Inability to produce due to a lack of cohesive teams

2.3.8.4 Communication gap:

Whenever the service delivered does not correspond to the quality that the business originally promised. We're talking about a communication gap when a business offers anything which can't deliver and then delivers something different in the end. It happens because Customers' expectations are sometimes raised by assurances made by businesses via promotional mass communication. A communication gap occurs when over-promising in branding doesn't quite match real service quality. Consumers are dissatisfied when the offered service does not meet their expectations, and they may seek out other product suppliers as a result. As per Kasper et al. (2013), this discrepancy stems from management's mistranslation of the service policy into staff norms and instructions. Some businesses struggle to translate customer expectations into precise service quality performance. Poor service design, inability to maintain and constantly improve their supply of excellent customer service or just a lack of uniformity are all examples of this. Because of this chasm, customers may go for a comparable service from a rival.

2.3.8.5 The Customer Gap:

The customer gap is the discrepancy between what customers anticipate and what they believe. Service quality is something a customer expects based on accessible resources, and it is affected by cultural context, family structure, personality, geography, promotion, previous experience with comparable goods, and internet information. Consumer perception is based on the consumer's encounter with the service and is entirely subjective. The customer's happiness with a particular service, as well as the quality-of-service delivery, determines perception. The customer gap is the most significant because, in a perfect world, the customer's expectations and perceptions become almost equal. Offering a great service for a specific item should be based on a thorough knowledge of the target market in a customer-oriented approach.

In today's digital world, businesses are intensely competitive, and consumers are more educated than ever, making attaining and sustaining maximum customer satisfaction more difficult than ever. For many businesses, the effort to fill such "service gaps" is quite apparent. " A service gap is a difference between what was intended and what was certainly accomplished, either between what was anticipated and what was actually experienced (Mastrogiacomo and Franceschini, 2018). Service marketing gurus Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry, recognise five service gaps SERVQUAL and split them into two categories – customer and business. The only gap that fits under the first category is the service gap. To prevent any misconceptions, this research has been discussing the service gap as a whole, but the service gap is still a sub-category that is frequently referenced as the "customer gap" as that is the only one that relates to the consumer.

The following section was summarised from different works of literature that can be taken as considerations to close the customer gap.

2.3.8.5.1 Ways to minimise the customer gap:

Having loyal customers is a top priority for almost all businesses, irrespective of whether they provide goods or services or both. The hospitality industry is using the word "services" more often these days, but the same concept applies whether you're selling goods or services. If the customers are happy with any services, the business will be able to build a trusting connection with them, which will help the business to gain market share effectively in the

industry (Batt and Tong, 2020). If the customers are happy, it indicates the business is trustworthy. Most businesses define customer satisfaction as innovating and improving service while attempting to fulfil their requirements, although this does not necessarily indicate full contentment. This is where the unpleasant "service gaps" show up. Customer gap can be minimised by addressing all of the dimensions of the service quality

Isabella and Patrick, (2012) have established that tangibility factors create the major service quality gap. By addressing tangibility factors, the satisfaction level can be increased. The following action, as suggested by Isabella and Patrick (2012), need to be considered to minimising the customer perception gap

- Keep all the equipment's in running condition and arrange maintenance work at a regular interval and whenever necessary.
- Fix immediately any issues that accommodation guests face during their stay.
- Improve work processes and standardise repetitive job requirements to ensure accuracy and stability by replacing hard technologies for human touch.

Establishing a client feedback survey to assess concerns about services, goods, personnel, return or delivery policies, and even user experience is crucial to figuring out how to enhance your business. Consumer expectations are always shifting. Even though accommodation providers want to tell consumers what customers should anticipate from the accommodation, they are likely to have a different idea. Feedback from customers enables accommodation to discover friction spots in the customer journey and, as a result, anticipate potential and address consumer expectations (Chang, 2014). The following need to be considered to address these issues as per Isabella and Patrick, (2012), Chang (2014).

- Understanding client requirements and expectations may be the most effective approach to bridge the gap.
- Feedback evaluation, consumer groups, and other methods get a deeper knowledge of consumer expectations.
- Enhance comprehension and express contacts between management and accommodation guests.

- Assist management positions in establishing, communicating, and reinforcing customer-focused service levels in their working groups.

The greatest customer service will primarily be determined by the ability of the front desk staff members to provide assistance to your consumers. As a result, it's critical to determine if hotel workers understand what's expected of them around the customer service experience (Woodall, 2016). This will allow the hotel to determine if everyone on the staff knows the purpose of each step of the customer service experience and is aware of the implications. Woodall, (2016), Isabella and Patrick, (2012) have given the emphasis on the following to minimise the customer gap

- Teach supervisors the skills they'll need to lead their teams to provide excellent service.
- Be open to innovative business models that remove obstacles to providing high-quality service.
- Set measurable service quality objectives that are difficult, attainable, and specifically intended to fulfil client expectations.
- Make it clear to workers which activities have the greatest effect on the quality and should be prioritised.
- Ascertain that workers are aware of and accept the company's aims and priorities.
- Evaluate performance and give comments regularly
- Clarify staff responsibilities.
- Ascertain that all workers are aware of how their work contributes to customer satisfaction.
- Employees should be matched to jobs skills and expertise.
- Employees should be educated about consumer expectations, views, and issues.
- Develop communication skills among workers, particularly in dealing with clients under pressure.
- Teach workers how to prioritise and manage their time.

Service evaluation is frequently a huge eye-opener for company owners since it provides a genuine chance to discover potential issues in your existing procedures. It may also compare its own customer journey to that of competitors. The goal of recognising these flaws is to

allow accommodation to make improvements to the current process and take steps to decrease the issues. For example, if the consumers express dissatisfaction with the service quality, the accommodation provider may take immediate steps to solve the issue by increasing the number of training sessions available to the support staff. As a result, staff will have a better knowledge of the service and will be able to better support the consumers. Providing staff members with client services tools will enable them to better fulfil client expectations in the long run (Koerner, 2017).

Consumers' happiness may be improved through observing, comprehending, and making adjustments to narrow the gap between the quality-of-service customers anticipate and what they ultimately get. But keep in mind that this is a continuous process. As a service provider, lodging must recognise that this is not a one-time event. Customer requirements change over time, and the methodologies in place to assist overcome the gap must be evaluated on a periodic basis to identify that they can stay up (Yoo, 2017).

Consumers who believe the service falls short of their expectations will move their investment elsewhere, given the high degree of rivalry in the current economy. Since a result, just listening to consumers may not be sufficient, as the company may still fall short of customers' needs (Yoo, 2017). That is why all of these suggestions are essential for keeping consumers and guaranteeing the long-term sustainability of the company.

- Verify that promotional materials properly represent the service qualities that consumers value most in their interactions with the company.
- Manage consumers' demands by making them aware of what is and isn't feasible – and identify and explain unforeseen causes for services quality inadequacies. Offer clients several levels of service at various rates, along with an explanation of the distinctions between such levels.
- When developing new marketing initiatives, seek feedback from operational people.
- Create ads that show actual workers doing their duties. Allow service providers to see promotions before consumers are exposed to the service.

The distinction between the provided service and the customer's expectations for that service is represented by this difference. Previous experiences and expertise, as well as prior contact

with service providers, may all impact the user needs. Because the business alone has authority over its own marketing messages, it must ensure that they are clear and not misleading since it is the only gap that can be measured, in contrast to being the only one that relates to the customer.

2.3.9 Overview of Service Quality Models:

Service quality has become more complicated due to the introduction of multidimensional models (Parasuraman et al. 1985). The main problem confronting services research is to identify the drivers of service quality, which is required in order to describe, measure, manage, and enhance consumer perceived service quality (as described by Johnston, 1995). By the 1980s, most of the work done in the field of customer service was devoted to figuring out what quality customer service included and developing strategies to provide it (Chowdhary and Prakash, 2007).

Also known as the Nordic school of thought, early inventors of services publicity were pioneers in the field of services publicity in Europe. The Nordic school of thinking is mostly credited to inventor Charles Gronroos, who developed a theoretical service quality model known as the Technical-Functional model (Al Bassam, 2013). He said that the process of matching anticipated service with perceived service in order to achieve customer satisfaction is critical for businesses. Gronroos (1984) noted that there are three aspects of service quality: technical excellence, functional quality, and firm corporate image. Additional elements such as physical and interaction quality were added to the service quality model by Lehtinen (1985). Also known as the North American School of thinking, the North American School has its roots in Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1985), who created the North American School and created the SERVQUAL model (Al Bassam, 2013).

Christian Gronroos, Parasuraman et al. (1985) is considered to be the pioneering work in the field of services management by building on the pioneering work of the Nordic School of service management, especially that of Christian Gronroos, who conducted important research in this area. SERVQUAL model (Parasuraman et al., 1988) was evaluated on five service sectors and found that Parasuraman et al. discovered that Tangibility, Reliability, Responsiveness, Empathy, and Assurance are all better indicators of customer perception of service quality than Parasuraman's SERVQUAL model.

Parasuraman et al. (1985) discovered that service companies had 97 service-related characteristics, with each of these traits having an effect on the quality of service. Customer expectation and impression on service delivery are considered significant when evaluating 97 traits (Kumar et al. 2009). It was first categorised into ten dimensions (Parasuraman et al. 1985), including tangibles (durability, responsiveness, communicability, credibility, security, competence, courtesy, understanding, and knowledge of customers) and intangibles (concealability, destructibility, compromise, dependability, institutional respect, confidentiality, privacy, security, and utility) (Daniel and Berinyuy, 2010). Parasuraman et al. (1988) reduced the 10 aspects of tangibility, dependability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy to five dimensions by utilising factor analysis: tangibility, trustworthiness, responsiveness, reliability, and empathy (Mokhlis, 2012).

The following section discusses the development of the SERVQUAL model in detail.

2.3.9.1 SERVQUAL:

The service quality study that measures five aspects of service quality may be considered a multidimensional research instrument since it is intended to capture respondents' expectations and views. Matched pairs of questions from the questionnaire, organised into five dimensions. These dimensions are thought to mirror the consumer's mental map of service quality characteristics. 22 items, including 4 items to capture tangibles, 5 items to capture dependability, 4 items for responsiveness, 4 things for assurance, and 5 items to capture empathy, make up the questionnaire's expectations and perceptions components. For statistical reliability, the questionnaire needs a moderate to high sample size. It is standard practice to include extra details such as the respondent's demographics, past experience with the brand or category, and their likelihood to make future purchases. To complete the final questionnaire, respondents would have to answer 60 questions. Each respondent should be able to complete the questionnaire in around 15 to 20 minutes.

The initial model received a lot of criticism, and that's when Parasuraman et al. (1988) refined their approach, lowering the complexity and reliability of the model. SERVQUAL, a global quality of service evaluation, was developed by Parasuraman et al. (1988) using five distinct elements (Donnelly and Dalrymple, 1996). The scale was created and validated in four different sectors of services: including telecommunication, financial, and retail services.

In its complete version, SERVQUAL consists of 22 pairings of questions divided into two sections; the first component (expectations) assesses customers' expectations for a certain industry's quality of service. The second section, which includes 22 items, assesses consumers' perceptions of a company's current quality of service (Parasuraman et al., 1988). The anchors "strongly agree" and "strongly disagree" are used to show both sets of items on a seven-point Likert scale. The difference scores are determined by deducting the expectation levels from the matching perception level to determine service quality.

The implementation of the service quality framework included a comprehensive research project that started in 1983 and culminated in the release of the SERVQUAL instrument in 1988 after numerous modifications. The model's creators started with a thorough literature review to find things that were thought to have an effect on perceived service efficiency. This preliminary search yielded approximately 100 products that were included in the initial phases of market research. Initial results demonstrated that such elements were included into ten dimensions (or components) of service efficiency, was extracted through factor analysis. The first ten dimensions thought to reflect service quality are as follows:

1. Competence is described as having the necessary expertise and experience to accomplish the task. Competence can exist, for instance, in contact personnel's skill and experience, technical support personnel's experience and abilities, and the institution's analysis capability (Brodhead, Quigley and Wilczynski, 2018).
2. Courtesy manifests itself as good manners, reverence, and sociability, as well as concern for the host's premises and a clean and tidy presence of contact staff (Goffman, 2014).
3. Credibility combines reliability, conviction, and integrity. It entails prioritising the best interests of the consumer (Orlitzky and Swanson, 2012). The identity of the organisation, its prestige, and the personal attributes of the contact staff can all have an effect.
4. Security provides a sense of protection, uncertainty, and certainty to the client, comprising personal safety, economic security, and privacy (Choi, Jeon and Kim, 2019).

5. Accessibility refers to a person's desire to be approachable and reachable, as for example, flexible working hours and sites for office operations (Choi, Jeon and Kim, 2019).
6. Communication entails also providing information to consumers in a clear and understandable manner and responding to them (Orlitzky and Swanson, 2012). A firm's vocabulary might have to be adjusted to meet the demands of its various clients. For example, data may provide a description of the service and its expense, the interaction between resources and costs, including clarification of how any issues would be handled efficiently.
7. Knowing the consumer entails taking the opportunity to recognise the clients' unique desires, offering personalised service, and remembering the consumer as they meet, among other things. This, in particular, aids in delighting consumers by exceeding their needs.
8. The existence of the actual structures, instruments and supplies being used to deliver the operation, the presence of staff and contact materials, and the existence of other people in the service centre are all examples of tangible things.
9. Reliability is best defined as the willingness to consistently deliver the anticipated service in an honest and dependable way. Reliability builds the confidence level of the customers (Barua, Aimin and Hongyi, 2017).
10. Staff responsiveness refers to their preparation and ability to assist clients by offering prompt and efficient resources, such as submitting a purchase form or convening a meeting rapidly (Richmond, Braughton and Borden, 2018).

Researchers Valarie A. Parasuraman, Valarie Zeithaml, and Len Berry developed the service gaps model during a long-term study effort that began in 1983 and continued until 1988. SERVQUAL is defined by the model as is a framework for evaluating service quality. When the model was created, the authors identified 10 distinct characteristics of consumer efficiency, but this proved not to be the case. Further study and retesting proved that many of the previously isolated characteristics were, in fact, associated. Therefore, the elements were composed of five dimensions. All five factors are assumed to reflect service quality dimensions in a variety of sectors and contexts. Further researchers also revealed that some of the ten initial SERVQUAL dimensions were significantly related or auto-linked. As a result, the ten original measurements were shortened, and the marks were updated to accommodate

the new dimensions. The developers simplified the template to five variables by the 90s, which proved to be reasonably reliable in research. Reliability is the capacity to provide the promised service consistently and correctly. Tangibles include the look of physical facilities and equipment as well as the appearance of people and communication materials. Providing clients with compassionate, one-on-one service is the fourth characteristic. The desire to assist clients and to offer timely service are examples of responsiveness.

These are the five measurements of service efficiency that the SERVQUAL analysis material's individual items are based on. The SERVQUAL measurement instrument, according to Nyeck (2002), "also seems to be the most comprehensive effort to conceptualise and quantify service quality." As per Song and Jung, (2017) Many studies have used the SERVQUAL measurement instrument in a variety of service sectors and settings, including hospitals, finance, and banking.

Large companies use the Survey model to assess potential service performance issues, as well as the SERVQUAL model to identify possible reasons. The expectancy-confirmation hypothesis assumes that customers view consistency on the basis of the satisfies their standards for that service. As a result, service efficiency can be thought of as a straightforward formula:

$$P - E = SQ$$

SQ is service quality

P represents the Customer's perception

E represents customers' expectations.

Service output is considered inadequate as consumer expectations exceed their perceptions of achieved performance. Service efficiency is good as perceptions surpass expectations. The SERVQUAL instrument recognises five gaps that may lead to low service quality for consumers. SERVQUAL instruments were basically developed, keeping the GAP 5 of the GAP model as $P-E=SQ$ can be measured directly. Gaps 1-4 can't be computed, instead used to diagnose the service issues.

2.3.9.2 The GAP analysis as a part of SERVQUAL model (1985):

The SERVQUAL model was developed in order to measure the disparity between customers' expectations of service and their perceptions of the actual service delivered, and using ten dimensions: tangibility, durability, responsiveness, competence, accessibility, respect, coordination, reputation, protection, and consumer comprehension.

Gap 1: The Consumer Expectation–Management Perception Distance is the name given to this gap. It's designed to analyse service provision policy; if managers do not understand or define customer preferences correctly, it manifests itself in the quality of service provided by workers who are less informed about the regulations (Daniel and Berinyuy, 2010; Al Bassam, 2013).

Gap 2: Managers Interpretation of Quality Classification is based on the assumption that administration does not explicitly logically deduce service policy by standards and regulation. As a result, workers are unsure of the regulation or are not given specific guidance about how to comply with it (Daniel and Berinyuy, 2010; Al Bassam, 2013)

Gap 3: It is referred to as Service Quality Specification–Service Delivery when employees are unable to properly grasp the rules or put directions into action because of a lack of proper understanding of the rules or translation of directives into action. This may be due to a lack of planning and growing resources available to the business at the time. A lack of coordination across the various levels of management may also be a contributing element in this situation (Daniel and Berinyuy, 2010; Al Bassam, 2013).

Gap 4: External Communications Gap: Whenever a firm's commitments to consumers from external interactions do not represent the real service delivery, a gap arises (Daniel and Berinyuy, 2010; Al Bassam, 2013).

Gap 5: The initial four gaps spread within the organisational design that has been credited for bridging the gaps that exist inside an organisation between staff members, administrative employees, top management, and customers, among other groups. This, in particular, leads to the fifth gap: a break between consumers' preferences and their perceptions of the service provided. The fifth gap is commonly known as the customer gap (Batt and Tong, 2018).

Parasuraman, Valarie A. Zeithaml, and Len Berry created the gaps model of service efficiency during a comprehensive research programme conducted throughout 1983 and 1988. Service quality concerns are defined by the model, which also provides a framework

for evaluating service quality (SERVQUAL), and the model specifies the elements that contribute to service quality problems are identified. It was originally thought that the model's authors would identify 10 elements of consumer efficiency, but after considerable study and retesting, it was found that several of the variables are interconnected. As a result, the components were arranged in five-dimensional configurations. All five factors are assumed to reflect service quality dimensions in a variety of sectors and contexts. The shorthand RATER, which is made up of the first letters of each of the five factors, is common to the students as a receptive skill. Zeithamal and Bitner (2003) have indicated the significance of managing the gap 5 that exist between the consumers' expectation and perception.

In order to control service quality, it is recommended that service providers need to understand client expectations and perceptions. According to them, service quality will have a higher positive influence if the gap 5 is lower. They also referred that to keep the gap 5 minimum, service providers have to ensure to minimise the other 4 gaps as all the factors on these 4 gaps have a contribution for customer perception and expectation. The accommodation service providers will experience a positive impact on the reflection on the service quality if they fulfil customers' expectations. On the basis of the customers' expectancy disconfirmation theory, the SERVQUAL tool was introduced by Parasuraman et al. (1985) for measuring the customers' pre- and post-consumption experience of services.

The SERVQUAL model was developed by Parasuraman and colleagues in the early 1990s with ten dimensions considering the service quality expectation and perception forming factors. Later on, the dimensions were revised in 1988 and redefined the SERVQUAL model with the following five dimensions

Table 2: Summary of SERVQUAL Dimensions- Zeithamal and Bitner (2003)

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original table can be found at:

Bitner, M.J., Zeithaml, V.A. and Gremler, D.D. (2010) "Technology's impact on the gaps model of service quality," *Handbook of Service Science*, pp. 197 -218. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4419-1628-0_10.

2.3.9.2.1 Tangibility:

The tangibility dimension is dedicated to providing a tangible impression of the staff of the service location and a physical impression of tools and equipment needed to deliver the service. Everything in terms of physical facilities and the amenities offered like materiality is tangible in the service sector, as the hotel industry. The fundamental variables for measuring the tangible quality of accommodation service as per the reservation channels are as follows

1. Presence of modern equipment
2. Attractiveness of the physical features
- 3 Presence of safety and security equipment
4. Employee's appearance with professional attire.

2.3.9.2.2 Reliability:

Kersten and Koch, (2010) describe the reliability dimension as the capacity to deliver the service consistently and dependably. Furthermore, it shows that the business keeps its commitments to consumers regarding billing accuracy, record keeping, and timely service (Parasuraman et al., 1985). Regardless of the kind of service bought, customers appreciate dependability and, as a result, have loyalty to the brand.

In other words, Hensley, and Utley (2011) suggested a service reliability paradigm in which failure rate, consistency, and error avoidance are used to identify how best to use technical reliability solutions in practice. The main factor affecting Hotel and shared housing dependability is what this is worth to customers and their perception of service quality. A

good measure of an organisation's reliability is its attention to issues like security, fulfilling commitments, and prompt communication in times of need. As per the guest reviews and feedback on the reservation platforms, the following variables were found that consist of the reliability issues of the accommodation services

1. Commitment completion effectiveness
2. Accurate bookkeeping
3. Working condition of the.
4. Secured payment service
5. Safe and secure environment

2.3.9.2.3 Responsiveness:

For customers, responsiveness is being ready to serve at a moment's notice. For example, timely service concerning sending transaction receipts may include getting transactions to customers on time and responding to calls as soon as feasible. This may include getting appointments fixed promptly (Parasuraman et al. 1985). Research by Prabakaran et al. (2008) showed that tangibility and responsiveness were essential for sustainable tourism growth in Kerala, India. The research found that international visitors placed a great deal of emphasis on the responsiveness attribute.

A desire to help customers and offer timely service by the employees is essential for success in the hotel business. Accommodation guests expect to be treated as individuals, regardless of their payment. Customers expect assistance only if it is treated as a service and not a duty or obligation. Customers want employees to act proactively to achieve the desired service level, which will minimise the difference between expectations and experiences about attentiveness in that specific company.

The degree to which the property handles service, the quality of the reservation services, and the desire of its staff to assist guests are all considered aspects of customer service. Reservation platforms like booking.com, Expedia, TripAdvisor and Airbnb were analysed to construct the responsiveness variables for the hotel and shared accommodation

1. Flexibility to respond to customer queries

2. Employee's approach to help
3. Supportive management towards employee
4. Employee performance to compete for any service

2.3.9.2.4 Assurance:

It encompasses abilities such as competence, comfort, efficiency, and accessibility (Shahin, 2005). Customers will come to doubt the quality of the company's systems and have a bad experience. Following a content analysis on the guest reviews on the online reservation platforms, the following variables were formed for the assurance dimension:

1. Appropriate cleanliness
2. Comfortable bed
3. Efficiency of the physical features as per service offered.
4. Convenient operating hours

2.3.9.2.5 Empathy:

Individual attention and care are provided to consumers by way of being empathetic (Somwang, 2008). Customers like it when firms have accessible systems, friendly employees, and an approachable business organisation. The empathy dimension is dependent on the following factors

1. Personalised attention
2. Employee attitude
3. Reliability of the employees
4. Individuals need recognition
5. Feelings towards customer

It has been described in detail in the preceding sections that the SERVQUAL dimensions, which are concerned with the human elements of service delivery (response time, dependability, assurance, and empathy), as well as the tangible characteristics of service. As Ladhari (2009) recommended, the SERVQUAL project is a dynamic scale to use

when evaluating service quality in a variety of specific industries. However, he adds that choosing the most important dimensions from a customised service being assessed is also appropriate to obtain more consistent results.

The capacity of an enterprise to satisfy the requirements of a diverse range of consumers affects the degree to which service quality is considered to be of high quality. The importance of service quality has prompted academics to address this problem and further study it across a variety of service industries and cultural contexts.

Yi and La (2003) recognise that each quality element has a distinct impact on customer satisfaction and that an organisation may be assessed by assessing the relative SERVQUAL based on customer satisfaction. Because service quality is a critical element in the hospitality and shared accommodations industries, a number of academics have used ideas and techniques related to service quality in the hospitality and shared accommodations sector.

The SERVQUAL technique of evaluating service quality has been utilised in most prior research on Hotel and shared accommodation service quality. Because of the peculiarities of Hotel and shared accommodation service quality, it is necessary to modify the SERVQUAL items to measure all hotel and shared accommodation service quality elements. According to Park et al. (2005), the quality of Hotel and shared accommodation services differs from the quality of services in other sectors; the quality of a hotel and shared accommodation service comprises both physical and intellectual characteristics. Since providing high-quality service is the most important process of a company's marketing plan, the manager must have the ability to measure it (Hui et al., 2008).

Consequently, in accordance with the guidelines of several researchers, including Park et al. (2005), Abu Jadayil et al., (2020), the Measurement scale will be modified in order to be suitable for this DBA study because it considers accommodation service users' expectations and perceptions, which is the main factor determining service quality in the service industry (Taherdoost, 2019). In addition, as proposed by Khan (2010), this will be examined in a new and modified context as part of the DBA Study.

The SERVIQUAL equipment is used to diagnose issues related to service quality. A mathematical equation has been devised using the formula $SQ = P - E$, where SQ refers to

service quality, P relates to consumers' impression of the service, and E denotes customer anticipation of the service (Parasuraman et al. 1985). This multiple measurement scales identify the gap that exists between the customers' perception and expectation. Researchers have been using the SERVQUAL measurement scale for various service contexts.

2.3.9.3 Explanation of GAP 5:

The level of customer satisfaction has been extensively discussed in the literature, and like with the concept of a service, and there does not seem to be agreement on a specific term. Contrary to popular belief, there is almost widespread consensus on the critical role of excellent service in pleasing consumers. While providing steadily rising service to customers is regarded to offer long-term advantages to companies operating in a competitive market, the research has frequently noted how challenging it is to deliver regularly. Service quality is considered complicated, hard to interpret, and tough to manage, particularly for companies with a high level of client interaction (Tontiset and Ittarat, 2014). Due to the intangible nature and unpredictability of services, it is challenging to develop and maintain exact quality standards inside a firm, resulting in consumers being unable to assess quality before experiencing the actual service (Leisen Pollack, 2008). Rather than that, consumers must depend on other confidence factors, such as the firm's business, the appropriateness of physical infrastructure, or the look and attitude of individuals.

If service providers are uncertain about the concept and structure of quality service, it may be particularly challenging to recognize and analyse consistent service quality delivery. If services are primarily unquantifiable efficiency between the provider and the customer, intangibility and fluctuation attributes may make it hard to specify objective quality standards (Leisen Pollack, 2008). Facilities with high customer interaction may create difficulties for consumers to find reliable validation criteria. If services are taken to serve the exclusive offer available for actual purchase behaviour, this may include the identical challenges that have been aligned with customer loyalty. However, it could also involve physical goods defined and can be mentioned by exact information security and can provide customers with possibilities for quality control before the acquisition (Arora and Arora, 2015). Depending on the characteristics of a service, these problems only apply in certain situations.

Except for the difficulties inherent in continuously providing high service quality and describing it, most authors believe that the quality of a service can only be assessed from the

customer's perspective since he is the final arbiter of quality in the industry (Tronvoll, 2007). Additionally, the researchers think this viewpoint is founded on the distinction between consumers' initial expectations for a service and their future expectations. Consumers' perceptions of service quality are established via a comparison of their expectations for the services they will get and their evaluations of the performance of the companies that offer those services (Panno, 2019). If the actual consequences are more than or equal to the anticipated consequences, the clients are satisfied; however, if the actual consequences are less than or equal to the anticipated consequences, the client is dissatisfied (Huang and Hsu, 2016).

If customers' expectations and perceptions play a critical role in defining quality, the first and foremost step is to meet or surpass customers' expectations to ensure customer satisfaction. Additionally, customers' views of the quality of service are critical. In short, service quality is the difference between what customers anticipate from service and how they perceive it after they get it. When consumer expectations are fulfilled or surpassed, an exhaustive model is used., excellent service quality is realized; when expectations are not met, then poor service quality happens (Ueltschy, Laroche, Eggert and Bindl, 2007). It is, however, necessary to define words such as "expectations" and "perceptions" if this postulate is to be taken seriously.

2.3.10 The Gronroos Model:

Gronroos (1982) created the first service framework, which used a standard. The CS/D (Customer Satisfaction/Dissatisfaction) model is used to describe the efficiency of service delivery (Gronroos, 1984), a leading figure inside the Nordic school of service research, argues that a thorough understanding of service efficiency should be customer centred (Gronroos, 1984). As a result, the key aspect of his service quality framework is consumer expectations of service quality, though it also incorporates other components of service quality. Professional and operational efficiency are the two aspects of service quality (Keyser and Lariviere, 2014).

Functional quality is concerned with the service's output, or what consumers got as a result of their experiences with service providers in order to adapt to the particular requirements. The technical reliability of service describes the technique of evaluating the manner in which the

service is provided. However, due to human factors such as experiences that arise during the service period, the quality is more difficult to define (Rasisanen and Gronroos 2012). It's worth noting that this model only uses success ratings to assess service efficiency after acknowledging the difficulty in measuring consumer preferences independently. Many features of Gronroos's (1984) paradigm, specifically the manner in which consumers access service, have been widely adopted by various scholars. Academic s including Kang and James (2004) and Lasser et al. have used the framework in their work (2002). Others, like Kang (2008), (Rashid and Patnaik, 2015), conclude that the technological and practical consistency dimensions are insufficient to define all aspects of a facility. It's also thought that none of these measurements should be prioritised above the other. Last but not least, since the paradigm is largely dependent on human-to-human interaction, It cannot be used in services where physical and technological elements play a major role since it cannot be generalised.

2.3.11 The SERVPERF Model:

Service quality is related to the principles of discrepancy or the difference between consumers' opinions and preferences in the SERVQUAL model. Despite its logical appeal and intellectual logic, the potential of these scores to include additional knowledge beyond that found in the perception variable is questioned.

Although understanding can be described and measured in a direct manner as a consumer's perception regarding service, expectation can be interpreted in a variety of ways and has thus been operationalised differently by various scholars. It is proposed that the SERVQUAL scale's formulation is incompatible with customer loyalty, and it is recommended that the interpretation be abandoned; as a result, the SERVPERF model comes into effect.

The SERVPERF tool, or the 'effectiveness only' instrument, is a well-known version of SERVQUAL that evaluates just consumer experience without querying about their aspirations. As a result, SERVPERF solely employs the perception aspect of the SERVQUAL scale (Yu and Hyun, 2019). The claim is that, instead of the gap between needs and experiences, as stated by Parasuraman et al., perceptions of real service received are a superior predictor of service quality (1985, 1988). Consumer experiences are quantified in the SERVPERF model using a set of criteria designed to accurately represent the service (Torres Fragoso and Luna Espinoza, 2017).

There is no disagreement between Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988)'s conceptions and definitions of service quality; nevertheless, they disagree on how to assess service perceptions. Kelkar (2010) claims that the SERVPERF framework is designed to determine the service quality by accomplishment rather than "performance-expectation.

Customer demands are integrated into outcomes, according to Kelkar (2010); thus, it is redundant to measure them independently. According to Carrillat et al., (2007) the terms SERVQUAL and SERVPERF have been used in a similar manner in previous years. They came to the conclusion that both measures are equally reliable and accurate indicators of overall service quality; nevertheless, the researchers believe that the SERVQUAL framework is more significant. SERVPERF has been tested by a number of different researchers, all of whom have found it to be reliable in a range of different industries (Qin et al., 2010).

2.3.12 Other multi-dimensional service quality models:

Other quality of service structures with a related underpinning theory to SERVQUAL in this section is discussed because it is important to recognise that many of the frameworks have quality levels that are comparable to those of Parasuraman et al. (1985, 1988) and rely on the consumer's perspective, even if they are more precise in some cases. Rust and Oliver (1994) developed a two-dimensional framework based on Gronroos's (1984) paradigm. This method treats functional quality as a single variable that may be measured. In spite of the fact that the method has not been tested, Brady and Cronin (2001) and Martinez and Martinez (2010) both expressed support for it.

The P-C-P service attribute model was created by Philip and Hazlett (1997), who believed that SERVQUAL, as well as other models, did not effectively manage a few of the important difficulties connected with the evaluation of potential services. Their approach suggests a pyramid relationship based on three primary attribute classes: crucial, core, and periphery.

The SERVQUAL factors are combined in the P-C-P framework's core and peripheral categories, whereas the pivotal grouping is part of Gronroos' practical service quality recommended (1984). However, there isn't much evidence for this hypothesis in the research.

Dabholkar et al. (2000) proposed a sequelae model, claiming that antecedents instead of elements, are a better representation of service quality. This approach incorporates a global assessment along with the individual drivers of service quality.

A multivariate framework by Brady and Cronin (2001) was developed in order to combine Nordic and American schools where the technical and the terms functional quality and outcome were adapted from Gronroos (1988); however, they were changed to read as result and interaction.

The third element was inspired by the real research of Rust and Oliver's (1994) three-c conceptual framework of the service quality model, which is a three-c framework of the service quality model. Brady and Cronin (2001) found that the three main aspects of interaction, environment, and result may be subdivided into a number of subcategories based on their findings.

Consumers, in other words, judge the three related sub-dimensions before assessing the key aspects. Consumers' evaluations of the secondary dimensions thereby impact their judgments of the key elements, resulting in the sense of the ultimate quality of service (Brady and Cronin, 2001). The conclusion they reached as a consequence of their research was that a multilayer approach to service quality seemed to be more relevant.

Using his research, Kang (2006) said that the first empirical foundation for the Nordic perspective on service quality had been established via his study, which was focused on the technical and functional elements of service quality. Carr (2007) claimed that one of SERVQUAL's significant backlog is that equity theory was excluded while constructing the scale, despite the fact that prior studies show that equity is frequently assessed in service interactions.

FAIRSERV, as an extension to the original SERVQUAL, was developed by Carr (2007) that includes fairness dimension in addition to the SERVQUAL dimensions to assess the service quality.

2.3.13 Applications of service quality models in the service and hospitality industries:

Several industry-oriented frameworks were also formulated in recent times. Parasuraman et al. (2005) designed a scale (E-S-QUAL) for evaluating online shopping. Collier & Bienstock (2006) and Fassnacht & Koese (2006) established two alternative models for evaluating e-service performance in online shopping.

Baurer et al. (2006) constructed the eTransQual framework, a transaction process-based scale for assessing the overall quality of online purchasing services; another new model, consisting of a 29-item questionnaire, was created by Abdullah et al. (2011), especially for the unique character of the banking sector, while Senthikumar and Arulraj (2011) established the SQM-HI model for education specifically for the unique nature of the education sector (service quality in higher education in India).

Additionally, a number of conceptual models have been created for the aviation sector in particular. SERVPEX is a questionnaire created by Robledo (2001) that evaluates disconfirmation in a single questioning. The validity of this was examined by Ling et al. (2005) in the context of airline service quality, and they discovered that it gives the most accurate findings for the airline industry (Wu and Cheng 2013).

Having said that, there are no significant differences between SERVPEX and SERVQUAL in terms of functionality (Lee et al., 2004). A hierarchical model for the airline business was created by Wu and Cheng (2013) by integrating the work of Brady and Cronin, 2001; Chen et al. 2011; and Rust and Oliver (1994). This model includes the unique features of the airline sector. Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Berry, (1990) defined service quality as determined by the impression and expectations of consumers about the service by the service provider. Service quality, according to the majority of academics, is defined as the efficiency with which services are provided per the service specification (Robledo, 2001). According to Zeithaml (1990), customers need to perceive service to assess the service quality. Customers can measure this quality of the service by measuring the expectation and perception gap. Service quality combines a set of attributes to identify the appropriateness of delivered service to meet customers' expectations.

Both the traditional hotels and the shared accommodation need to maintain the quality of service for customer satisfaction (Byers, Proserpio and Zervas, 2013). The expectation and the perception of the customers differ for both types of accommodation services. Customers tend to choose the services depending on their expectations (Lu et al., 2015). Although the service concept is quite similar, the service quality differs from various dimensions. From the customers perspective, there exist gaps in their expectations and perception (Singh et al., 2017). Accommodation service providers need to satisfy certain attributes to the customers in order to maintain the quality of the service. These attributes comprise the physical appearance of the property, cleanness, customer services, comfort, communication facilities etc. Customers generally hold an expectation towards the service offering; however, they tend to compare their expectation after the service consumption and measure the satisfaction level (Bodet, Anaba and Bouchet, 2016).

Akbaba, A. (2006) has measured service quality in the hotel industry in Turkey and quantified the difference between the expectation and perception of a guest. Through a deductive approach, the researcher administered a questionnaire, and to collect information, a modified version of the SERVQUAL model was used. The study team utilised a descriptive statistic to examine the expectations and opinions of hotel guests about service quality, and they discovered five service quality characteristics that may be used to predict traveller behaviour. According to the results of this research, out of the five dimensions of service quality, the category of "tangibles" has emerged as the most accurate predictor of total service quality. These results support the argument that, although the SERVQUAL scale is a highly helpful idea, it must be tailored to the particular service settings as well as the cultural context in which it is used to achieve maximum effectiveness (Na, Bang and Son, 2018). This study may be expanded to include other types of accommodations such as shared accommodations, bed and breakfast motels, resorts, and other types of lodging.

According to Bedradina (2019), the context of the service industry should be the determinant of the dimension of the SERVQUAL model. Andreani, Winata and Halim, 2018) also agrees that the service quality scales should be customized according to the specific business context. Thus, the SERVQUAL scale has been modified for a wide range of research and extended according to the industry context. The following table summarises the key modifications of the SERVQUAL framework.

Table 3: Modified SERVQUAL Models- source: Author's own work

Modified SERVQUAL Models			
Sector	Author	Year	Modified Scale
Clubs and Travel Agent	Cronin and Taylor	1994	SERVPERF
Education	Senthikumar and Arulraj	2011	SQM-HI
Airline	Robledo	2001	SERVPEX
Online Transaction	Baurer et al	2006	eTransQual
Food and beverage	Stevens et al	1995	DINESERV
Airline Industry	Petrick	2002	SITEQUAL
Online shopping	A. Parasuraman et al	2005	E-S-QUAL
Historic Houses	Frochot and Hughes	2000	HISTOQUAL
Ecological tourism	Khan	2003	ECOSERV
Library	Cook et al	2002	LibQUAL
Educational Service	Toncar et al	2006	SELEB
Low-cost airline	D'Silva	2015	LCCQUAL

2.3.14 Justification for using the modified SERVQUAL model in this study:

Following an examination of the many service quality frameworks mentioned above, it is clear that the greater part of quality frameworks incorporates the SERVQUAL aspects to assess service quality in various markets through slight modification. SERVQUAL, as per Na, Bang and Son, (2018), was used as an initial point for the formulation of the element in 30 different sectors to assess the quality of service.

In order to conduct a thesis DBA research, it is essential to have a comprehensive knowledge of what service quality involves. It is also critical to create an appropriate instrument to analyse service quality. The stakeholders of hotels and shared accommodation can use it to uncover the judgments and perceptions of their prospective visitors in London. Song and Jung, (2017)) described SERVQUAL as a multidimensional framework that aligns with the

definition of service quality and effectively measures the consumers' perception and expectation.

As a result, the SERVQUAL model will be modified into LSQUAL (Lodging Service Quality) in this research. The five dimensions created by Parasuraman et al. (1988) were used to create this LSQUAL measuring scale, with required adaptations so that it can be used in the lodging sector.

The following table summarises the key literature on service quality models in the hospitality industry

Table 4: Literature on service quality model-Author's own work

Title & Author	Research Question	Research Methodology	Conclusion & Recommendations	Gap for further research
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Title & Author	Research Question	Research Methodology	Conclusion & Recommendations	Gap for further research
Measuring service quality in mid-scale hotels (Rauch, Collins, Nale and Barr, 2015)	How do customers evaluate the perceived service quality of a hotel experience?	A deductive approach was used in this case. The service quality was assessed via the use of a self-administered questionnaire. For example, factor structure may be determined via a structural equation model, and predictors of a hotel's capacity to fulfil customer expectations and deliver value can be identified through logistic regression.	Prediction on guests' expectations can be used to shape the service environment. A deductive approach was used in this case. The service quality was assessed via the use of a self-administered questionnaire. For example, factor structure may be determined via a structural equation model, and predictors of a hotel's capacity to fulfil customer expectations and deliver value can be identified through logistic regression.	Future researchers have the opportunity to compare the service quality ratings of hotel staff and customers.

Title & Author	Research Question	Research Methodology	Conclusion & Recommendations	Gap for further research
Exploring international tourists' perceptions of hotel operations by using a modified SERVQUAL approach – a case study of Mauritius. (Devi Juwaheer, 2004)	<p>What are the dimensions of the hotel service quality?</p> <p>How do the service quality factors influence the overall satisfaction?</p>	Using a self-administered questionnaire, the data was collected, and then a correlation analysis was performed to analyse the results.	According to the findings of the study, nine service characteristics out of 39 variables are responsible for determining the degree of visitor satisfaction.	The researchers have suggested considering whether the factor structure proposed in this study is valid in other classes of accommodation such as guesthouses and private bungalows, as well as whether the perceived quality levels differ by location.
Service quality, emotional satisfaction, and behavioural intentions: A study in the hotel industry. (Ladhari, 2009)	<p>What are the ramifications of consumers' opinions on the quality of a product or service?</p> <p>What works as a predictor of a customer's future behavioural intentions is unknown.</p>	The information was gathered via a questionnaire survey, and descriptive statistics were utilised to analyse the information.	The suggested and tested cognitive-affective-behavioural model of the connections among the dimensions of service quality, emotional satisfaction, and behavioural intents has been developed and evaluated in this research.	By testing and improving the suggested model in different service sectors, we may fill in the gaps in our knowledge about service quality.

Title & Author	Research Question	Research Methodology	Conclusion & Recommendations	Gap for further research
<p>Measuring quality gaps in hotels: the case of Crete. (Ingram and Daskalakis, 1999)</p>	<p>To what extent the ISO accredited hotels integrate the service quality elements? How do the customers' perceptions and expectations differ?</p>	<p>The deductive method was used in the study. In order to gather the necessary information from the hotel guests, a self-administered questionnaire was developed in line with the SERVIQUAL paradigm.</p>	<p>On the subject of service quality aspects, the study discovered that there is a misalignment between what hotel guests perceive and what they anticipate from them. There is no guarantee that the quality certification frameworks will help to close the gap between service quality intentions and customer satisfaction. Hotel management must devise innovative and objective methods of monitoring the requirements of their customers if they are to succeed.</p>	<p>This research was conducted on a tourist area. Further research can be conducted on big cities.</p>

Title & Author	Research Question	Research Methodology	Conclusion & Recommendations	Gap for further research
<p>Measuring and managing service quality: integrating customer expectations</p> <p>(Robledo, 2001)</p>	<p>Do service quality assessment and management depend on customer expectations?</p>	<p>The research approach was deductive. A questionnaire survey was conducted. Six instruments were used to measure the service quality of three international airline companies.</p>	<p>The quality dimension in airlines is investigated, and it is discovered that tangibility, dependability, and customer care are the three variables that seem to be important drivers of overall consumer satisfaction. Understanding client expectations is essential for providing better service since consumers assess service quality by comparing their impressions of the service with their expectations, which is how they evaluate service quality. It is recommended by this article that SERVPEX techniques are better than the others after evaluating the validity and dependability of six distinct models.</p>	<p>Research needs to be conducted on to understand customers psychology for setting up the expectation level</p>

2.3.15 Key takings from literature:

- A conclusion is drawn by Al Khattab and Aldehayyat (2011) regarding the ranking of the service quality that hotel guest ranks lower in relation to the physical appearance of the service equipment, employee representation and restrictions of the hotel operating hours.
- Loyalty of consumers is very significant because it is much more expensive to acquire new consumers than it is to retain current clients Dabija, Dinu, Tachiciu, and Pop, 2014; Balciunas, Jasinskas, and Koisoava, 2014. The principal reason that some hotels are lagging behind is customer satisfaction. In order to reach higher levels of customer retention, accommodation providers need to reveal the ability to respond to customer requirements to be able to retain new consumers other than their current customers. The value of service quality for customer satisfaction is better assessed by the loyal customers.
- Boon-Liat, C., & Zabid, A. R. (2013) acknowledged that the service quality depends on the standard of the accommodation provider. Guests' expectations differ based on the value paid for the service. The higher a guest pay for a service, the higher the expectation would be. The perception and expectation gap can be minimised through the improvement of the physical features, service delivery and serviced output. Customer loyalty is substantially and positively influenced by the combination of expression, fairness, sincerity, belief, and communication together. The perceived service quality lacks behind the expectation of accommodations guests.
- Responsiveness is connected to the disposition of the staff; it is the duty of accommodation service to deliver guests with a better provision of service such that the level of hospitality can decide the guests' loyalty, Arrifin and Magzhi, (2012)
- It is the nature of hotel guests to link their standards to the very first impression of service they receive. The front office should then create a desirable environment to satisfy the needs of consumers.
- Accommodation providers sustainability relies on the standard of service delivery. Better service standards are resulting in maximising customer retention. Mohsin and Lockyer, (2010)

- Rahaman et al., 2011 pointed out that quality of service is an approach to handle accommodation service operations to ensure total customer reliability, which would help improve the service industry's productivity and efficiency. The summary of the research is that service quality plays a very significant role to grow and expand the customer base in the hotel business.
- Both comparative evaluations and the desire to return are linked with the concept of value. Aspects of service quality have an impact on the likelihood of a customer returning. The desire to return is influenced directly by both the value and the quality of the product. Travellers' judgments of value may be encoded as a summary of pertinent product details, according to this hypothesis. As a result, these perceptions of value are critical in assisting visitors in making decisions, underscoring the importance of companies focusing on value improvement initiatives. Firms may create value through increasing perceived value or decreasing perceived price.
- Five service quality dimensions help to predict travellers. “Tangibles” has appeared as the best predictor of overall service quality. Although the SERVQUAL scale is a highly helpful idea, it must be tailored to the particular service settings as well as the cultural context in which it will be used (Kamenidou, Balkoulis and Priporas, 2009).
- Prediction on guests’ expectations can be used to shape the service environment. Mid-scale hotel customers place more emphasis on the service product and service atmosphere than they do on other aspects of the hotel experience, such as service delivery.
- There was no fundamental difference between the different understandings of managers and accommodation visitors; however, the two groups had their own ways of describing luxury, service quality, and customer pleasure. Managers prefer to assess customer happiness in terms of the services given, while consumers compare customer satisfaction in terms of the value obtained in relation to the price.
- Tangibility, reliability, and customer care are the three factors that appeared as determinants of customer satisfaction. Understanding client expectations is essential for providing better service since consumers assess service quality by evaluating their impressions of the service with their expectations, which is how they assess service quality (Luo, Wang, and Sakura, 2019).

- There exists a gap between the perception and expectation of hotel guest on the service quality factors. Quality accreditation frameworks do not ensure minimising the gap between service quality intentions and customer satisfaction. Hotel managers need to find new and objective ways of monitoring the needs of their guests (Batt and Tong, 2020).
- Respondents who stayed at a shared accommodation like Airbnb indicated a significantly greater experience of all eight dimensions – entertainment, education, escapism, esthetics, serendipity, localness, communities, and personalization – compared to the traditional hotel guest (Shandliya, 2019).
- Researchers have found that shared accommodation like Airbnb outperforms hotels in communities and localness. Moreover, Airbnb is increasingly considered as a hotel's substitute and is expected to outperform budget hotels and underperform upscale hotels.
- Tangibles, Assurance, Responsiveness, Empathy and Reliability are dominant service quality factors that influence behavioural intention. The indirect effect of satisfaction plays a stronger role to drive future visiting intention; however, customers expectation and satisfaction varies according to the trip mode (Batt and Tong, 2020).
- The variables on the SERVQUAL dimension need to be amended according to the industry context to measure the service quality gap.
- Accommodation guests evaluate the quality of service based on a variety of criteria; according to Pride and Ferrell (2017), coping with service quality is a difficult challenge that management confronts. Customers utilise five aspects of service quality to evaluate service quality, according to the authors: dependability, attentiveness, confidence, understanding, and tangibles. According to Pride and Ferrell (2013), the most significant factor in influencing consumers' perceptions of service quality is dependability. Several writers highlighted a set of features that are important in terms of service quality from the consumer's perspective. According to Mathies and Burford (2011), one of the most significant requirements of consumers in terms of workers' knowledge of their demands is "listening." They also discovered that when front-line service workers offer excellent service with a product or tangible service result, they fulfil consumer requirements.

- Consumers' expectations are crucial in determining a service's worth; as a result, consumers have varying degrees of expectation. Consumers' perceptions of the quality of service given are influenced by factors such as dedication, commitment, and contentment. Furthermore, consumer loyalty affects client satisfaction, which has a significant influence on an organization's financial performance.
- According to Shahin and Samea (2010), management has to adapt rapidly to the service procedures. They claim that quality service has a direct impact on customer perception and that customer service is a consequence of performance management. As all consumers have encountered bad service at some point, providing excellent service is a tough job. As a result, it is critical for businesses to take measures to improve service quality by examining the four elements that influence it: expected service, quality of service standards, staff efficiency, and service expectation management.

2.4: Conceptual framework:

The following conceptual framework has been developed based on the discussion on the literature review section to fill the research objective. The underpinning conceptual framework for this study is shown in the Figure below:

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

As per the proposed LSQUAL conceptual framework for the hotel and shared accommodation guests can be surveyed to measure their expectation and perception for each of the dimensions. The gap would be calculated by using the gap model formula $Gap = E - P$. The gap score can be used to determine the relation on the satisfaction level and the future recommendations. The following hypothesis was generated by combining the discussion in the above literature review section and the proposed conceptual framework.

Hypothesis 4:

- H4-1: Choice of future accommodation significantly depend on the Satisfaction level
- H4-0: Choice of future accommodation does not depend on satisfaction level.

Hypothesis 5:

- H5-1: There exists a negative correlation between the gap of the service quality factors and the satisfaction level.
- H5-0: There exists no correlation between the gap of the service quality factors and the satisfaction level.

By testing the above hypothesis, the relation among the customer gap, satisfaction level and the future recommendation can be established.

2.5 Conclusion:

The discussion of the research articles resulted in the identification of the most important service quality criteria in the hospitality sector. According to the papers, it has been discovered that the majority of the researchers attempted to create a connection between service quality elements, customer happiness, value creation, and the desire to return to the site. They have discovered that there are discrepancies between what customers perceive and what they anticipate. The perception and expectation of the customer have both a direct and indirect effect on their level of satisfaction and their behavioural intentions.

Almost all of the research was conducted on either for the different type's hotels or the shared accommodation or in a particular location. However, there lacks a comparative analysis on the service quality factors between the traditional hotels and shared accommodation to measure the competitive advantage.

These papers have already established the key service quality factors in both shared accommodation and traditional hotels. This chapter addressed and demonstrated the importance of service quality and client loyalty in the accommodation sector. Additionally, this chapter examined several service quality models and their application in a variety of industries. Furthermore, this chapter serves as a foundation for the study, while the subsequent chapter concentrates on the methodology and the application for this research.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction:

To present the fundamental information in relation to the aim of the research that is to analyse the gap of service quality factors between traditional hotels and shared accommodation, previous literature has been discussed theoretically and empirically in the previous chapter. This chapter addresses several research methodologies and approaches in order to aid and collect data and to assist in addressing the key research issue that was discussed in the introductory chapter. This chapter also outlined the secondary and primary data collection process, sampling, questionnaire design, pilot testing, questionnaire data coding, statistical data analysis tools, in relation to this study, along with the justification of using these methods and tools.

3.2 Problem Identification, Research Questions and Hypothesis Formulation:

The hospitality industry is highly competitive, and the competition is gradually increasing (Deloitte, 2018). To stay in the competition, hotel and accommodation service providers are concerned about the service quality factors as the overall feedback for the quality standard lies on the service quality factors (Dedeoglu and Demirer, 2015). However, the hotel and accommodation service providers cannot fully satisfy every single customer as the diverse nature of human characteristics (Lu et al., 2015). The hotel and accommodation service providers are very keen to know about the service quality gaps and the influence of the gap on the satisfaction of the customers (Jade Conroy, 2018).

Establishing a service quality standard has been considered a composite task. Human desire and satisfaction have diverse nature. Service quality factors get special attention from the service providers to get ahead in the competitive business environment (P. Crick and Spencer, 2011). The demand for research on the hospitality industry is increasing for advancing knowledge and creating new values (Torres, 2014). Conducting hospitality service business in a multicultural city like London, the hotel and accommodation service providers tend to keep the service quality gap as minimised as possible for customer loyalty. Prior researchers have acknowledged the importance of the service quality factors for both

traditional hotels and shared accommodation (Torres, 2014; Chen, 2013; Lee, Barker and Kandampully, 2003). However, a comparison on the gap of the service quality factors between the traditional hotels and shared accommodation like Airbnb is yet to be analysed. Considering the problem mentioned above on the service quality factors, the research will measure the gap of the service quality gap in the hotels differ from shared accommodations. In doing so five hypothesis were formulated in the above literature review chapter.

The table below outlines the main method, service quality factors and data for testing each hypothesis.

Table 6: Method - used for testing each hypothesis- Author's own work

Research Question	Hypothesis	Service Quality Dimensions
1. Does the service quality factors vary between traditional hotels and shared accommodation?	H-1- There exists a variation in the service quality gap between hotels and shared accommodation.	Dimension one: TANGIBILITY (4 items) 1. Presence of modern equipment 2. Attractiveness of the physical features 3 Presence of safety and security equipment 4. Employee's appearance with professional attire. Dimension two: RELIABILITY (Five items) 1. Commitment completion effectiveness 2. Accurate bookkeeping 3. Working condition of the. 4. Secured payment service 5. Safe and secure environment
Do the hotels and shared accommodation have the same level of the customer's expectation?	H-2- There is a variation in the guest's expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation.	
Do the hotels and shared accommodation have the same level of the customer's perception?	H-3- There is a variation on the guest's perception towards the hotel and shared accommodation	

<p>1. How does the gap of the service quality factors influence the choice of future accommodation?</p>	<p>H-4- Choice of future accommodation significantly depends on Satisfaction level.</p>	<p>Dimension three: ASSURANCE (Four items)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Appropriate cleanliness 2. Comfortable bed 3. Efficiency of the physical features as per service offered.
<p>How does the customer gap influence the satisfaction level?</p>	<p>H-5- There exists a negative correlation between the gap of the service quality factors and the satisfaction level.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 4. Convenient operating hours <p>Dimension four: EMPATHY (5 items)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Personalised attention 2. Employee attitude 3. Reliability of the employees 4. Individuals need recognition 5. Feelings towards customer <p>Dimension five: RESPONSIVENESS (4 Items)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Flexibility to response customer queries 2. Employee’s approach to help 3. Supportive management towards employee 4. Employee performance to compete any service

3.3 Research Philosophy:

Research philosophy refers to the progress of the nature and understanding of the research. Research philosophy consists of set assumptions that how the research will be carried out. In particular, research philosophy combines the way of data collecting, analysing, and using for a phenomenon. The research strategy and design will be strengthened by these assumptions.

Research philosophy mainly links up the development of the research understanding and the way of conducting the research.

Research philosophies are derived from the term epistemology and doxology. Epistemology refers to the facts that are known for being true, while doxology indicated the factors that are considered to be true. According to Ryan (2018), the Western tradition of science has categorised the research philosophies as positivism and interpretivism.

Positivism philosophy sticks to scientific knowledge and allows observing and quantifying the research findings (Michele, 2019). Positivism is objective rather than subjective; that is, the reality is possible to observe and describe without conducting any study on any phenomenon. The study of any event is essential to the interpretivism argument, as is the assertion that researchers cannot avoid having an impact on the phenomenon they are investigating. Despite the fact that researchers acknowledge that there may be a variety of interpretations of reality, they maintain that it is structural interpretations that they are seeking (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010).

In 2003, Saunders and colleagues defined realism as being predicated on the belief that a definition states that is separate and distinct concerns and convictions and that this reality may have an effect on people's decisions either deliberately or inadvertently. According to (Scheurich, 2007) studies on business are mostly carried out with a combination of positivism and interpretivism philosophies as a mirror of realism.

The goal of the research is to gather more information through the use of investigational procedures. There are two types of research that can be done. One is to address a current dilemma in the workplace. Intervention and applied science are terms used to describe this kind of science (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010). Typically, this kind of study is utilised to resolve a management-related problem in which flexibility is limited, and it is difficult to speculate the results to comparable challenges in other organisations. The goal of applied science is to get a better understanding of particular patterns and problems that emerge in companies and markets, as well as how to address and resolve such trends and issues (Sekaran, 2006).

Another aim of the research is to build a connection between the researcher's area of interest and the larger bodies of knowledge in that area. This is known as the linkage goal. The primary objective of conducting actual research is to develop a better understanding of

occurrences and to develop hypotheses based on the findings. Such hypotheses then serve as the basis for further investigation of the phenomenon. In the field of management, this method of building on established expertise allows for concept growth (Sekaran, 2006).

This study used questionnaires, empirical framework, and statistical tests on the collected data used by positivist researchers. Statistical equations, such as SPSS, descriptive statistics, are also used to convert the sample units into statistical models as suggested by (Jennings, 2010). This research is aimed to quantify the service quality factors and find the gap of the service quality factors that exist between the traditional hotel and the shared accommodation. As the key aim of the research is to measure the service quality gap between the hotel and shared accommodation, the research followed the positivism philosophy as positivism philosophy relies on stability and observation ability (Saunders et al., 2015). Therefore, a questionnaire based on the LSQUAL framework on a five-point Likert scale was used, and the data were analysed using the SPSS statistical tool. The correlation between different variables of service quality factors was also examined within the research. As the basis of positivism, philosophy is to stick into scientific knowledge and allows quantifying the research findings and allows better understanding of a particular issue, this research meets similar criteria and therefore the philosophy for this research is positivism.

3.4 Research Approach:

The approach would either be inductive or deductive that depending on the goal of the research. The inductive approach begins with the perceptions to establish theories through experimentation. Inductive research seeks to include examples from perception and the advancement of clarifications. Hypotheses are developed and applied in inductive reasoning toward the start of the exploration, and the observer remains open regarding modifying the heading for the examination after the experimental procedure had initiated, While the deductive approach allows analysing and extending existing theories. Reality can be tested through the deductive approach (Saunders et al., 2007).

The positivism theory is synonymous with deductive analysis, while interpretivism is aligned with inductive research (Gill and Johnson, 2010). It is important to understand all methods to make an informed decision about which testing method to use. The deductive method is described as reasoning that starts with a basic idea or hypothesis and progresses to more

concrete facts (Gill and Johnson, 2010). It denotes that the inference is actually deduced from the facts. The inductive approach relies mainly on identifying the characteristics of the phenomena, while the deductive approach is driven by knowledge.

The inductive approach is a method of reaching hypotheses by objectively analysing the interpretation of data analysis findings. This method starts with a particular problem and then draws on a preliminary hypothesis, which is then linked to a valid paradigm by finding the correct theory from different sources. The inductive method seems to be a “bottom-up” approach, founded on the assumption that we observe trends and propose any preliminary hypotheses that can then be investigated by forming theories or finding the underlying theory (Ridenour et al., 2008). Particularly in the early stage, this form of logic is far more open-ended and investigative. The advantage of this method is that the inference would almost always be founded on-premises. However, since it usually shifts from individual circumstances to universal premises, this form of logic entails complexity.

Positive psychology uses the deductive procedure to improve a calculated and hypothetical angle prior to testing it through experimental perception, whereas interpretivism uses an inductive strategy, which is the opposite of positivism, to engage in the improvement of an inductive angle before testing it through experimental perception. Interpretivism takes into account current and previous experiences (Davies, 2017). Realistic approaches are well-suited to the application of both deductive and inductive processes (Scheurich, 2007).

This study is mainly based on the hypothesis test to answer the research question and fulfil the research objective rather than developing theories, which is the main emphasis of inductive research. As the adoption of the research approach depends on the research philosophy (Rea and Parker 2006), this study is considered to follow the deductive approach. Because the main study goal is to determine the extent to which service quality elements are lacking in the accommodation sector, the research will seek to establish a connection between service quality factors and the customer experience in the accommodation sector. Moreover, the research will also test the reliability of the LSQUAL framework for service quality context in a multicultural city like London. Thus, following the positivism philosophy, the research approach will be deductive.

3.4.1 Theoretical underpinning and SERVQUAL model:

After analysing the numerous service quality framework listed in the literature review chapter, it is obvious that the vast almost all quality frameworks incorporate the SERVQUAL aspects to assess service quality in various markets through slight modification. SERVQUAL as per Ladhari (2008), was used as an initial point for the formulation of the element in 30 various sectors are evaluated in order to determine the overall quality of service.

In order to conduct a thesis DBA research, it is essential to have a comprehensive knowledge of what service quality involves. It is also critical to create an appropriate instrument to analyse service quality. The stakeholders of hotels and shared accommodation can use it to uncover the judgments and perceptions of their prospective visitors in London.

Sunaeva, (2019) described SERVQUAL as a multidimensional framework that aligns with the definition of service quality and effectively measures the consumers' perception and expectation.

It was found via a research of the literature that the SERVQUAL instrument would be the most suitable for this study in order to get a scale for lodging service quality; however, SERVQUAL is a general model and has to be modified in order to be industry related, as proposed by (Caruana et al. 2000; Ladhari 2008). According to the SERVQUAL dimensions (Parasuraman et al. 1988), the questionnaire was conducted by the researcher of this DBA study and was then adjusted as LSQUAL to modify factors to analyse the Service quality customer gap between conventional hotels and shared accommodation. The variables for LSQUAL were derived from an in-depth analysis through content analysis into the online hotel and shared accommodation reservation platforms.

As a result, the SERVQUAL model will be modified into LSQUAL (Lodging Service Quality) in this research. The five dimensions created by Parasuraman et al. (1988) were used to create this LSQUAL measuring scale, with required adaptations so that it can be used in the lodging sector.

3.5 Research strategy:

An outline of the essential segments of research, such as the research element and the primary emphasis, the research perspective, the research structure, and the research methods, are

presented in a research strategy. It allows the way of finding out the answers for the research question along with the implementation policy.

Saunders et al. (2007) defined the research as the methods and procedures used to collect and analyse study results, comprising questionnaires, evaluation, interviews, and analytical and non-statistical processes. The use of quantitative, qualitative, and multimethod approaches is common in most scientific studies. According to Saunders et al. (2007), researchers perform analysis using case studies, qualitative interviews, and quantitative surveys, based on the research parameters. It is less likely that action-oriented analysis will be used to do research.

3.5.1 Content and thematic analysis:

The concept "content analysis" was introduced about sixty years ago and was described as the assessment of the current and latent subject matter of a body of communication material by interpretation, collation, and review of In Webster's dictionary, the definition is "to examine a work's major symbols and ideas in order to determine its importance and potential effect. Content interpretation involves a comprehensive examination of a body of documents, pictures, and symbolic matter, not simply from the viewpoint of the speaker or consumer. Content interpretation can be used in inductive reasoning or sequentially on both primary and secondary data (Elo and Kyngas, 2008).

It also helps the scholars to draw observable and true inferences from data to context in order to provide information, new ideas, reflect the evidence, and deliver a realistic guide to action, according to Krippendorff (2014). Elo and Kyngas (2008) concluded that implementing this method would result in a better outcome. The researcher would be able to recognise the terms or categories that characterise the phenomena being studied. The aim of defining certain terms or concepts is to create a model, a conceptual model, a conceptual structure, or a set of classifications. Dey Jennings (2010), describes content analysis leading to the finding a subject for the study, reading and classifying the data, that naturally go ahead on to the development of categories ideas are always collected, their value assessed, and their applicability assessed.

These research has followed the suggestion of Jennings (2010) in order to collect related information regarding the service quality factors. The online hotel and shared accommodation

reservation platform like booking.com, Tripadvisor, Airbnb were extensively investigated to obtain the material information and formulate the industry specific service quality factors. The contents on the customers reviews and feedback on the reservations channels were filtered to gather the related information. Thus, the researcher was able to examine the materials without being guided by any theories. This helped to find the descriptive units for the research. The researchers take the responsibility of the material secondary information and filtered the data in light of the context of the industry. These analytical data also represented the actual experience rather than immaterial. Considering the suggestion from Dincer (2018) the content was explained in the literature review section in light of the lodging industry service quality dimensions.

3.5.2 Triangulation and mixed methods:

Triangulation is a navigation and army tactics analogy that considers several control variables to identify a material's exact location" (Jack and Raturi, 2006). This is a concept that refers to the application of a variety of research methodologies to determine the validity of a study (Bryman, 2011). During the research study, methodological triangulation of various research techniques is integrated for both quantitative and qualitative data collecting techniques and analysis techniques (Saunders et al. 2007).

Researchers' attitudes on the practice of triangulation in a study have been divided. In the opinion of some authors, triangulation is merely to gain a more comprehensive and triangulation is used to enhance research accuracy, in which case triangulation is one of the validity measurements; others believe triangulation is used to improve study accuracy, in which case triangulation is one of the validity measures. Triangulation research is described as employing various qualitative and quantitative techniques to investigate a single phenomenon to increase the credibility of the study results. Thus, triangulation integrates two or more methods, theoretical perspectives, data sources, and researchers, and analytic procedures to investigate the same phenomena from several perspectives (Bauwens, 2010). Although some researchers believe that combining qualitative and quantitative paradigms in the same study is beneficial, others believe that the two paradigms are opposed on epistemological and ontological grounds. However, both paradigms are geared at increasing knowledge of a specific topic area of interest. The major advantages and downsides of each

choice should be evaluated and accounted for. Consequently, when two methods are combined, there is a high likelihood of neutralising the shortcomings of one technique while enhancing the advantages of the other, resulting in improved research outcomes.

Triangulation's efficacy is based on the notion that the flaws of any individual technique will be balanced by the concomitant capabilities of another (Reid, 2019). The use of triangulation in research is controversial among researchers. Some researchers believe that triangulation to be nothing more than a strategy for giving insights from researching a phenomenon. Others (Hussein, 2009; Golafshani, 2003) define it as "a reliability method in which scholars strive for consistency across diverse and disparate information resources in order to establish a different pattern in research.

Furthermore, triangulation is described by Bryman (2004) as the employment of various approaches, mostly qualitative and quantitative approaches, in the assessment of the same phenomena. The study should make ensure the ultimate output takes advantage of the multidimensional approach. Jack and Raturi (2006), identified the following forms of triangulation

- Data triangulation
- Investigator triangulation,
- Theory triangulation
- Methodological triangulation.

3.5.2.1 Data triangulation:

Data triangulation helps to write a more substantial article. Combining various study elements from numerous sources, ideas, or techniques is a simple approach that may be used for any research anyone is interested in doing. Three kinds of triangulation have been identified by Denzin (1978) and Patton (1999): The triangulation methods are as follows: In order to determine the consistency of results obtained via various techniques of data gathering, In a study, it is usual to have both qualitative and quantitative information. These two studies provide light on different facets of the same phenomena. In this case, several analysts are used to evaluate the results, or multiple observers and analysts are used in conjunction with each other (Haapanen, 2018).

3.5.2.2 Methods triangulation:

Methods The application of several techniques to investigate a situation or phenomena is referred to as triangulation. Ultimately, the goal is to reduce the inadequacies and biases attributed to a particular technique. In other words, the advantages of one technique may be sufficient to compensate for the disadvantages. When employed in social science research, this kind of triangulation is quite parallel to the mixed research methods used to improve, augment, and explain the findings of one method by using the results of another method. Also known as data triangulation, it is a variant of the concept that emphasises the use of data gathered by various techniques rather than data collected for distinct programmes, places, or people, among other things (Haapanen, 2018).

One of the essential advantages of techniques triangulation is its ability to reveal unique distinctions or essential information that would otherwise have gone undetected if just one strategy or data collecting methodology had been used in the research. Several experts say triangulation between and within methods yields much more comprehensive results than relying only on a single technique. Triangulation of techniques suffers from several drawbacks, including the high cost of deploying multiple/mixed methodologies, the difficulties in integrating quantitative and qualitative results, and the variable quality of research conducted using various approaches (Haapanen, 2018). When using techniques triangulation, it is essential to note that errors in data from one method do not always decrease or balance the flaws in data from another approach throughout the analysis process. This is indeed why it is critical to make use of tried-and-true techniques for both quantitative and qualitative work while doing research.

3.5.2.3 Investigator triangulation:

An investigator triangulation experiment is one in which a study is conducted with the participation of more than one questioner, spectator, researcher, or data analyser. In the absence of previous communication or cooperation amongst investigators, having the capacity to corroborate results across investigators may substantially increase the trustworthiness of the results. Investigator triangulation is essential for reducing partiality in a research project's data collection, publishing, and analysis phases (Archibald, 2015).

3.5.2.4 Theory triangulation:

When investigating a condition or phenomena, theory triangulation is the application of many theories or hypotheses simultaneously. The aim is to examine a scenario from various viewpoints, through various lenses, and with a variety of questions in mind, before concluding. Moreover, the various theories or hypotheses do not have to be comparable or consistent with one another; in fact, the more diverse they are, the greater the likelihood of identifying particular problems and challenges. of each source, and it seeks for a convergence of data to form broad generalisations.

The main advantage of theoretical triangulation is its capacity to conduct research and look more widely at results, which is a significant advantage. Furthermore, limiting the number of potential explanations for a situation or event to a single theory, viewpoint, or hypothesis may reduce possible explanations. In reality, using numerous — even competing — viewpoints or hypotheses may force analysts to go beyond apparent answers and discover sharper methods of analysing and interpreting results, thus increasing their productivity.

This research has applied data triangulation as it was an appropriate instrument for the collection of data from different online sources for hotel and shared accommodation reservations. An extensive investigative study to discover amenities offered by the hotel and shared accommodation providers gave more scope for the subsequent layers of data collection. Feedback filtering allowed the researcher to formulate the industry-specific service quality factors. Data triangulation allowed the researcher to capture more information is a highly effective method of collecting more detail, reducing the impacts of partiality, particularly in the current pandemic situation.

3.5.3 Justification of triangulation:

A triangulation analysis could only be carried out if sufficient data are available, whether they come from several sources, investigators, or hypotheses, or obtained via various techniques. Although triangulation may and should therefore be utilised when data is available, there are many reasons why it should and should not be. Questions that are difficult to answer. Having the capacity to pull information from various more prominent, more significant sources while attempting to answer difficult questions about a program's quality, execution, result, and effect may offer a more immense, more enormous, more extensive plethora of viewpoints and a much deeper insight into problems underlying the complex

questions. Data that is dissimilar. A valid conclusion or a new hypothesis that can be tested may be reached with enough evidence, but it is dissimilar. Triangulation can help to balance the various viewpoints and lead to a valid conclusion or a new hypothesis that can be tested.

In reality, triangulation may provide chances to evaluate a wide variety of facts on a specific scenario or phenomena side by side, giving fresh insights and creating new hypotheses resulting from the comparison—data of poor quality. Whenever relevant data from various sources, investigators, and techniques are available, triangulation may be used to compensate for low-quality data. This is provided that the validity and reliability of the other data can be verified. There is insufficient information. The use of triangulation may be used to piece together population-level findings when no data on individual outcomes are available. Triangulation can be used to piece together individual judgments when no data on organisational results are available. It is critical to emphasise that triangulation can and should be included in the monitoring and evaluation process on an institutional level.

For this DBA research, the data triangulation method is used because selecting a framework is critical because it necessitates the researcher's decision on whether to structure concepts first before progressing the study by exploring the world across academic evidence, or whether to take a different methodology and let theory come first, and empirical research follow (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). Despite the fact that there are significant distinctions between these two paradigms, Gibson, (2016) argue that none is better since they provide ideologies that are distinct from one another. According to Creswell and Clark (2007), the employment of several methods (triangulation) to guarantee the validity of research may be a productive strategy to ensure the validity of the study. The criteria for selecting a research design are thus ultimately determined by the researcher's own preferences as well as the objectives or context of the research project in question (Smith et al. 1995). Therefore, data triangulation is used in this study to develop the service quality factors for the LSQUAL framework. The present research used triangulation using the online reservation channels different data sources and methods like content analysis for the secondary data and for the primary data, a questionnaire was used. Data triangulation helped the researcher to collect more information and reduce the effects of bias, which is especially important in the present pandemic crisis.

The following figure represents the mapping of the data triangulation process for the research to find the service quality gap between the hotel and shared accommodation.

Figure 2: Data triangulation- "Author's own work"

The main goal of the study is to create a modified version of SERVQUAL that comprises the factors that are appropriate for evaluating service quality gaps between the hotel and shared accommodation in central London. Therefore, through content analysis from the hotel and shared accommodation booking channel fine prints and reviews, this study includes the

lodging specific service quality factors to construct the LSQUAL framework and formulate the questionnaire for primary data collection.

3.6 Research Design:

The research design is a strategy or framework for carrying out the study, which includes data collection. It specifies the precise techniques and processes that must be followed in order to get the information required, and it entails a sequence of logical decision-making options (Sekaran, 2006). The researcher goes on to say that research designs may be exploratory in character, descriptive in nature, and/or performed to test a hypothesis, with the latter being the most common. It is dependent on the type of study as well as the current level of knowledge in the research field. As the study progresses, the choice of the design gets more rigorous, moving from exploratory to descriptive in nature. Research design initially includes the planning of way finding out answers for the research questions (Saunders et al. 2012). Flick (2011) has described the research design as a portrayal of the research procedure. It is a structure that incorporates the contemplations that prompted the suitable technique being embraced, the manner of choosing and the way of processing the data. Research design might be descriptive, explanatory, or exploratory in characteristics. Bryman (2012) considered the descriptive research design as a mirror to understand the participants in any research. Saunders et al., (2007) explained the focus of the explanatory research design as the way of clarifying the attributes of a population. This may be considered influential when a quantitative framework is used, and the effect of one variable on another can be established (Kothari, 2004). The exploratory research investigates an issue where there exists a lack of knowledge in any particular research field. It is normally utilized as guidance for a future researcher (Neuman, 2003).

3.6.1 Secondary Data collection:

During the different phases of this Doctoral research, comprehensive preliminary/secondary research, i.e., literature reviews, is undertaken on a variety of subjects, including the hospitality sector, service efficiency, customer loyalty, the SERVQUAL model, the hospitality industry, and lodging providers. A selection of supplementary references was used to help the systematic review, including:

- Scholarly journals and research database platforms including Emerald, Ethos, Sage Publications, and a plethora of several other internet resources.

- Research paper references from a variety of colleges and public libraries
- Online booking channels and review sites like trip advisor, Booking.com, Airbnb, and other services provide guest ratings on hotel stays.

3.6.2 Primary Data Collection Method:

One or more data collecting procedures needed to be employed once the study methodology and design had been finalised. Generally, a researcher chose one (or more) data collecting strategy after weighing the research's overall acceptability (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010). It is understandable that a particular research issue may not be adequately investigated since specialised data collecting procedures to acquire the data required to defend queries (Kerlinger and Howard, 2008).

3.6.2.1 Questionnaire:

Questionnaires, as an effective data collection tool, helps to gather data from a large population for quantitative research (Saunders et al, 2003). Questionnaires can be applied with both positivism and interpretivism methodologies of research. An effective questionnaire should have the characteristics of generating an upper response rate, highly reliable and valid (Scheurich, 2007). To gather data about respondents' opinions and attitudes, questionnaires can be designed as closed, open-end and scale (Davis, 2007). Closed questions limited numbers of options for the respondents to choose from, whereas open-end question provides freedom to the respondent to answer according to his choice from several numbers of probable answers. The scale helps to measure participants' stunt about a question.

A questionnaire, according to Curwin and Slater (2007), must have a logical structure with well-designed questions. According to Weisberg, Krosnick, and Bowen's rules, the expression should be maintained as plain as possible, as this questionnaire would be filled out by hotel and Airbnb visitors, all of whom would come from diverse ethnic and educational backgrounds. As a result, the questionnaire for this study will be kept short and straightforward.

The SERVQUAL questionnaire has been considered to be quite useful for assessing service efficiency in a variety of sectors by academics; though, it requires more task-based on industry-oriented variables (Ladhari, 2010).

As the SERVQUAL factors are considered as the key competency for lodging operators and are taking on new aspects as a result of accelerated technical developments, this DBA analysis will refine the SERVQUAL design by applying accommodation service-related variables to provide a more applicable framework for the analysis.

The LSQUAL (lodging Service Quality) to measure hotel and shared accommodation Service Quality GAP is a modified sector-oriented model in which the five initial SERVQUAL measurements were standardised, and the parameters were revised as per the industry facilities by the researcher for this DBA study. The modified questionnaire was adapted based on the in-depth content analysis research on the booking channel extranet, like booking.com, TripAdvisor, Expedia Airbnb etc. in addition to the review of the literature on service efficiency and SERVQUAL method itself.

The questionnaire was split into three segments; section 1 comprises of few demographic factors, and two accommodation related questions. Section 2 contains the 22 Expectation and 22 Perception questions followed by 4 added post-stay feedback queries to identify the satisfaction and likelihood to recommend factors. Based on the SRVQUAL framework, the 22 expectation and perception questions were adapted as per the five dimensions of the service quality framework.

- Tangibility
- Reliability
- Assurance
- Empathy
- Responsiveness

3.6.2.1.1 Dimension one: TANGIBILITY (4 items)

1. Presence of modern equipment
2. Attractiveness of the physical features
- 3 Presence of safety and security equipment
4. Employee's appearance with professional attire.

3.6.2.1.2 Dimension two: RELIABILITY (Five items)

1. Commitment completion effectiveness
2. Accurate bookkeeping
3. Working condition of the.
4. Secured payment service
5. Safe and secure environment

3.6.2.1.3 Dimension three: Assurance (Four items)

1. Appropriate cleanliness
2. Comfortable bed
3. Efficiency of the physical features as per service offered.
4. Convenient operating hours

3.6.2.1.4 Dimension four: EMPATHY (5 items)

1. Personalised attention
2. Employee attitude
3. Reliability of the employees
4. Individuals need recognition
5. Feelings towards customer

3.6.2.1.5 Dimension five: RESPONSIVENESS (4 Items)

1. Flexibility to respond to customer queries
2. Employee's approach to help
3. Supportive management towards employee
4. Employee performance to compete for any service

The questionnaire was formulated on the basis of the fundamental aim of the proposed research which is to find out the extent of the gap of the service quality factors that exist between traditional hotels and shared accommodations. Before finalising the questionnaire,

the question was sent to two academics for their feedback. The academics have figured out few grammatical errors in the questionnaire and suggested to keep a logical flow in the questionnaire for example the perception question should immediately follow the expectation question for the same factor, so that the guests can compare their actual experience immediately. The necessary grammatical corrections were made, and the questions were presented in a logical flow according to their feedback.

3.6.2.2 Scale Development:

This research employs a research instrument to allow for data analysis to improve the quality and accuracy of the results. This research employs a Likert five-point scale, which is a basic form of scaling procedure that participants find straightforward to realize (Johns, 2010).

When using a Likert Scale, the elements are arranged in a particular sequence. For example, in the current research, individuals who chose '1' agreed more with the statement than people who chose '2', while people who chose '2' agreed more with the statement than people who chose '3', and so on and so forth. This results in a collection of ordinal data with the categories 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 being utilised as the categories.

According to Rossiter (2002), Likert scales may produce inconsistency in ratings since they are not accurate enough; this study disagrees with Rossiter and implied a Likert scale with a 5-point scale. This study has considered Kokku et al. (2011), as it was pointed out on that study that a five-point Likert scale helps the participants to save time in service SERVQUAL evaluation over a seven-point scale. The 5-point Likert scale is straightforward, less time consuming and relatively simple to understand for the survey participants to respond in relation to the 7-point scale. The response rate also high with a 5-point scale While a 7-point Likert scale might lead to a lower response rate. Thus, the reliability is better for large scale survey in using a 5-point comparing to the 7-point scale. Provides respondents with the choice of remaining indifferent rather than being forced to get a possibility that does not reflect their experience and enables for a lower confidence intervals. Provides a thorough understanding of participants experience that leads to produces trustworthy quantitative data. Therefore, considering the time restrictions and sample size of the survey a 5-point Likert scale was used for the questionnaire.

3.6.2.3 Pilot testing:

A pilot survey is used to evaluate the questionnaire's reliability and validity (Harrison, 2012). The proportion of a sample size that is used to reveal the status intended sample size. This step of survey administration involves administering the questionnaire to a proportion of the whole sample population or, in more informal situations, to a convenience sample of the entire population.

When conducting complicated surveys, it is sensible to complete a pilot before beginning actual data collecting. In order to conduct a pilot survey, it needs to test all of the survey procedures from beginning to end using a sufficiently sized sample (Cape, 2017). The pilot sample size is determined by the size of the absolute sample and the number of data collectors. Assuming that the survey was previously tested, piloting will most likely reveal practical key challenges and instead design issues with the survey. Lack of staff training, difficulties with the logistics of distributing and collecting the survey, or mistakes in data input are only a few examples of problems. These may then be addressed before conducting the actual survey.

For this research, a total of 25 questionnaire were sent for pilot testing including 20 accommodation guests, 6 hotel and shared accommodation managers, 3 professionals, who frequently stay in different accommodation for their work purposes, for their expert opinion. The following suggestions were received from the pilot testing

- Most of the accommodation guests has pointed out that the term ‘Customer Gap’ in the consent form is confusing to them and suggested that online link is easier for them to fill in as they can translate any term into their native language.
- Accommodation managers have suggested that the question about the stay duration might be unnecessary for the intended purpose of the research. They also suggested that as London is a multicultural city and most of the accommodation visitors are from EU countries, it might be beneficial to prepare the questionnaire in different language versions.
- The professionals have found that the questionnaire might be quite lengthy to fill out for the hotel guests and suggested to keep the questions precise and as short as possible to minimise the questionnaire fill out time. They also suggested that questions like stay duration should be removed as this question is unnecessary for this research.

After receiving the feedback from the pilot testing the following amendments have been made.

- As most of the guest was confused with the term ‘Customer Gap’ this term was rephrased to ‘Customer’s Experience’ in order to make it simple for the guests.
- As per the feedback from both the accommodation managers and professionals the question about the stay length was removed from the questionnaire for the final survey.
- Although the accommodation managers has suggested to produce the questionnaire in different language versions, it was not possible on that time because of the time restriction of this study. The hotel guests were also comfortable with the online version of the questionnaire that helped them to translate any questions or any word where necessary for them.

3.6.2.4 Population and Sampling:

Research population is the entire range of components out of which data is to be gathered and conclusions drawn. The survey population and target population are the two kinds of populations. A survey population is the population out of which data can be acquired in the research, while a target population is the group about which data is to be gathered. The extent of the research is also referred as the target population, and the survey population is also referred as the research coverage (Kotzian, 2019).

It was difficult to figure out the entire population for the survey in the current restrictive situation, however the survey population was considered to be the hotel and shared accommodation users in central London. The actual reservation obtained from the properties and the booking channels from the last three weeks of June 2021 was considered as the target population for the research. The figure came out as 22507 as of 5th June 2021.

Sampling is a method to generate an appropriate representative of a large population (Bryman, 2012). Sampling method selection is crucial as it is very significant to generate an effective representative segment for any research. The sample size is a proportion chosen from the population as a representative portion that is utilized research (Newman, 1998).

The key goal of any sampling strategy is to have guidance for choosing a sample that represents the entire population so that enough data can be generated at a reasonable cost and the results can be generalised throughout the population. Sekaran (2006) stated that 'Population applies to the whole community of individuals, activities, or objects of concern that the author wanted to examine'.

Sample size needs to be represented as it is fundamental in deciding the dependability of the research outcome. Larger sample size plays a vital role to increase the reliability of any quantitative research (Flick, 2011). In qualitative research sample size has less impact on the reliability of the research.

3.6.2.4.1 Cluster sampling:

Clustered sampling is a kind of probability sampling that is frequently used to investigate large populations, particularly ones that are dispersed over a broad geographic region. As a starting point for clusters, researchers often use pre-existing organisations such as schools or cities (Sedgwick, 2014). Cluster sampling is a research method that divides a population into smaller groups called clusters for further investigation. They then select a sample at random from among these clusters to produce a sample. The findings' validity is determined by the quality of the clusters and their ability to reflect the broader population accurately. In an ideal world, clusters would satisfy all of the following requirements:

- The population of each cluster should consist of as many different people as feasible.
- Each cluster should have a characteristic distribution similar to the population's overall distribution.
- When all clusters are put together, the population should be covered in terms of possible characteristics.
- There must not be any overlap between clusters of information

To the greatest extent possible, each cluster should be a miniature representation of the whole population. Nevertheless, in reality, clusters may not always accurately reflect the features of the population, which is why this approach offers less statistical confidence than a simple random sampling method.

3.6.2.4.2 Simple Random Sampling:

Simple random sample is to be an impartial representative of a group designed to do this. It is seen as an acceptable method of selecting a sample from a more significant population. Since every member has an equal probability of getting selected, all members have an equal influence on the outcome of the sampling process (Sedgwick, 2014). The size of the survey is an essential consideration for quantitative researchers, while qualitative researchers must determine how long to extract responses from people. In answer to the aforementioned methodological analysis concerns, Jennings (2010) suggests that the following points should be taken into account:

- The population size is the first factor to consider
- Recognising the characteristics of the population
- Assessing the population's approachability.

For the DBA research, the entire population was clustered into hotels and shared accommodation properties. Cluster sampling is easy to use as well as efficient for time and money (Thompson, 2013). Then a simple random sampling procedure was applied to the hotel and shared accommodation users to pick up the required 378 participants from the accommodation users from each of the clusters. The key benefit of using simple random sampling is that there would be an equal opportunity for each member of the population to be selected as a participant as in the research process (Ardilly and Tille, 2006). The questionnaire survey was conducted in 15 selected hotels and 15 selected shared accommodation properties in central London. The hotels and shared accommodations were carefully selected based on similar criteria so that these accommodation properties represent the overall accommodation providers that fall on the same criteria. The following criteria were considered from Booking.com and Airbnb's web portal

- Location
- Price range
- Star Rating
- Cancellation Policy
- Room type

- Stay period

To obtain an equal representation of the hotel and shared accommodation, the filtering criteria to find out the property was kept the same. Based on the filter 93 hotel and 79 shared accommodations were found. From these accommodation providers, a total of 30 properties has been selected from which the staying guest was considered for participation in the research.

The sample size was calculated as 378 using the online sample size calculator tool. The criteria for sample size were as follows

- Population size 22507
- Confidence level 95%
- The margin of error is 5%

A cluster sampling followed by a simple random sampling method was applied for the DBA research, as the cluster sampling procedure help to divide the population into cluster groups (Thompson, 2013).

3.6.2.5 Ethical Approval:

Any participation in research necessitates the approval of research ethics from the related body. Research approval is a prerequisite to approach any human participant. Ethical approval plays a vital role for the Research participants to gain confidence in associated risk minimisation. (Gelling, 2016). In ethical guidelines, there are a number of factors that impact the depth and breadth of ethical research conducted by academics.

The most important objective is to keep participants safe. Secondly, it is important to ensure that the assessment is conducted in a way that is beneficial to the individuals, institutions, and/or the cultural world as a whole. It is the ultimate aim to determine the legal legality of specific research practises and programmes, with particular emphasis on issues such as risk management, confidentiality, and the informed permission process (Velip, 2018). For this DBA research hotel and shared accommodation, guests are the participants. Any vulnerable groups were not targeted as participants for this research.

When it came to the main data collecting procedure, the major source of concern was the covid-19 safety precautions. To ensure the safety measure the researcher has taken all the

necessary steps in order to avoid transmission of the virus. In addition, an electronic format of the questionnaire was produced so that the participants can fill out the questionnaire at a convenient time.

To ensure compliance with the Data Protection Act, 2018 and the General Data Protection Regulations (GDPR), and participants' right of access to any personal data stored in relation to them. In accordance with the Data Protection Act 1998, the researcher will ensure that any personal data are obtained only with the permission of participants.

In this DBA study, ethical issues were given the highest careful consideration. The questionnaire was prepared, and a pilot test was conducted to ensure the standard of the questionnaire. A few modifications were made from the suggestion of the pilot study. After finalising the questionnaire, it was sent to the ethical committee of the University of the West of Scotland for certification. The ethical approval was received on due course to collect the primary data.

3.6.2.5 Administering the questionnaire:

The ability to optimise the satisfaction rating is a vital issue of a standard questionnaire. When evidence is not obtained from the sample chosen for the questionnaire, there exists a chance of a biased response. As a result, studies need to use extreme caution when administering questionnaires to boost response rates. There exist several ways to deliver the questionnaires as per Kendall (2008) the followings are quite applicable

1. Bringing together all of the participants at the same time
2. Personal administration of the questionnaire.
3. Participants are given priority to complete the questionnaire
4. Distributing the questionnaire using mail services.
5. Using an online platform to distribute the questionnaire

In this study, personal distribution of the questionnaire was deemed the most effective approach, however, considering the current covid situation and social restrictions measures online platforms and professional networks have been used to deliver the questionnaire. The questionnaires were distributed to the hotel and shared accommodation guests across central London.

- The online link was sent to the hotel and shared accommodation guests, with permissions, through email, mobile message, and social media platforms like WhatsApp and Facebook messenger etc.
- The researcher has also used the professional network hotel and shared accommodation managers to distribute the paper-based questionnaire and online link of the questionnaire with their checking out guests.
- The online questionnaire link has given the flexibility to the guest to fill it at any spare time within a given set date.
- The researcher has also administered more than 50 questionnaires personally to the hotel and shared accommodation guests in Bayswater and Paddington.

A total of 378 questionnaires was distributed to the Hotel and shared accommodation guests. The questionnaire was distributed equally to the hotel and shared accommodation guests. Out of the 378 questionnaires, 179 questionnaires were distributed through an online platform sharing the online link with the consent of the hotel and shared accommodation guest and 199 paper-based questionnaires were distributed to the hotel and shared accommodation guests. Almost fifty per cent of the paper-based questionnaires were distributed with the help of accommodation managers. These questionnaires were distributed with an envelope that can be sealed so that the guest can seal the envelope after their response. This ensured the guest. The researcher has personally administered 105 questionnaires to the hotel and shared accommodation guests. 298 participants have completed the survey without leaving any questions incomplete. There were also 23 incomplete questionnaires. The incomplete questionnaires were not taken into consideration for further analysis. The response rate from the paper-based questionnaire was 76%. Whereas the response rate from the online platform was surprisingly 94%. The flexibility to fill up the online questionnaire was a likely reason to get a high per centage of the response. Willimack et al. (2002) has outlined that any response rate above 50% is satisfactory enough for research.

3.6.2.6 Reliability of the Content:

The elements that make up a Likert scale are strongly inter-correlated; it is considered to be consistent. The items' high inter-correlations indicate that they are calculating a similar structure (DeVellis, 2012).

The Cronbach Alpha coefficient, which is a metric of internal accuracy for measuring the efficiency of an element, can be used to test its material reliability. The scale's reliability increases as it gets closer to one. Reliabilities of 0.80 or higher, according to Churchill (1979), are particularly suitable for scientific studies.

The internal accuracy approach was used to determine the measurement of the object's reliability in the current DBA analysis. After making the necessary amendments to the questionnaire, the reliability of the content was tested using the SPSS. In this case, the correlation between all of the components in the questionnaire was 0.84, indicating that they all assessed the same construct. The following table represents reliability of the LSQUAL questionnaire content.

Table 5: Cronbach's Alpha

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.841	0.867	52

Table 6: Cronbach's Alpha-Total Statistics

Item-Total Statistics						
Dimension/Question Type	Question	Factor	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Demographic	Age	Age	183.65	230.316	-0.109	0.852
	Nationality	Nationality	184.40	228.275	-0.052	0.845
	Gender	Gender	184.95	224.868	0.170	0.840
	Accommodation Type	Accommodation Type	184.93	229.141	-0.114	0.844

Tangibility	Presence of modern equipment (Expectation)	E T1	181.80	227.371	-0.002	0.843
	Presence of modern equipment (Perception)	P T1	183.00	209.485	0.652	0.830
	Attractiveness of the physical features (Expectation)	E T2	182.09	225.791	0.062	0.842
	Attractiveness of the physical features (Perception)	P T2	183.22	214.198	0.470	0.834
	Presence of safety and security equipment (Expectation)	E T3	181.80	224.102	0.200	0.840
	Presence of safety and security equipment (Perception)	P T3	182.62	212.577	0.535	0.833
	Employees appearance with professional attire (Expectation)	E T4	182.74	223.522	0.154	0.841
	Employees appearance with professional attire (Perception)	P T4	182.99	223.918	0.100	0.842

Reliability	Commitment completion effectiveness (Expectation)	E RE1	182.31	219.688	0.301	0.838
	Commitment completion effectiveness (Perception)	P RE1	182.89	212.957	0.603	0.832
	Accurate bookkeeping (Expectation)	E RE2	182.52	222.148	0.238	0.839
	Accurate bookkeeping (Perception)	P RE2	182.89	220.394	0.341	0.837
	Working condition of the equipment (Expectation)	E RE3	181.84	226.533	0.060	0.841
	Working condition of the equipment (Perception)	P RE3	182.75	208.146	0.634	0.830
	Secured payment service (Expectation)	E RE4	181.92	226.400	0.060	0.842
	Secured payment service (Perception)	P RE4	182.84	209.632	0.676	0.830
	Safe and secure environment (Expectation)	E RE5	181.69	223.327	0.310	0.839
	Safe and secure environment (Perception)	P RE5	182.69	217.798	0.410	0.836

	environment (Perception)					
Assurance	Appropriate cleanliness (Expectation)	E A1	181.86	224.232	0.214	0.840
	Appropriate cleanliness (Perception)	P A1	182.94	207.311	0.624	0.829
	Comfortable bed (Expectation)	E A2	181.73	222.683	0.344	0.838
	Comfortable bed (Perception)	P A2	182.91	208.303	0.636	0.830
	The efficiency of the physical features as per service offered (Expectation)	E A3	181.95	222.510	0.320	0.838
	The efficiency of the physical features as per service offered (Perception)	P A3	183.02	210.307	0.667	0.830
	Convenient operating hours (Expectation)	E A4	182.06	224.774	0.179	0.840
	Convenient operating hours (Perception)	P A4	182.43	226.286	0.028	0.843
Empathy	Personalised attention (Expectation)	E E1	183.17	215.846	0.529	0.834
	Personalised	P E1	183.57	215.986	0.508	0.834

	attention (Perception)					
	Employee attitude (Expectation)	E E2	182.45	223.634	0.171	0.840
	Employee attitude (Perception)	P E2	182.96	218.271	0.457	0.836
	Reliability of the employees (Expectation)	E E3	182.18	229.202	-0.100	0.844
	Reliability of the employees (Perception)	P E3	182.96	215.954	0.499	0.834
	Individual need recognition (Expectation)	E E4	183.21	222.046	0.225	0.839
	Individual need recognition (Perception)	P E4	183.61	217.222	0.542	0.835
	Feelings towards customer (Expectation)	E E5	183.44	222.104	0.258	0.839
	Feelings towards customer (Perception)	P E5	183.39	212.546	0.582	0.832
Responsiveness	Flexibility to response customer queries (Expectation)	E RS1	182.41	217.942	0.058	0.860
	Flexibility to response customer queries (Perception)	P RS1	183.11	214.250	0.515	0.833

	Employees approach to help (Expectation)	E RS2	182.48	218.244	0.395	0.836
	Employees approach to help (Perception)	P RS2	183.18	219.777	0.366	0.837
	Support of management towards employee (Expectation)	E RS3	182.99	220.785	0.305	0.838
	Support of management towards employee (Perception)	P RS3	183.53	221.335	0.354	0.838
	Employee performance to compete any service (Expectation)	E RS4	182.07	225.125	0.131	0.841
	Employee performance to compete any service (Perception)	P RS4	183.14	214.475	0.505	0.834
Post stay Questions	Purpose	Purpose	183.80	231.358	-0.128	0.856
	Factor	Factor	182.50	229.377	-0.087	0.852
	Satisfaction	Satisfaction	182.74	204.834	0.652	0.828
	Likelihood to recommend	LTR	182.87	206.095	0.635	0.829

3.6.2.7 Quantitative data analysis:

The next phase is to evaluate quantitative data obtained from a population sample to assess study problems, goals, or theories (Sekaran, 2010). Data, on the other hand, have

to go through a number of steps before it can be analysed. First, the data have to be reviewed; precisely, all questions need to be thoroughly scrutinised in order to remove any null answers or blank data.

According to Scheffer (2002), missing information is a concern in nearly all studies and many planned tests, regardless of how diligently the analyst has sought to verify whether or not all questions have been addressed, or how well-designed a research is, are important considerations. The question would be how to deal with lost data when it occurs. recovering the real null values is difficult.

Case omission is one of the conventional ways to reduce the effect on data processing Scheffer (2002). As per Hedges and Pigott (2004), the common and simplest approach is to use just those scenarios with full data.

Researchers skip survey questions that lack full evidence for the factors of significance from data analysis. Instead of using thorough assessment, plausible value can also be applied for incomplete questions, such as the average of the detected cases for that parameter. When a participant leaves numerous questions unclear, the researcher can contact the participant again and see whether the details can be provided such that the survey can be completed Scheffer (2002). Probability selection, on the other hand, typically indicates that the researcher did not collect any of the participants' contact information unless it was required by the survey.

The fully completed questionnaires were described in the current analysis after the survey results had been obtained. Just 516 of the 540 questionnaires gathered from the participants could be used for continued study since the others had major parts left unresolved. Although the majority of respondents were willing to undertake the survey, a possible cause may be that participants were preparing for their upcoming plans for the day and left before finishing the survey.

The researcher has crossed checked each question as the participant filled it out so that if there was a missed element, the participant was eventually requested if they could fill it out. Nevertheless, when the study was alone and had to assist certain participants in filling out their questionnaires because they were keen to participate but because of the language barrier, this wasn't always easy.

3.6.2.8 Primary data coding:

After the collection of data, the next phase was to determine the way to code every object in order to specify the values to insert into SPSS. This was important as the data have to be represented numerically for the programme to produce an accurate interpretation. This coding method made the data insertion smoother, resulting in fewer mistakes. A further advantage of coding is that it eliminates the need to recall the initial data and has a definitive archive of the database (Cunningham and Aldrich, 2012).

The dataset was initially coded on the main questionnaire, before uploading to a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet using a data table that can be exported to statistical analysis tool SPSS. The table below represents the coded questionnaire.

Table 7: Questionnaire coding

SERVQUAL Dimensions	Factors	Expectation	Perception
Tangibility	Presence of modern equipment	E T1	P T1
	The attractiveness of the physical features	E T2	P T2
	Presence of safety and security equipment	E T3	P T3
	Employees' appearance with professional attire.	E T4	P T4
Reliability	Commitment completion effectiveness	E RE1	P RE1
	Accurate bookkeeping	E RE2	P RE2
	Working condition of the equipment.	E RE3	P RE3
	Secured payment service	E RE4	P RE4

	Safe and secure environment	E RE5	P RE5
Assurance	Appropriate cleanliness	E A1	P A1
	Comfortable bed	E A2	P A2
	The efficiency of the physical features as per service offered	E A3	P A3
	Convenient operating hours	E A4	P A4
Empathy	Personalised attention	E E1	P E1
	Employee attitude	E E2	P E2
	Reliability of the employees	E E3	P E3
	Individual need recognition	E E4	P E4
	Feelings towards customer	E E5	P E5
Responsiveness	Flexibility to response customer queries	E RS1	P RS2
	Employees approach to help	E RS2	P RS3
	Support of management towards employee	E RS3	P RS4
	Employee performance to compete for any service	E RS4	P RS5

3.6.2.9 Data Entry:

In MS-Excel, a spreadsheet was established, and primary data was inserted into it. This was a significant part of the study since there were so many variables to input and special care was needed to input the data into the correct cell. The worksheet was verified after every single entry to ensure that the right numbers had been recorded.

3.6.2.10 Quantitative data analysis tools:

Computers programs significantly aid in the study of quantitative statistics. Without a suitable knowledge of the scientific principles and accurate explanations, selecting a suitable mathematical instrument as a judgement method is always a challenge.

There are several major techniques for doing statistical research. Researchers prefer the two popular tools for research data analysis. The first one is a standard spreadsheet of Microsoft and the second one is a customised statistical program like SPSS. For this particular research, MS Excel was used to record data and produce table graphs and SPSS was used to analyse the data.

SPSS is an application program that allows to inserting data for further analysis in order to present tabular and graphical format (Fields, 2009). It is a vastly used application for analysing numerical data (Jennings, 2010). SPSS can handle vast volumes of data for further processing.

Due to the way SPSS records all gathered data independently from the findings, it guarantees that the information is maintained separately from the data itself (Cunningham and Aldrich, 2012). When compared to Microsoft Excel, the study findings are kept in the same data spreadsheet, raising the danger of inadvertently duplicating essential data throughout the research process. In this study, the SPSS software was shown to be the most effective method of understanding and analysing the data collected. Secondary analysis was studied and analysed, as well as SPSS specialists, to assist the researcher with using the mathematical programme of the SPSS.

Descriptive research was performed using frequency distributions, and Cronbach's Alpha was conducted to test the reliability of the data. Cross tabulation was used to determine the frequency of the guest's perception and expectations response. To analyse the gap of the expectation and mean and analysis was executed.

3.6.2.11 Statistical Analysis:

The data analysis was done in two parts, the basic analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics to describe the data findings and the major analysis was conducted to compare the means and test the hypothesis. Basic analysis, which comprises statistical measures on the demographic items and LSQUAL dimensions, was carried out in order to make the data easier to comprehend and interpret. One-way ANOVA and nonparametric correlation are two of the most important statistical tests. The gap score analysis is carried out by calculating the difference between the perception score and the customer expectation score for each kind of lodging in the dataset under consideration. The reliability and validity of the LSQUAL model for each dimension's data set are also included in the main study. Cronbach's alpha was calculated for each characteristic because Cronbach's alpha is a statistic that is used to determine the internal consistency of data.

3.6.2.11.1 One-way Anova:

In alternative approaches, one should always consider the whole effect of each measure. Independent groups, one-way ("analysis of variance") is used to evaluate if statistical proof shows that the related population means are substantially different. In statistical analysis, one-way is referred to as a parametric test. A dependent variable is a variable that is reliant on another. It is also characterised as the grouping variable or element. It is used to classify instances into two or more reciprocally exclusive levels. It is also known as an independent variable or factor.

Requirements for data:

1. A continuous dependent variable is required
2. An independent variable that has a categorical distribution.
3. There are cases in which values are present on both the dependent and independent variables.
4. Independent samples or groupings of people
5. No subject in either group can stimulus individuals in the other group. 3. No group can influence subjects in the other group

6. Data from a random sample of the population is collected.

7. The dependent variable for each group was distributed in a usual manner.

1. Uneven population distributions, particularly those with fat tails or highly skewed, have a significant impact on the test's statistical power.

2. A breach of normality may result in pretty accurate p values in moderate or large samples.

The homogeneity of variances is a seventh characteristic (i.e., variances approximately equal across groups)

The p-value for the overall F test is untrustworthy when this assumption is broken, as is the case when the sample sizes vary across groups.

In the case of a violation of this assumption, regardless of equality in group size, the findings of post hoc testing may not be reliable.

When doing a one-way, researchers often adhere to a number of general guidelines:

- There must be at least six participants in each group (ideally more; inferences about the population will be more tenuous if there are too few subjects).
- Balanced designs are ideal (i.e., each group has the same number of participants); Violations of any of the criteria or assumptions may jeopardise the validity of the F test in highly imbalanced designs.

It can be used in another way, and this implies that at least one of the methods is distinct from the others. It does not, however, specify which meaning is distinct from the others. It is necessary to do contrasts in the tests to determine whether particular pairs of means are substantially different.

Setup of the data:

At least two variables (expressed in columns) should be included in the data set since they will be utilised in the analysis. A categorical independent variable with at least two groups, and a continuous dependent variable with at least two groups, should be used. Each row of the dataset must represent a distinct subject or experimental unit. Actual and predicted findings in any research is due to chance or if it is due to a link between the variables.

3.6.2.11.2 Cross table Crosstabs:

A cross-tabulation is a particular kind of table that is used to illustrate the connection between two categorical variables. Frequency tables are used to describe a single category variable. The classifications of one variable define the table's rows, while the categories of the other variable decide the table's columns in a cross-tabulation. The how often a specific collection of categories happened is recorded in the table's columns. The total number of measurements for that category is usually shown in the table's edges.

Frequency tables are used to describe a single category variable at a time. A cross-tabulation is a particular kind of table that is used to describe the connection between two categorical variables (or "crosstab" for short). In a cross-tabulation, the rows of the table are determined by the categories of one variable, while the columns of the table are determined by the categories of the other variable. This table contains information on the number of times a specific combination of categories was encountered in the data set. On the "edges" (also known as "margins") of the table, the total number of observations for that category is usually shown.

- A crosstabulation is another name for this kind of table.
- A table that can be used both ways.
- A contingency table is a table that lists all possible outcomes.

The cross-tabulation is shown in the table above. After selecting the boxes for Observed Count, Expected Count.

3.6.2.11.3 Spearman's rank correlation method:

Spearman's correlation coefficient (r_s , often abbreviated as r_s) is a measure of the strength of the connection between two ranking variables, and it is calculated as follows: According to Lehmann and D'Abbrera (2006), it is a nonparametric rank statistic that assesses the strength of the relationship between two independent variables. In other words, the test is carried out in order to assess the degree to which two category variables are aligned. It is shown by a positive correlation coefficient if the levels are in line; otherwise, it is indicated by a negative correlation coefficient.

When no numerical measurements can be made, ordinal data can be used to identify the best and worst, as well as the most and least favoured, in a list of data (a rank). Ordinal data can be used in situations where there is no numerical measurement but where best and worst, as well as most and least favoured, can be identified (Curwin and Slater, 2007). Nonetheless, in circumstances where the best and the worst options must be recognised but it is difficult to determine how much better the first option is than the second, it is essential to proceed with care in the interpretation of a rank correlation coefficient. It was thus decided to use Spearman's rank correlation test to evaluate the relationship between the variables after speaking with several statisticians and reviewing internet literature on SPSS software.

Using the straight difference as a way of investigating the gap between expectations and perceptions would be another option. However, this is regarded unwise since it is inapplicable when working with ordinal data, as is the case here. Spearman's Correlation was the statistical test to apply for the data in this research since it allowed us to determine the ranks of the data first, and then compute the gaps between them.

The procedure of using Spearman's correlation technique includes a check to ensure that the data to be analysed is capable of being analysed using this method. This is essential because Spearman's correlation can only be used if the data meets two of the assumptions that are needed for the technique to provide a valid result. If the data does not satisfy these assumptions, the method will not work. For the sake of this exercise, it is assumed that that the two variables should be assessed on an ordinal, intervallic, or ratio scale.

Given that the data in this research was gathered using an ordinal Likert scale, this assumption may be supported by the findings. According to the second premise, there is a monotonic connection between the two variables in question. When the values of the variables grow in tandem, or when the values of one variable increase as the value of the other variable declines, a monotonic connection is established. The statistical techniques that were utilised to test the hypotheses are summarised in the following table.

Table 8: Statistical techniques for hypothesis testing: Author's own work

Research Question	Hypothesis	The method used to

		test the hypothesis
How Does the service quality differ between the conventional hotel and shared accommodation?	<p>H1-1: There exists a variation in the service quality gap between hotels and shared accommodation.</p> <p>H1-0: There is no variation in the service quality gap between hotels and shared accommodation.</p>	One-way Anova
Do the hotels and shared accommodation have the same level of the customer's expectation?	<p>H2-1- There is a variation in the guest's expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation.</p> <p>H2-0: There exists no variation in the guest's expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation.</p>	One-way Anova
Do the hotels and shared accommodation have the same level of the customer's perception?	<p>H3-1: There is a variation on the guest's perception towards the hotel and shared accommodation</p> <p>H3-0: There exists no variation in the guest's perception towards the hotels and shared accommodation.</p>	One-way Anova
1. How does the gap of the service quality factors influence the choice of future accommodation?	<p>H4-1: Choice of future accommodation significantly depend on the Satisfaction level</p> <p>H4-0: Choice of future accommodation</p>	Spearman's rank correlation

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which factor do guests consider most for choosing accommodation? 	<p>does not depend on satisfaction level.</p>	
<p>How does the customer gap influence the satisfaction level?</p>	<p>H5-1: There exists a negative correlation between the gap of the service quality factors and the satisfaction level.</p> <p>H5-0: The exists no correlation between the gap of the service quality factors and the satisfaction level.</p>	<p>Spearman's rank correlation</p>

3.7: Conclusion:

The above methodology chapter went through the techniques that were used to carry out the research. The research process are explored in dept from selecting the best research approach to creating the most efficient and meaningful study design. The sampling procedure, primary and secondary data collection technique, questionnaire design, scale development techniques that were used for this study were clarified. This survey used content analysis technique and data triangulation, which combined the accommodation guests reviews and feedback from several online accommodation reservation channels to form the LSQUAL factors for measuring service quality of the accommodation users. Quantitative data collection using a questionnaire procedure along with the data coding procedure, statistical analysis tools were also discussed in detail. The following chapter presents the empirical findings of the survey in detail.

CHAPTER 4: RESEARCH RESULTS AND ANALYSIS:

4.1 Introduction:

The aim of this chapter is to disclose the findings on the primary data. Extensive secondary research through content analysis has been conducted on the guest reviews that were selected randomly from different booking channels like bookin.com, Expedia, Trip advisor and choice hotels to construct the LSQUAL factors for the primary data collection through questionnaire.

Primary research was conducted to find out the information that could not be collected through the secondary research which is the expectation and perception of the guests on their stay either on the hotel or shared accommodation through a questionnaire. Emphasis has been given to collecting information about guests' demographic information, tour purpose, SERVQUAL dimensions, satisfaction and return intentions. An almost equal proportion of the hotels and shared accommodation have been picked up through filtering the same criteria.

According to chapter three, research methodology, this study examined five dimensions of the hotel and shared accommodation service quality, which was then subdivided into numerous additional variables under each dimension. A total of 298 accommodation guests participated in this survey. and the questionnaire survey was administered over three weeks. The researcher had the privilege of meeting hotel and shared housing customers who were supposed to leave their accommodations from 08:00 to 11:00 a.m. As a consequence, there were fewer answer mistakes and fewer surveys that were not completed. For this research purpose accommodation guests only older than 18 years were approached.

The quantitative analysis of the questionnaire is addressed in the next part under the five features of tangibility, reliability, assurance, empathy, and responsiveness.

4.2 Demographic Analysis:

One of the research's goals was to "explore the effect of changes in the demographic characteristics of accommodation customers on the development of hotel and shared lodgings." As a consequence, it is critical to emphasise some of the demographic findings

from the study to illustrate the demographic changes that are occurring in London as a result of the present pandemic crisis.

4.2.1 Gender:

A total of 298 questionnaires were filled without any errors, of which, 139 (47%) were by male accommodation guests and 159 (53%) were by female accommodation guests, which corresponded to the general ratio of male to female accommodation guests observed for the survey. The following table reflects the proportion of male and female participants in this questionnaire survey.

Table 9: Gender

Gender	Frequency	Per cent	Valid Per cent
Female	159	53.36	53.4
Male	139	46.64	46.6
Total	298	100.00	100.0

4.2.2 Age Group:

During the self-administered survey, visitors from a variety of age groups were contacted by the researchers. The age group between 31 and 35 years old has been the most often travelled with hotel and shared accommodations, possibly because they were travelling for work, business, or an important reason under the lockdown limitations. The following table represents the questionnaire survey findings for the different age groups of participants.

Table 10: Age Group

Age	Frequency	Per cent	Valid Per cent
18-25 Years	60	20.1	20.1
26 to 30 Years	74	24.8	24.8
31 to 35 Years	89	29.9	29.9
36 to 40 Years	40	13.4	13.4
41 to 45 Years	20	6.7	6.7

Above 45 Years	15	5.0	5.0
Total	298	100.0	100.0

Figure 3: Age group

These demographic findings were significant because they demonstrated that travel patterns had shifted after the epidemic era started in 2019.

4.2.3 Nationality:

London has a higher proportion of expats than citizens, it was critical to learn about the various nations that stayed in hotels and shared accommodations throughout my research. Consequently, it is critical to understand which countries have stayed in the hotel and shared lodgings on a more frequent basis.

Table 11: Nationality

Nationality	Frequency	Per cent
European Countries	81	27.2
UK	165	55.4
USA/Canada	19	6.4

Asian Countries	33	11.1
Total	298	100.0

Figure 4: Nationality

The greatest proportions were from the UK (55%), followed by the EU (27.2%). Other nationalities that were surveyed were 18%. It is important to note here that a high percentage of accommodation guests stayed in the hotel and shared accommodation are from the UK as they travelled to for work and business purposes. It is critical for hotels and shared accommodations to recognise that different ethnicities and cultures have varying expectations and perceptions of the hotel and shared accommodation; as a result, hotels and shared accommodations should analyse their guests' cultural backgrounds and improve their service quality as a result of this analysis.

4.2.4 Accommodation Type:

A total number of 298 accommodation guests have participated successfully in this survey. The following table shows the ratio of the participation

Table 12: Accommodation type

Accommodation Type	Frequency	Per cent
Hotel	151	50.7
Shared Accommodation	147	49.3

Total	298	100.0
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4.2.5 Summary of Demographic Results:

To conclude the demographic, accommodation guests from the UK have stayed more during the current travel restrictions. The age group and nationality of the visitors that stayed in the accommodations were the demographic findings that were addressed. There has been a substantial shift in the travelling patterns and types of accommodations used by visitors staying in hotels or shared accommodations in the central London area, according to the findings of all of the demographic groups examined.

4.3 The findings of the expectations and perceptions of accommodation guests:

Taking into consideration the participants' expectations and assessments, the questionnaire was created for the participants. There were 22 questions in each of the three sections. Respondents were asked to choose the most suitable number on a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5, with 1 representing strongly agree and 5 representing strongly disagree, based on their anticipation and impression. The next parts of this chapter will concentrate on analysing each dimension and newly discovered variables to fit the industry-specific factors in order to evaluate the overall quality of service provided by hotels and shared accommodations in central London.

5.3.1 Dimension one: TANGIBILITY:

Presence of modern equipment:

Expectation:

The table below shows the responses on the expectation of the participants on the question about the presence of modern equipment in the accommodation they stayed in. 66.2% of hotel guests have strongly agreed that they expect the presence of modern equipment, 28.5% of hotel guests agreed to expect the presence of modern equipment and only 5% neither agreed nor disagreed to expect the presence of modern equipment in the hotel. There were no participants who disagreed or even strongly disagreed to expect the presence of modern equipment in the conventional hotels. While 68% of shared accommodation guests have very

high expectations of the presence of modern equipment in any shared accommodation. A decent number of shared accommodation guests, which is 27.2% agreed to expect modern equipment in any shared accommodation. Just below 5% shared accommodation guests remained neutral on their expectation towards the presence of modern equipment in the shared accommodation. The shared accommodation guests also did not disagree or even strongly disagree on their expectation to have modern equipment in the shared accommodation.

Table 13: Presence of modern equipment-expectation

E T1 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Presence of modern equipment			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E T1	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	8	7	15
		% within Accommodation Type	5.3%	4.8%	5.0%
	Agree	Count	43	40	83
		% within Accommodation Type	28.5%	27.2%	27.9%
	Strongly Agree	Count	100	100	200
		% within Accommodation Type	66.2%	68.0%	67.1%
Total		Count	151	147	298

In summary, most of the participants (above 65%) for both conventional and shared accommodations expected the presence of modern equipment in the accommodation.

Figure 5: Presence of modern equipment-expectation

The bar graph for the expectation of Presence of modern equipment with accommodation type. According to the above graphs, we conclude that both hotel and shared accommodation expectation on the presence of modern equipment is very high.

Perception:

Table 14: Presence of modern equipment-perception

P T1 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Presence of modern equipment		Accommodation Type			Total
		Hotel	Shared Accommodation		
P T1	Strongly Disagree	Count	2	0	2
		% within Accommodation	1.3%	0.0%	0.7%

	Type				
Disagree	Count	23	26	49	
	% within Accommodation Type	15.2%	17.7%	16.4%	
Neither agree nor disagree	Count	67	36	103	
	% within Accommodation Type	44.4%	24.5%	34.6%	
Agree	Count	46	65	111	
	% within Accommodation Type	30.5%	44.2%	37.2%	
Strongly Agree	Count	13	20	33	
	% within Accommodation Type	8.6%	13.6%	11.1%	
Total	Count	151	147	298	
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

The above contingency table shows the association between the presence of modern equipment perception with accommodation type. The 67 respondents of hotel and 36 of shared accommodation remained neutral on the presence of modern equipment. Only 1.3% of hotel guests strongly disagreed with having found modern equipment, while no share

accommodation guests strongly disagreed that they found modern equipment in the shared accommodation. Around 15% to 17 % of the accommodation guest has reported disagreeing with the presence of modern equipment. Near about 31% of hotel guests have agreed that they found modern equipment in the hotel, while a surprising number (44.2%) of shared accommodation guests agreed to have modern equipment in the shared accommodation. The percentage of the hotel guest who has strongly agreed that the hotels have modern equipment is 8.6%, besides 13.6% shared accommodation guests reported to be strongly agreed about the presence of modern equipment.

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the perception on the presence on the presence of modern equipment slightly differs between the hotel and shared accommodation guests.

Figure 6: Presence of modern equipment-perception

The attractiveness of the physical features:

Expectation:

The below table represents the responses on the expectation of the participants on the question about the attractiveness of the physical features on the accommodation they stayed

in. 46.4% of hotel guests have strongly agreed that they expect the physical features to be attractive, while 51% shared accommodation guests strongly agreed to expect the attractive physical feature. A similar proportion of the hotel and shared accommodation guests agreed that they expect attractive physical features in the accommodation, which are 37% and 35.4%, respectively. Near about 17% of hotel guests and 14% of shared accommodation guests remained neutral on their expectation towards the attractiveness of the physical features in the accommodation. Similar nil response to the modern equipment has been found towards the expectation on the attractiveness of the physical features from both of the hotel and shared accommodation guests.

A total of almost 85% of the hotel and shared accommodation guests have the higher expectation of finding attractive physical features in the accommodation

Table 15: Attractiveness of the physical features-Expectation

E T2 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
The attractiveness of the physical features			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E T2	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	25	20	45
		Expected Count	22.8	22.2	45.0
		% within Accommodation Type	16.6%	13.6%	15.1%
	Agree	Count	56	52	108
		Expected Count	54.7	53.3	108.0
		% within Accommodation Type	37.1%	35.4%	36.2%
	Strongly Agree	Count	70	75	145

		Expected Count	73.5	71.5	145.0
		% within Accommodation Type	46.4%	51.0%	48.7%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

The above bar graph represents the distribution of the expectation towards attractive physical features for hotels and shared accommodation.

Perception:

Table 16: Attractiveness of the physical features-perception

P T2 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
The attractiveness of the physical features			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodat ion	
P T2	Strongly Disagree	Count	4	1	5
		Expected Count	2.5	2.5	5.0
		% within Accommodation Type	2.6%	0.7%	1.7%
	Disagree	Count	40	20	60
		Expected Count	30.4	29.6	60.0

		% within Accommodation Type	26.5%	13.6%	20.1%
Neither agree nor disagree		Count	60	71	131
		Expected Count	66.4	64.6	131.0
		% within Accommodation Type	39.7%	48.3%	44.0%
Agree		Count	34	42	76
		Expected Count	38.5	37.5	76.0
		% within Accommodation Type	22.5%	28.6%	25.5%
Strongly Agree		Count	13	13	26
		Expected Count	13.2	12.8	26.0
		% within Accommodation Type	8.6%	8.8%	8.7%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

The information in the preceding table reflects the perspective of the hotel and shared accommodation guests toward the attractiveness of a physical element. Respondents from hotels and shared accommodation guests (8.6 per cent from hotels and 8.8 per cent from shared accommodations) strongly agreed that the accommodation had visually appealing physical elements. In a recent survey, 22.5 per cent of hotel guests and 28.6 per cent of shared accommodation guests felt that the accommodations' physical characteristics are

appealing. The majority of lodging guests (65 per cent) are neither agreeing nor disagreeing with the statement about the presence of appealing physical elements in the hotel. While 26.5 per cent of hotel guests disagreed that they found visually appealing physical features in the hotel, only 13.6 per cent of shared accommodation guests disagreed that shared accommodation providers provide visually appealing physical features, which is nearly half the per centage of hotel guests. In comparison, only 2.6 per cent of hotel visitors strongly disagreed with the statement that the hotel offered beautiful physical equipment, whereas only 0.7 per cent of shared accommodation customers strongly disagreed with the statement that the shared housing had attractive physical characteristics

Figure 7: Attractiveness of the physical features-perception

The above bar chart reflects the guest experience on the appeal of the physical features in the hotel and shared accommodation. The overall perception towards shared accommodation is better to compare to the hotels in case of offering attractive physical features.

Presence of safety and security equipment:

Expectation:

Table 17: Table 19: Presence of safety and security equipment-Expectation

E T3 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Presence of safety and security equipment			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E T3	Disagree	Count	1	0	1
		Expected Count	.5	.5	1.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.7%	0.0%	0.3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	3	4	7
		Expected Count	3.5	3.5	7.0
		% within Accommodation Type	2.0%	2.7%	2.3%
	Agree	Count	56	42	98
		Expected Count	49.7	48.3	98.0
		% within Accommodation Type	37.1%	28.6%	32.9%
	Strongly Agree	Count	91	101	192
		Expected Count	97.3	94.7	192.0
		% within Accommodation Type	60.3%	68.7%	64.4%
Total		Count	151	147	298

	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

The information in the preceding table is a representation of the existence of safety and security devices in the accommodation. The majority of hotels and shared accommodations strongly support the need that safety and security equipment to be kept on the grounds of the establishment. A total of 60.3 per cent and 68.7% of the population live in hotels and shared accommodations, according to statistics. Approximately 37% of hotel guests and 48% of shared accommodation guests have stated that they anticipate the presence of safety and security devices on the premises of the accommodation. Only a tiny per centage of those who answered the survey said they had the utmost confidence in the existence of safety and security devices.

Figure 8: Presence of safety and security equipment-Expectation

The chart above reflects the high expectation on the present safety and security equipment of the accommodation premises.

Perception:

Table 18: Presence of safety and security equipment-Perception

P T3 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Presence of safety and security equipment			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P T3	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	1	1
		Expected Count	.5	.5	1.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.0%	0.7%	0.3%
	Disagree	Count	15	13	28
		Expected Count	14.2	13.8	28.0
		% within Accommodation Type	9.9%	8.8%	9.4%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	31	39	70
		Expected Count	35.5	34.5	70.0
		% within Accommodation Type	20.5%	26.5%	23.5%
	Agree	Count	81	49	130
		Expected Count	65.9	64.1	130.0
		% within Accommodation Type	53.6%	33.3%	43.6%

	Strongly Agree	Count	24	45	69
		Expected Count	35.0	34.0	69.0
		% within Accommodation Type	15.9%	30.6%	23.2%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

According to the above data, almost 16% of hotel guests and 31% of shared accommodation guests strongly agree that the accommodation maintains safety and security equipment on the premises. The majority of hotel guests, about 54 per cent, stated that they discovered safety and security equipment on hotel grounds, while this percentage is 33.3 per cent for shared housing. One-fifth of hotel visitors and one-fourth of shared accommodation guests were unconcerned about the safety and security equipment in their particular accommodations. Approximately 10% of hotel and shared accommodation customers disagreed on the availability of safety and security devices on the premises. There has been no complaint of a lack of safety and security equipment from hotel guests, whereas just one shared accommodation visitor has reported a lack of safety and security equipment.

Figure 9: Presence of safety and security equipment-Perception

The above graph visually reflects the perception of the safety and security equipment on the accommodation premises.

Employee’s appearance with professional attire:

Expectation:

Table 19; Employee’s appearance with professional attire-Expectation

E T4 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Employee’s appearance with professional attire:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E T4	Disagree	Count	0	26	26
		Expected Count	13.2	12.8	26.0

		% within Accommodation Type	0.0%	17.7%	8.7%
Neither agree nor disagree	Count		51	25	76
	Expected Count		38.5	37.5	76.0
	% within Accommodation Type		33.8%	17.0%	25.5%
Agree	Count		90	77	167
	Expected Count		84.6	82.4	167.0
	% within Accommodation Type		59.6%	52.4%	56.0%
Strongly Agree	Count		10	19	29
	Expected Count		14.7	14.3	29.0
	% within Accommodation Type		6.6%	12.9%	9.7%
Total	Count		151	147	298
	Expected Count		151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

According to the above table, hotel and shared accommodation guests do not place a great value on hotel workers' professional look. However, the expectation of properly attired workers is double that of shared accommodation guests compared to hotel guests, which is almost 13 per cent. The majority of hotel and shared accommodation customers want hotel and shared accommodation staff to dress professionally while on duty. These figures are 59.6 and 52.4 per cent, respectively. Almost 34% of hotel guests have no clear expectation of the

staff professional dress, while 17% of shared accommodation guests have a neutral attitude in this respect. No hotel visitor disagreed that hotel workers should dress professionally, while almost 18 per cent of shared accommodation guests disagreed that shared accommodation personnel should dress professionally.

Figure 10: Employee's appearance with professional attire-Expectation

The above bar diagram reflects the survey participants expectation on the employee appearance with professional attire while they are on duty.

Perception:

Table 20: Employee's appearance with professional attire-perception

P T4 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation			
Employee's appearance with professional attire:	Accommodation Type		Total
	Hotel	Shared Accommodation	

P T4	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	15	15
		Expected Count	7.6	7.4	15.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.0%	10.2%	5.0%
	Disagree	Count	12	0	12
		Expected Count	6.1	5.9	12.0
		% within Accommodation Type	7.9%	0.0%	4.0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	74	68	142
		Expected Count	72.0	70.0	142.0
		% within Accommodation Type	49.0%	46.3%	47.7%
	Agree	Count	58	30	88
		Expected Count	44.6	43.4	88.0
		% within Accommodation Type	38.4%	20.4%	29.5%
	Strongly Agree	Count	7	34	41
		Expected Count	20.8	20.2	41.0
		% within Accommodation Type	4.6%	23.1%	13.8%
Total	Count	151	147	298	
	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0	

	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
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The above primary data found on the guest perception about the employees' professional is reflected on the above table. 23% of the shared accommodation guest has strongly agreed that they found that the employees wear professional attire when they are on duty. On the other side, only 4.6 % of the hotel guest strongly agreed to have found the hotel employees wear professional attire. 38.4% of the hotel guest moderately agreed that hotel employees wear professional attire, A relatively low proportion (20%) of the shared accommodation guest have reported to moderate agree to have found the employees professionally dressed. Around half of the hotel and shared accommodation guests were neither agreed nor disagreed on the question related to the professional attire of the employees.

Figure 11: Employee's appearance with professional attire-perception

The above graph shows the questionnaire response of the survey participants regarding the question on the professional attire of the hotel and shared accommodation employees.

5.3.2 Dimension two: RELIABILITY:

Commitment completion effectiveness:

Expectation:

The table below represents the accommodation guest’s expectation on the effective completion of the offered commitment of the reliability dimension. It has been found from the primary data that near about 45% of participants agree to expect the hotel provider to complete the offered commitment. In the case of shared accommodation, the percentage is relatively high, which is 61%. Almost 6% hotel and shared accommodation guest has shown their high expectation on the commitment completion by the accommodation provider. There exists a huge fluctuation who remain neutral on this question that is 43% for the hotel and 15.6% for the shared accommodation. The disagreement is relatively low for this factor for both of the accommodation types.

Table 21: Commitment completion effectiveness: Expectation

E RE1 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Commitment completion effectiveness:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E RE1	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	1	1
		Expected Count	.5	.5	1.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.0%	0.7%	0.3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	60	20	80
		Expected Count	40.5	39.5	80.0
		% within Accommodation Type	39.7%	13.6%	26.8%
	Agree	Count	27	76	103
		Expected Count	52.2	50.8	103.0

		% within Accommodation Type	17.9%	51.7%	34.6%
	Strongly Agree	Count	64	50	114
		Expected Count	57.8	56.2	114.0
		% within Accommodation Type	42.4%	34.0%	38.3%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 12: Commitment completion effectiveness: Expectation

According to the above graphs, we conclude that a similar proportion of the respondents of the hotel of remains either neutral or strongly agreed whereas most of the shared

accommodation guests have either agreed or strongly agreed that they expect the shared accommodation provider to complete the offered commitment effectively.

Perception:

The primary data represented in the following table shows that the high number of shared accommodation guests has found the shared accommodation to complete the commitment effectively. About this factor, 44% of hotel guests have agreed to have found effective completion of the commitment by the hotels. A similar proportion of 6% of the accommodation guest strongly agreed to experience effective commitment completion for both of the accommodation types. 6.6% of hotel guests disagreed that the hotels failed to complete the commitment effectively. In the case of shared accommodation, this proportion is comparatively double that of the hotel. No hotel guest has strongly disagreed that they found effective completion of the commitment and only a few participants experienced the failure of the shared accommodation to complete the commitment effectively. Moreover, 43% of the hotel guest remained undecided whether the hotel completed the commitments effectively and the proportion is 15.6% for the shared accommodation.

Table 22: Commitment completion effectiveness: Perception

P RE1 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Commitment completion effectiveness:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P RE1	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	2	2
		Expected Count	1.0	1.0	2.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.0%	1.4%	0.7%
	Disagree	Count	10	23	33

		Expected Count	16.7	16.3	33.0
		% within Accommodation Type	6.6%	15.6%	11.1%
		Count	65	23	88
	Neither agree nor disagree	Expected Count	44.6	43.4	88.0
		% within Accommodation Type	43.0%	15.6%	29.5%
		Count	67	90	157
	Agree	Expected Count	79.6	77.4	157.0
		% within Accommodation Type	44.4%	61.2%	52.7%
		Count	9	9	18
	Strongly Agree	Expected Count	9.1	8.9	18.0
		% within Accommodation Type	6.0%	6.1%	6.0%
		Count	151	147	298
	Total	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		Count			

Figure 13: Commitment completion effectiveness: Perception

The above graph shows the distribution of the guest experience on the effectiveness of the commitment completion for both of the accommodation types.

Accurate bookkeeping:

Expectation:

The results from the survey show that 57.6% of hotel guests and 61.2% shared accommodation guests expect that the accommodation provider should keep the proper records. Almost one-third of the hotel guest has high expectation on accurate record-keeping whereas a relatively low proportion (2.7%) of shared accommodation guest highly expect accurate record keeping. The neutral proportion on this factor for hotels and shared accommodation is 11.3% and 29.3% respectively. None of the hotel guests disagreed on this factor for the hotel, however, only 6.8% shared accommodation guests disagreed to expect proper record-keeping for their stay.

Table 23: Accurate bookkeeping: Expectation

E RE2 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Accurate bookkeeping:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E RE2	Disagree	Count	0	10	10
		Expected Count	5.1	4.9	10.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.0%	6.8%	3.4%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	17	43	60
		Expected Count	30.4	29.6	60.0
		% within Accommodation Type	11.3%	29.3%	20.1%
	Agree	Count	87	90	177
		Expected Count	89.7	87.3	177.0
		% within Accommodation Type	57.6%	61.2%	59.4%
	Strongly Agree	Count	47	4	51
		Expected Count	25.8	25.2	51.0
		% within Accommodation Type	31.1%	2.7%	17.1%
Total		Count	151	147	298

	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 14: Accurate bookkeeping: Expectation

As per the above graph drawn from the primary results most of the hotel guests either agree or strongly agree that they expect the hotel to keep the proper records of their stay while most of the shared accommodation users moderately agree that shared accommodation should keep an accurate record of their stay.

Perception:

The primary data represented in the following table shows that the high number of shared accommodation guests could not decide whether the hotel or the shared accommodation keep the proper records of the stay. About this factor, 40% of hotel guests have agreed to have found accurate record-keeping by the hotels. An almost similar proportion of 37% of the accommodation guest agreed to experience accurate record-keeping by the hotels. 7% to 9% of accommodation users have strongly agreed to find accommodation providers to keep

records of the stay. Only 3% and .7% hotel and shared accommodation users respectively reported not to find any record-keeping in the accommodation during their stay.

Table 24: Accurate bookkeeping: Perception

P RE2 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Accurate bookkeeping:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P RE2	Disagree	Count	5	1	6
		Expected Count	3.0	3.0	6.0
		% within Accommodation Type	3.3%	0.7%	2.0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	74	78	152
		Expected Count	77.0	75.0	152.0
		% within Accommodation Type	49.0%	53.1%	51.0%
	Agree	Count	61	55	116
		Expected Count	58.8	57.2	116.0
		% within Accommodation Type	40.4%	37.4%	38.9%
	Strongly Agree	Count	11	13	24
		Expected Count	12.2	11.8	24.0

		% within Accommodation Type	7.3%	8.8%	8.1%
Total	Count		151	147	298
	Expected Count		151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 15: Accurate bookkeeping: Perception

The above graph represents that most of the accommodation guests did neither agree nor disagree on accurate record-keeping by the accommodation providers while a two-fifth proportion of the guests agreed that they found accurate record-keeping in the accommodation.

Working condition of the equipment:

Expectation:

The primary result shows that all of the hotel and shared accommodation guests expect to find the equipment in the accommodation to be in well working condition. Almost 65% of hotel guests belongs very high expectations of the equipment condition whereas 51% of the shared accommodation guest have high expectations of the condition of the accommodation equipment. Moreover, 35% of hotel guests 49% shared accommodation guests agreed that they expect sound equipment. None of the accommodation guests expects the equipment to be faulty during their stay. The table below represents the proportion of the accommodation guest’s expectation on the equipment condition.

Table 25: Working condition of the equipment: -Expectation

E RE3 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Working condition of the equipment:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E RE3	Agree	Count	53	72	125
		Expected Count	63.3	61.7	125.0
		% within Accommodation Type	35.1%	49.0%	41.9%
	Strongly Agree	Count	98	75	173
		Expected Count	87.7	85.3	173.0
		% within Accommodation Type	64.9%	51.0%	58.1%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0

	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
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Figure 16: Working condition of the equipment: Expectation

From the above bar chart, it is quite clear that all of the guests expect that the equipment in the accommodation should be completely sound during their stay.

Perception:

According to the questionnaire data collection, accommodation guests have mixed perceptions of the accommodation equipment condition. The table below reflects the guest experience on the equipment condition during their stay. Two-fifths of the guest from both of the accommodation types agreed that they have found the equipment provided by the accommodation was in good working condition. One fourth of the hotel guest has reported that the hotels they stayed in have met their expectation very satisfactorily. Whereas 155 of the shared accommodation guest thinks the shared accommodation highly meet their expectation on the equipment condition factor. One-fifth of both accommodation users could not decide whether the equipment has met their expectations or not. Hotels have failed to meet 10.6% of their guest expectation on the condition of the equipment factor. Relatively,

shred accommodation could not satisfy 21% of their guests on the efficiency of the equipment.

Table 26: Working condition of the equipment: Perception

P RE3 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Working condition of the equipment:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P RE3	Strongly Disagree	Count	0	3	3
		Expected Count	1.5	1.5	3.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.0%	2.0%	1.0%
	Disagree	Count	16	31	47
		Expected Count	23.8	23.2	47.0
		% within Accommodation Type	10.6%	21.1%	15.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	32	28	60
		Expected Count	30.4	29.6	60.0
		% within Accommodation Type	21.2%	19.0%	20.1%
	Agree	Count	63	63	126
		Expected Count	63.8	62.2	126.0

		% within Accommodation Type	41.7%	42.9%	42.3%
	Strongly Agree	Count	40	22	62
		Expected Count	31.4	30.6	62.0
		% within Accommodation Type	26.5%	15.0%	20.8%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 17: Working condition of the equipment: Perception

The above bar chart reflects the guest experience level from using the equipment on the accommodation during their stay.

Secured payment service:

Expectation:

The primary data from the hotel and shares accommodation guests’ reveals that both of the accommodation guest’s expectation is high in terms of the security on the payment service. The proportion of the high level of expectation on the secured payment service of the hotel guest is 44% whereas 58% of the shared accommodation guest wants highly secured payment service. 52% of the hotel users and 42% of the shared accommodation users agree that they want security on the payment services. 4% of the hotel guest could not decide on the payment service factor. No guest expects insecure payment service on the accommodation.

Table 27: Secured payment service: Expectation

E RE4 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Secured payment service:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E RE4	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	6	0	6
		Expected Count	3.0	3.0	6.0
		% within Accommodation Type	4.0%	0.0%	2.0%
	Agree	Count	79	62	141
		Expected Count	71.4	69.6	141.0
		% within Accommodation Type	52.3%	42.2%	47.3%
	Strongly Agree	Count	66	85	151

		Expected Count	76.5	74.5	151.0
		% within Accommodation Type	43.7%	57.8%	50.7%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 18: Secured payment service: Expectation

The above graph represents the expectation level of the accommodation guests about the secured payment service.

Perception:

Hotel and shared accommodation guest's perception of the secure payment service is presented in the below table. It was found that 13% to 15% of the hotel and shared

accommodation respectively found that the accommodation has provided high secured payment services during their stay. 36% of the hotel guest agreed that they felt secure on the payment service during their stay while almost 50% of shared accommodation guests said they have found a moderate level of security on the payment service. 38% of the hotel guest could not decide whether the payment service was secured or not. Relatively 22.4% of guests who stayed in the shared accommodation have responded as neither agree nor disagree. 10% of the hotel guest and 15.6% of the shared accommodation guest disagree that the payment service was secured.

Table 28: Secured payment service: Perception

P RE4 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Secured payment service:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P RE4	Disagree	Count	16	23	39
		Expected Count	19.8	19.2	39.0
		% within Accommodation Type	10.6%	15.6%	13.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	58	33	91
		Expected Count	46.1	44.9	91.0
		% within Accommodation Type	38.4%	22.4%	30.5%
	Agree	Count	55	72	127
		Expected Count	64.4	62.6	127.0

		% within Accommodation Type	36.4%	49.0%	42.6%
	Strongly Agree	Count	22	19	41
		Expected Count	20.8	20.2	41.0
		% within Accommodation Type	14.6%	12.9%	13.8%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 19: Secured payment service: Perception

The above graph reflects the accommodation guests experience level on the payment security during their stay in the hotel.

Safe and secure environment:

Expectation:

The primary data from the hotel and shares accommodation guests’ reveals that both of the accommodation guest’s expectation is high in terms of the security on the premises. The proportion of the high level of expectation on the secured environment is 72.8% for both the hotel and shared accommodation. A similar result has also been found from the accommodation users that 27.2% of guests moderately expect the secured environment in the accommodation premises. It can be summarised that both hotel and share accommodation guest expects and gives priority on the security on the accommodation.

Table 29: Safe and secure environment: Expectation

E RE5 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Safe and secure environment:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E RE5	Agree	Count	41	40	81
		Expected Count	41.0	40.0	81.0
		% within Accommodation Type	27.2%	27.2%	27.2%
	Strongly Agree	Count	110	107	217
		Expected Count	110.0	107.0	217.0
		% within Accommodation Type	72.8%	72.8%	72.8%
Total		Count	151	147	298

	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 20: Safe and secure environment: Expectation

The above graph shows the high proportion of guest expectation on secured environment factor for both of the hotel and shared accommodation.

Perception:

Hotel and shared accommodation guest’s perception of the secured environment on accommodation premises is presented in the below table. It was found that 23% of the hotel guest respectively found that the accommodation has a secured environment to stay in. only 1.4% of the shared accommodation guest highly agreed that they found the shared accommodation premises to have a secured environment. 52.3%% of the hotel guest agreed that they felt secured on the premises during their stay while 56.5% % of shared accommodation guests said they have found a moderate level of secured environment present on the premises. 19% of the hotel guest could not decide whether the hotel premises were

secured or not. Relatively 33.3% of guests who stayed in the shared accommodation have responded as neither agree nor disagree on the question of a secured environment. 14.6% of the hotel guest and 8.8% of the shared accommodation guest disagree that the accommodation was safe and sound.

Table 30: Safe and secure environment: Perception

P RE5 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Safe and secure environment			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P RE5	Disagree	Count	7	13	20
		Expected Count	10.1	9.9	20.0
		% within Accommodation Type	4.6%	8.8%	6.7%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	29	49	78
		Expected Count	39.5	38.5	78.0
		% within Accommodation Type	19.2%	33.3%	26.2%
	Agree	Count	79	83	162
		Expected Count	82.1	79.9	162.0
		% within Accommodation Type	52.3%	56.5%	54.4%
	Strongly Agree	Count	36	2	38
		Expected Count	19.3	18.7	38.0

		% within Accommodation Type	23.8%	1.4%	12.8%
Total	Count		151	147	298
	Expected Count		151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 21: Safe and secure environment: Perception

The above graph shows how secure was the accommodation during their stay either in the hotel or in the shared accommodation.

5.3.3 Dimension three: Assurance

Appropriate cleanliness:

Expectation:

Appropriate cleanliness is one of the factors that both the hotel and shared accommodation guests pose a high expectation. Guests expect assurance on cleanliness. Almost half of the hotel guest has answered that they strongly agree to expect the hotels maintain a high

standard of cleanliness. The other 50% of the hotel guests have also agreed that they expect appropriate cleanliness in the hotels. Similar results were also found for the shared accommodation guest. More than 60% shared accommodation guests' expectations on the cleanliness id very high. The remaining 37% of participants of the shared accommodation guest Agreed that they expect appropriate cleanliness. There was no guest for both of the accommodation types who expect to compromise the cleanliness of the accommodation. The table below expresses the measure of the cleanliness of the accommodation.

Table 31: Appropriate cleanliness: Expectation

E A1 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Appropriate cleanliness:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E A1	Agree	Count	76	55	131
		Expected Count	66.4	64.6	131.0
		% within Accommodation Type	50.3%	37.4%	44.0%
	Strongly Agree	Count	75	92	167
		Expected Count	84.6	82.4	167.0
		% within Accommodation Type	49.7%	62.6%	56.0%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0

	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
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Figure 22: Appropriate cleanliness: Expectation

From the above chart, it can be summarised that assurance on the cleanliness factor is one of the most expected service quality factors that the guests do not want to negotiate.

Perception:

A mixed view has been found from the questionnaire survey on the cleanliness factor of the assurance dimension. A similar proportion of 15% to 16% of the hotel and shared accommodation guests strongly agreed that they experienced a high standard of cleanliness in the accommodation they stayed in. 38% to 42% of the participants from the survey moderately agreed that the accommodation maintains appropriate cleaning standards. Almost 32% of the hotel guest has neither agreed nor disagreed on the cleanliness factor as they experienced. 19% of the shared accommodation guest remained undecided on the factor. Just above 13% of accommodation guests could not be assured on the cleanliness factor they have experienced during their stay in the accommodation. Just below 1% of the hotel guest strongly disagreed that the hotels they stayed in maintain the poor standard of cleanliness.

Whereas this proportion comparatively high with in the shared accommodation guest which is 9.5%. The table below exhibits the proportion of the guest perception level on cleanliness.

Table 32: Appropriate cleanliness: Perception

P A1 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Appropriate cleanliness:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P A1	Strongly Disagree	Count	1	14	15
		Expected Count	7.6	7.4	15.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.7%	9.5%	5.0%
	Disagree	Count	20	21	41
		Expected Count	20.8	20.2	41.0
		% within Accommodation Type	13.2%	14.3%	13.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	48	28	76
		Expected Count	38.5	37.5	76.0
		% within Accommodation Type	31.8%	19.0%	25.5%
	Agree	Count	58	62	120
		Expected Count	60.8	59.2	120.0

		% within Accommodation Type	38.4%	42.2%	40.3%
Strongly Agree		Count	24	22	46
		Expected Count	23.3	22.7	46.0
		% within Accommodation Type	15.9%	15.0%	15.4%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

The bar chart below is a visual representation of the proportion of the participants that how they have found the cleanliness factor on the accommodation they stayed in.

Figure 23: Appropriate cleanliness: Perception

Comfortable bed:

Expectation:

A comfortable bed is one of the most desirable factors for both of the accommodation guests. As sleep quality depends on a comfortable bed, the guest expectation is relatively very high on that factor. Almost 70% of guests for both accommodation types expect very highly that the accommodation’s bed quality would be very high. The remaining 30% of accommodation guests have agreed that they wish to have a comfortable bed on the accommodation that chooses to stay. There was no guest who participated in the questionnaire survey who reported that their expectation in the comparison below Par on a comfortable bed, that is all the guest expects to the accommodation equip the room with a comfortable bed. The table below presents the survey results for the comfortable bed.

Table 33: Comfortable bed: Expectation

E A2 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Comfortable bed:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E A2	Agree	Count	46	46	92
		Expected Count	46.6	45.4	92.0
		% within Accommodation Type	30.5%	31.3%	30.9%
	Strongly Agree	Count	105	101	206
		Expected Count	104.4	101.6	206.0
		% within Accommodation Type	69.5%	68.7%	69.1%

Total	Count	151	147	298
	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 24: Comfortable bed: Expectation

The above bar diagram shows the expectation of a comfortable bed for both the accommodation type. In summary, a comfortable bed is one of the most expected factors for the accommodation guest.

Perception:

Hotel and shared accommodation guests have a mixed experience on the service quality factor for the comfortable bed. 10.6% of the hotel guest strongly agreed that they found a very comfortable bed in the hotel they slept in whereas this experience is almost twice (20.4%) for the shared accommodation guest. Hotel guests who have answered as agreed for comfortable bed are 43% and shared accommodation guest proportion as agreed is 34%. A

dissimilar proportion of 37.7% and 17% hotel and shared accommodation guests respectively responded as they do not either agree or disagree on comfortable bedding. Similarly, almost 10% of the hotel guest have found an uncomfortable bed and 26% of shared accommodation guests have a similar experience of bed comfort. Guest who has strongly disagreed that the hotel bed was very uncomfortable id just below 1% and for the shared accommodation this proportion is 2.7%. The following table shows the results of the primary findings on the comfortable bed.

Table 34: Comfortable bed: Perception

P A2 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Comfortable bed:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P A2	Strongly Disagree	Count	1	4	5
		Expected Count	2.5	2.5	5.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.7%	2.7%	1.7%
	Disagree	Count	12	38	50
		Expected Count	25.3	24.7	50.0
		% within Accommodation Type	7.9%	25.9%	16.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	57	25	82
		Expected Count	41.6	40.4	82.0
		% within Accommodation Type	37.7%	17.0%	27.5%

Agree	Count	65	50	115
	Expected Count	58.3	56.7	115.0
	% within Accommodation Type	43.0%	34.0%	38.6%
Strongly Agree	Count	16	30	46
	Expected Count	23.3	22.7	46.0
	% within Accommodation Type	10.6%	20.4%	15.4%
Total	Count	151	147	298
	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 25: Comfortable bed: Perception

The above graph shows a different level of counts on the comfortable bedding factor.

The efficiency of the physical features as per service offered:

Expectation:

Table 35: Efficiency of the physical features as per service offered: Expectation

E A3 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
The efficiency of the physical features as per service offered:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E A3	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	0	2	2
		Expected Count	1.0	1.0	2.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.0%	1.4%	0.7%
	Agree	Count	66	92	158
		Expected Count	80.1	77.9	158.0
		% within Accommodation Type	43.7%	62.6%	53.0%
	Strongly Agree	Count	85	53	138
		Expected Count	69.9	68.1	138.0
		% within Accommodation Type	56.3%	36.1%	46.3%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0

	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
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The primary result shows that all of the hotel and shared accommodation guests expect to be assured of the efficiency of the physical features of the accommodation... Almost 56% of hotel guests belongs very high expectations of efficiency of the physical features whereas 36.1 of the shared accommodation guest have high expectations of the efficiency of the physical features. Moreover, 43.7% of hotel guests and 62.6% shared accommodation guests agreed that the efficiency of the physical features. None of the accommodation guests expects the equipment to be faulty during their stay. The table below represents the proportion of the accommodation guest’s expectation on the efficiency of the physical features in the accommodation.

Figure 26: Efficiency of the physical features as per service offered: Expectation

The above graph represents that how high the guest expectation on the efficiency of the physical features from the hotel and shared accommodation is.

Perception:

According to the questionnaire data collection, accommodation guests have mixed perceptions of the efficiency of the physical features for both of the accommodation types. The table below reflects the guest experience on the efficiency of the physical feature during their stay. 9.3% of the hotel guest found that the hotel they stayed in had efficient physical features. This proportion for shared accommodation is 4.8%. The proportion the hotel guest who have agreed that the hotel has an efficient physical feature is 35.8% and for the shared accommodation, this percentage is 45.6%. Guest who remained undecided on the efficiency factors of the physical features are 46.4% and 30.6% for the hotels and shared accommodation respectively. 7.9% of the hotel guest have disagreed that they found efficient physical features in the hotel whereas 15.06% shared accommodation guests experienced the same. Only a few accommodation guests have strongly disagreed that there were efficient physical features present on the accommodation they stayed in.

Table 36: Efficiency of the physical features as per service offered: Perception

P A3 * Accommodation Type Cross tabulation					
The efficiency of the physical features as per service offered:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P A3	Strongly Disagree	Count	1	5	6
		Expected Count	3.0	3.0	6.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.7%	3.4%	2.0%
	Disagree	Count	12	23	35
		Expected Count	17.7	17.3	35.0
		% within Accommodation Type	7.9%	15.6%	11.7%

	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	70	45	115
		Expected Count	58.3	56.7	115.0
		% within Accommodation Type	46.4%	30.6%	38.6%
	Agree	Count	54	67	121
		Expected Count	61.3	59.7	121.0
		% within Accommodation Type	35.8%	45.6%	40.6%
	Strongly Agree	Count	14	7	21
		Expected Count	10.6	10.4	21.0
		% within Accommodation Type	9.3%	4.8%	7.0%
Total	Count	151	147	298	
	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0	
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Figure 27: Efficiency of the physical features as per service offered: Perception

The above graph shows the relative experience on the efficiency of the physical factors on the hotel and shared accommodation.

Convenient operating hours:

Expectation:

Table 37: Convenient operating hours: Expectation

E A4 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Convenient operating hours			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E A4	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	1	1	2
		Expected Count	1.0	1.0	2.0

		% within Accommodation Type	0.7%	0.7%	0.7%
	Agree	Count	85	105	190
		Expected Count	96.3	93.7	190.0
		% within Accommodation Type	56.3%	71.4%	63.8%
	Strongly Agree	Count	65	41	106
		Expected Count	53.7	52.3	106.0
		% within Accommodation Type	43.0%	27.9%	35.6%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

The above contingency table shows the expectation on convenient operating hours with both accommodation types. 85 respondents of hotel stayers and 105 respondents of shared accommodation users have agreed that they expect that the accommodation should have convenient operating times. Among the hotels' users, 43% highly expect that hotels should be very flexible on operating hours. Whereas this proportion is almost 30% for the shared accommodation. Just below 1% of the accommodation users responded as they neither agree nor disagree on this operating hour factor. No participants responded either disagree or strongly disagree on this factor.

Figure 28: Convenient operating hours: Expectation

Perception:

Hotel and shared accommodation guests have a mixed experience on the hotel operating hours. Almost 50% of the hotel users strongly agreed that the operating hours of the hotels was highly convenient for them. A comparative low proportion of 13% of the shared accommodation users found the accommodation to have convenient operating hours for them. Only 13% of the hotel user's response was that they agree to have found the hotel operates in flexibility whereas 58.5% of the shared accommodation users agreed on that factor. Neither agree nor disagree proportion on convenient operating hours factor is 35.8% and 26.5% respectively.

Table 38: Convenient operating hours; Perception

P A4 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation		
Convenient operating hours	Accommodation Type	Total

			Hotel	Shared Accommodat ion	
P A4	Disagree	Count	1	3	4
		Expected Count	2.0	2.0	4.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.7%	2.0%	1.3%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	54	39	93
		Expected Count	47.1	45.9	93.0
		% within Accommodation Type	35.8%	26.5%	31.2%
	Agree	Count	21	86	107
		Expected Count	54.2	52.8	107.0
		% within Accommodation Type	13.9%	58.5%	35.9%
	Strongly Agree	Count	75	19	94
		Expected Count	47.6	46.4	94.0
		% within Accommodation Type	49.7%	12.9%	31.5%
Total	Count	151	147	298	
	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0	
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Figure 29: Convenient operating hours: Perception

The above Bar chart shows that how hotel and shared accommodation guests have responded to the factor convenient opening hours of the assurance dimension.

5.3.4 Dimension four: EMPATHY:

Personalised attention:

Expectation:

Personalised attention is an empathy dimensional factor that most of the hotel and shared accommodation guests' expectations was found as neither agree nor disagree. This proportion is 60% for the hotel users and 76.2% for the shared accommodation users. The count of agreeing on the expectation of the respondent from the questionnaire survey is 16.6% and 13.6% for the hotel and shared accommodation respectively about the personal attention. Among the hotel guest, 17% have expressed that they strongly agreed to expect personal attention from the hotel employees, whereas no shared stayers strongly agreed to expect personal attention during their stay in the shared accommodation. Only 6% of the hotel guest and 10% of the shared accommodation guest disagree to expect personal attention during their stay on the lodging. The below table represents the proportion of guest expectation measure on personal attention factors.

Table 39: Personalised attention: Expectation

E E1 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Personalised attention			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E E1	Disagree	Count	9	15	24
		Expected Count	12.2	11.8	24.0
		% within Accommodation Type	6.0%	10.2%	8.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	91	112	203
		Expected Count	102.9	100.1	203.0
		% within Accommodation Type	60.3%	76.2%	68.1%
	Agree	Count	25	20	45
		Expected Count	22.8	22.2	45.0
		% within Accommodation Type	16.6%	13.6%	15.1%
	Strongly Agree	Count	26	0	26
		Expected Count	13.2	12.8	26.0
		% within Accommodation Type	17.2%	0.0%	8.7%
Total		Count	151	147	298

	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 30: Personalised attention: Expectation

The above graph shows the Personalised attention extraction on guests expectations for their stay in the hotel and shared accommodation.

Perception:

The questionnaire survey has revealed that personalised attention is one of the most nonaligned service quality factors among accommodation users. The table below represents the findings of the perception from the questionnaire survey of the hotel and shared accommodation guests. 31.8% of the hotel guest and almost 70% of the shared accommodation guests have responded as they neither agree nor disagree as they found on personalised attention during their stay. Only 2.6% of the hotel guest strongly agree that they experienced personalised attention during their stay in the hotel whereas no one of the share accommodation users received personalised attention while they stayed in shared accommodation. The agreed count of perception on personalised attention for the hotel and

shared accommodation is 17.9% and 13.1% respectively. Near about half of the hotel, stayers disagreed that they received personalised attention and 16% of the shared accommodation guests disagreed on that service quality factor to be present during their stay. However, just around 1% of both accommodation guests strongly disagreed with the presence of personalised attention from the employees of the accommodation.

Table 40: Personalised attention: Perception

P E1 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Personalised attention:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P E1	Strongly Disagree	Count	2	2	4
		Expected Count	2.0	2.0	4.0
		% within Accommodation Type	1.3%	1.4%	1.4%
	Disagree	Count	70	23	93
		Expected Count	47.4	45.6	93.0
		% within Accommodation Type	46.4%	15.9%	31.4%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	48	101	149
		Expected Count	76.0	73.0	149.0
		% within Accommodation Type	31.8%	69.7%	50.3%

	Agree	Count	27	19	46
		Expected Count	23.5	22.5	46.0
		% within Accommodation Type	17.9%	13.1%	15.5%
	Strongly Agree	Count	4	0	4
		Expected Count	2.0	2.0	4.0
		% within Accommodation Type	2.6%	0.0%	1.4%
Total	Count	151	145	296	
	Expected Count	151.0	145.0	296.0	
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Figure 31: Personalised attention: Perception

The above bar chart represents the count of perceived personalised attention while staying in the hotel or shared accommodation.

Employee attitude:

Expectation:

The findings on the questionnaire survey revealed that most of the accommodation users agree to have positive expectations except on employee attitude. The proportion is 54% for the hotels' guests and 61.2% for the shared accommodation guest. Almost 40% of the hotel guests strongly agree that they expect the hotel employees to have a positive attitude towards customers while this proportion is surprisingly very low (1.4%) for the shared accommodation guests. 6.6% of the hotel guest and 33.3% of the shared accommodation guest's expectation remained neutral on attitude factor.

Table 41: Employee attitude: Expectation

E E2 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Employee attitude			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E E2	Disagree	Count	0	6	6
		Expected Count	3.0	3.0	6.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.0%	4.1%	2.0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	10	49	59
		Expected Count	29.9	29.1	59.0

		% within Accommodation Type	6.6%	33.3%	19.8%
	Agree	Count	82	90	172
		Expected Count	87.2	84.8	172.0
		% within Accommodation Type	54.3%	61.2%	57.7%
	Strongly Agree	Count	59	2	61
		Expected Count	30.9	30.1	61.0
		% within Accommodation Type	39.1%	1.4%	20.5%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 32: Employee attitude: Expectation

The above graph represents the proportion of guest’s expectation count on employee attitude factor for both of the accommodation types.

Perception:

Among the hotel users, 13% of the respondents have experienced a positive attitude from the employees during their stay. Almost half of the hotel guests agreed that hotel employees possess a positive attitude. 35% of the participants from the hotel guests could not decide whether the employees have a positive attitude or not. Only a total of 3% of hotel guests strongly disagreed that hotel employees showed a positive attitude towards them. For the shared accommodation guests 78% of participants responded that they do not either agree or disagree with the attitude of shared accommodation employees, however, 20% of the shared accommodation guest found the employees positively behaved with them. The table below reflects the measure of perception of the hotel and shared accommodation guests on employee attitude.

Table 42: Employee attitude: Perception

P E2 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Employee attitude			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P E2	Strongly Disagree	Count	1	0	1
		Expected Count	.5	.5	1.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.7%	0.0%	0.3%
	Disagree	Count	3	2	5
		Expected Count	2.5	2.5	5.0
		% within Accommodation Type	2.0%	1.4%	1.7%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	53	115	168
		Expected Count	85.1	82.9	168.0
		% within Accommodation Type	35.1%	78.2%	56.4%
	Agree	Count	74	30	104
		Expected Count	52.7	51.3	104.0
		% within Accommodation Type	49.0%	20.4%	34.9%
	Strongly Agree	Count	20	0	20

		Expected Count	10.1	9.9	20.0
		% within Accommodation Type	13.2%	0.0%	6.7%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 33: Employee attitude: Perception

The above bar chart reflects how the employee attitude differs towards customers for the two different types of accommodation.

Reliability of the employees:

Expectation:

The below table shows the association on the reliability of the employees' expectations with accommodation type. 59.6% of the respondents among the hotel participants agree that they expect the hotel employee to be reliable and 48.3% of respondents of the shared accommodation agreed that the shared accommodation employees be reliable. Almost 32% of the hotel guest and 37% of the shared accommodation guest strongly agree that they wish to see reliable employees in the accommodation. 8.6% of the hotel and 14.3% of the shared accommodation guests responded on their expectation to be neither agree nor disagree on the reliability of the accommodation employees.

Table 43: Reliability of the employees: Expectation

E E3 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation							
Reliability of the employees:				Accommodation Type			Total
				Hotel	Shared Accommodation		
E E3	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	13	21	34		
		Expected Count	17.2	16.8	34.0		
		% within Accommodation Type	8.6%	14.3%	11.4%		
	Agree	Count	90	71	161		
		Expected Count	81.6	79.4	161.0		
		% within Accommodation Type	59.6%	48.3%	54.0%		
	Strongly Agree	Count	48	55	103		
		Expected Count	52.2	50.8	103.0		

		% within Accommodation Type	31.8%	37.4%	34.6%
Total	Count		151	147	298
	Expected Count		151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 34: Reliability of the employees: Expectation

Perception:

The table below reflects the experience of the hotel and shared accommodation guests on the reliability of the accommodation employees. Almost 50% of the hotel guests and 31% of the shared accommodation guests have found the employees of the relative accommodation to be reliable. Most of the hotel and shared accommodation guests could not measure the reliability of the employees as they choose to answer neither agree nor disagree on that particular service quality factor. Only a few responded disagree that the employees of both accommodation types were reliable, however near around 6% of the guest disagree that the employees were reliable.

Table 44: Reliability of the employees: Perception

P E3 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Reliability of the employees:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P E3	Strongly Disagree	Count	2	3	5
		Expected Count	2.5	2.5	5.0
		% within Accommodation Type	1.3%	2.0%	1.7%
	Disagree	Count	9	4	13
		Expected Count	6.6	6.4	13.0
		% within Accommodation Type	6.0%	2.7%	4.4%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	62	77	139
		Expected Count	70.4	68.6	139.0
		% within Accommodation Type	41.1%	52.4%	46.6%
	Agree	Count	75	46	121
		Expected Count	61.3	59.7	121.0
		% within Accommodation Type	49.7%	31.3%	40.6%
	Strongly Agree	Count	3	17	20

		Expected Count	10.1	9.9	20.0
		% within Accommodation Type	2.0%	11.6%	6.7%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 35: Reliability of the employees: Perception

The above graph shows the accommodation guests perception of the reliability of the employees.

Individual need recognition:

Expectation:

The table below represents the accommodation guest's expectation on the individual need recognition by the accommodation employees. It has been found from the primary data that near about 4% of participants agree to expect the personal need recognition by the employees. In the case of shared accommodation, the percentage is comparatively low, which is 12%. While 3.3% of hotel guests and 5.4% of the shared accommodation guests have shown their high expectation on personal need recognition by the hotel employees. There exist a huge proportion of accommodation guest who remains neutral on this question that is 44% for the hotel and 61% for the shared accommodation. There were also 11% hotel guests and 21% shared accommodation guests who disagrees that they do not expect personal recognition from the hotel employees.

Table 45: Individual need recognition: Expectation

E E4 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Individual need recognition			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E E4	Disagree	Count	17	31	48
		Expected Count	24.3	23.7	48.0
		% within Accommodation Type	11.3%	21.1%	16.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	66	90	156
		Expected Count	79.0	77.0	156.0
		% within Accommodation Type	43.7%	61.2%	52.3%
	Agree	Count	63	18	81

		Expected Count	41.0	40.0	81.0
		% within Accommodation Type	41.7%	12.2%	27.2%
		Count	5	8	13
	Strongly Agree	Expected Count	6.6	6.4	13.0
		% within Accommodation Type	3.3%	5.4%	4.4%
		Count	151	147	298
Total	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0	
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	
	Count				

Figure 36: Individual need recognition: Expectation

The above graph shows the accommodation guest expectation and perception on the personal need recognition factor.

Perception:

There was a mixed view on the hotel and shared accommodation guest’s perception on the personal need recognition of the reliability factor. A surprising 83% per cent of the shared accommodation guests have responded as neither agreed nor disagreed. This proportion for the hotel guest is 43%. A moderately high proportion of the hotel guest has disagreed to receive any personal attention from the hotel employees, while 13.6% of the guest’s responses were as disagreed with receiving personal attention from the employees. Comparatively, a very low proportion of both types of accommodation guests have either strongly agreed or strongly disagreed with receiving personal attention from the accommodation employees.

Table 46: Individual need recognition: Perception

P E4 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Individual need recognition			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P E4	Strongly Disagree	Count	2	0	2
		Expected Count	1.0	1.0	2.0
		% within Accommodation Type	1.3%	0.0%	0.7%
	Disagree	Count	63	20	83
		Expected Count	42.1	40.9	83.0
		% within Accommodation Type	41.7%	13.6%	27.9%
	Neither agree nor	Count	65	122	187

	disagree	Expected Count	94.8	92.2	187.0
		% within Accommodation Type	43.0%	83.0%	62.8%
	Agree	Count	17	5	22
		Expected Count	11.1	10.9	22.0
		% within Accommodation Type	11.3%	3.4%	7.4%
	Strongly Agree	Count	4	0	4
		Expected Count	2.0	2.0	4.0
		% within Accommodation Type	2.6%	0.0%	1.3%
	Total	Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 37: Individual need recognition: Perception

The chart above is a visual representation of the perceived personal attention from the employees of the accommodation guest.

Feelings towards customers:

Expectation:

The table below represents the accommodation guest’s expectation of the accommodation employees feelings towards the customer. Most of the shared accommodation guests has responded that they neither agree nor disagree to find soft feelings from the hotel employees. The disagree count for the shared accommodation guest id 18%. The expectation of the hotel employees on this factor is 28.5% disagree, 32.5% neither agree nor disagree and 38.4% agree.

Table 47: Feelings towards customer: Expectation

E E5 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation		
Feelings towards customer	Accommodation Type	Total

			Hotel	Shared Accommodat ion	
E E5	Disagree	Count	43	27	70
		Expected Count	35.5	34.5	70.0
		% within Accommodation Type	28.5%	18.4%	23.5%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	49	120	169
		Expected Count	85.6	83.4	169.0
		% within Accommodation Type	32.5%	81.6%	56.7%
	Agree	Count	58	0	58
		Expected Count	29.4	28.6	58.0
		% within Accommodation Type	38.4%	0.0%	19.5%
	Strongly Agree	Count	1	0	1
		Expected Count	.5	.5	1.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.7%	0.0%	0.3%
Total	Count	151	147	298	
	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0	
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	

Figure 38: Feelings towards customer: Expectation

The above graph shows the guests expectation and perceptions on the SERVQUAL factor of employees' soft feelings towards customers.

Perception:

The primary data from the questionnaire survey has revealed that most of the accommodation guests could not decide on finding any soft feelings from the accommodation employees. Neither agree nor disagree count is almost 50 % for the hotel guest while this proportion is 65% for the shared accommodation. Around 25% of the guest from both of the accommodation types disagreed that they saw any kind of soft feelings towards them during their stay in the accommodation. 26% of the shared accommodation guest has agreed to find soft feelings towards them when they were staying in the accommodation. Almost 8% of the hotel guest have disagreed to find the factor exists in the hotel, while this proportion remained nil for the shared accommodation guest.

Table 48: Feelings towards customer: Perception

P E5 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation
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Feelings towards customer			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P E5	Strongly Disagree	Count	12	0	12
		Expected Count	6.1	5.9	12.0
		% within Accommodation Type	7.9%	0.0%	4.0%
	Disagree	Count	37	13	50
		Expected Count	25.3	24.7	50.0
		% within Accommodation Type	24.5%	8.8%	16.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	76	95	171
		Expected Count	86.6	84.4	171.0
		% within Accommodation Type	50.3%	64.6%	57.4%
	Agree	Count	10	39	49
		Expected Count	24.8	24.2	49.0
		% within Accommodation Type	6.6%	26.5%	16.4%
	Strongly Agree	Count	16	0	16
		Expected Count	8.1	7.9	16.0

		% within Accommodation Type	10.6%	0.0%	5.4%
Total	Count		151	147	298
	Expected Count		151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type		100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 39: Feelings towards customer; Perception

The above graph shows the accommodation guest perception of the accommodation employee's soft feelings towards them during their stay in lodging.

5.3.5 Dimension five: RESPONSIVENESS:

Flexibility to respond to customer queries:

Expectation:

The table below displays the hotels and shared accommodation guests expectations on the flexibility of the accommodation employees. As per the table, it can be seen that the response

from the hotel guest’s expectation on the question ‘flexibility to response customer queries’, around 20% strongly agreed, 68% agreed, and 10.6% guests neither agreed nor disagreed. The remaining 1.3% of guests disagreed that they expect the employees to be flexible in responding to customer queries. A similar result has also been found from the shared accommodation guest who has strongly agreed that they expect employees to be flexible to respond to customer’s queries. The highest proportion of the shared accommodation guests agreed on expecting flexibility towards responding to customers queries. 29.6% of the guests have responded that they do neither agree nor disagree while the remaining small proportion disagreed to expect the employee's flexibility on customer’s query

The table below displays the hotels and shared accommodation guests’ expectations on the flexibility of the accommodation employees. As per the table, it can be seen that the response from the hotel guest’s expectation on the question ‘flexibility to response customer queries’, around 20% strongly agreed, 68% agreed, and 10.6% guests neither agreed nor disagreed. The remaining 1.3% of guests disagreed that they expect the employees to be flexible in responding to customer queries. A similar result has also been found from the shared accommodation guest who has strongly agreed that they expect employees to be flexible to respond to customer’s queries. The highest proportion of the shared accommodation guests agreed on expecting flexibility towards responding to customer’s queries. 29.6% of the guests have responded that they do neither agree nor disagree while the remaining small proportion disagreed to expect the employees' flexibility on customer’s queries.

Table 49: Flexibility to respond to customer queries: Expectation

E RS1 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation						
Flexibility to respond to customer queries:			Accommodation Type		Total	
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation		
E RS1	Disagree	Count	2	6	8	
		Expected Count	4.1	3.9	8.0	

		% within Accommodation Type	1.3%	4.1%	2.7%
Neither agree nor disagree		Count	16	44	60
		Expected Count	30.4	29.6	60.0
		% within Accommodation Type	10.6%	29.9%	20.1%
Agree		Count	103	88	191
		Expected Count	96.8	94.2	191.0
		% within Accommodation Type	68.2%	59.9%	64.1%
Strongly Agree		Count	30	8	38
		Expected Count	19.3	18.7	38.0
		% within Accommodation Type	19.9%	5.4%	12.8%
43		Count	0	1	1
		Expected Count	.5	.5	1.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.0%	0.7%	0.3%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 40: Flexibility to respond to customer queries: Expectation

The chart above reflects the responses of the accommodation guest on the flexibility of the employees to respond to customers queries.

Perception:

Primary data from the questionnaire survey on the guest perception on the factor flexibility to respond customers query, most of both hotel and shared accommodation guest do not either agree or disagree that the found the employees to be flexible on responding customers queries. This proportion is 4% to 43% for both of the accommodation types. Guest’s perception on this factor as agreed 32.5% and 39.5% for the hotel and shared accommodation respectively. No guest has strongly agreed that they found the hotel employee to be flexible on responding to customers’ queries while 12% of the hotel guests have strongly agreed that they found the employees agreed flexible to responding customer’s queries. A very small proportion of the guests 0.7% and 2% respectively for the hotel and shared accommodation guests strongly disagreed that there was flexibility for the employees to respond to customers queries.

Table 50: Flexibility to response customer queries: Perception

P RS1 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation

Flexibility to respond to customer queries:			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P RS1	Strongly Disagree	Count	1	3	4
		Expected Count	2.0	2.0	4.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.7%	2.0%	1.3%
	Disagree	Count	21	23	44
		Expected Count	22.3	21.7	44.0
		% within Accommodation Type	13.9%	15.6%	14.8%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	62	63	125
		Expected Count	63.3	61.7	125.0
		% within Accommodation Type	41.1%	42.9%	41.9%
	Agree	Count	49	58	107
		Expected Count	54.2	52.8	107.0
		% within Accommodation Type	32.5%	39.5%	35.9%
	Strongly Agree	Count	18	0	18
		Expected Count	9.1	8.9	18.0

		% within Accommodation Type	11.9%	0.0%	6.0%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

The bar chart below represents the flexibility of the employees to respond to customer queries for both of the accommodation types.

Figure 41: Flexibility to respond to customer queries: Perception

Employee’s approach to help:

Expectation:

To explore the gap in the service quality factors customers were also asked about their expectations and perception of the accommodation employees’ willingness to assist the customers. It has been found from the primary response that guest expectation is moderately

high to be assisted by the employees in the accommodations they stay in. 52% of the hotel guests and 71% of the shared accommodation guests agreed to get help from the hotel and shared accommodation respectively. 24% and 14% of guests of the hotel and shared accommodation guests respectively have strongly agreed on that particular LSQUAL factor. Neither agree nor disagree proportion is 20.5% for the hotels and 5% for the shared accommodation guests. 3.3% of hotel guests and 10% shared accommodation guests in this survey disagreed that they expect any kind of assistance from the accommodation employees. The strongly disagreed count for this factor was nil in this survey.

Table 51: Employee’s approach to help: Expectation

E RS2 * Accommodation Type Cross tabulation					
Employee’s approach to help			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E RS2	Disagree	Count	5	15	20
		Expected Count	10.1	9.9	20.0
		% within Accommodation Type	3.3%	10.2%	6.7%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	31	7	38
		Expected Count	19.3	18.7	38.0
		% within Accommodation Type	20.5%	4.8%	12.8%
	Agree	Count	79	104	183
		Expected Count	92.7	90.3	183.0

		% within Accommodation Type	52.3%	70.7%	61.4%
	Strongly Agree	Count	36	21	57
		Expected Count	28.9	28.1	57.0
		% within Accommodation Type	23.8%	14.3%	19.1%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

The bar graph below represents the proportion of the accommodation guest's primary response on expectation and perception for the factor of getting assistance from the hotel and shared accommodation.

Figure 42: Employee's approach to help: Perception:

Perception:

The primary data has revealed that most of the hotel guests, which is 70%, have no specific view on their perception to receive any type of assistance from the hotel employees. 15% of the hotel guests have agreed that hotel employees are willing to help them during their stay. 11% of hotel guests strongly disagreed to have found assistance from the hotel employees. The experience from the shared accommodation guests is 53 % as agreed, while 40% could not decide whether they received any assistance or not from the shared accommodation guests. 4.8% of shared accommodation guests have strongly disagreed on that particular factor.

Table 52: Employee's approach to help: Perception

P RS2 * Accommodation Type Cross tabulation			
Employee's approach to help	Accommodation Type		Total
	Hotel	Shared Accommodation	

P RS2	Strongly Disagree	Count	2	3	5
		Expected Count	2.5	2.5	5.0
		% within Accommodation Type	1.3%	2.0%	1.7%
	Disagree	Count	17	7	24
		Expected Count	12.2	11.8	24.0
		% within Accommodation Type	11.3%	4.8%	8.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	106	59	165
		Expected Count	83.6	81.4	165.0
		% within Accommodation Type	70.2%	40.1%	55.4%
	Agree	Count	23	78	101
		Expected Count	51.2	49.8	101.0
		% within Accommodation Type	15.2%	53.1%	33.9%
	Strongly Agree	Count	3	0	3
		Expected Count	1.5	1.5	3.0
		% within Accommodation Type	2.0%	0.0%	1.0%
Total	Count	151	147	298	
	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0	

	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
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Figure 43: Employee's approach to help: Perception

The above bar chart shows the guest perception of the willingness of the accommodation employees to assist the hotel guest.

Supportive management towards employees:

Expectation:

The table below displays the hotels and shared accommodation guests' expectations on the management support towards accommodation employees. As per the table, it can be seen that the response from the hotel guest's expectation on the question 'management support towards employees', around 13% strongly agreed, 25% agreed, and 59% guests neither agreed nor disagreed. The remaining 3.3% of guests disagreed that they expect the employees to receive appropriate support from the management to serve the customer at a high standard. The highest proportion of the shared accommodation guests neither agreed nor disagreed on their expectation to find supportive management towards employees. 41% of the guests have

responded that they agree to expect supportive management while the remaining 6.8% of participants strongly disagreed to expect the employees receive enough support from the accommodation management.

Table 53: Supportive management towards employee: Expectation

E RS3 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Supportive management towards employee			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E RS3	Disagree	Count	5	10	15
		Expected Count	7.6	7.4	15.0
		% within Accommodation Type	3.3%	6.8%	5.0%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	89	75	164
		Expected Count	83.1	80.9	164.0
		% within Accommodation Type	58.9%	51.0%	55.0%
	Agree	Count	37	60	97
		Expected Count	49.2	47.8	97.0
		% within Accommodation Type	24.5%	40.8%	32.6%
	Strongly Agree	Count	20	2	22
		Expected Count	11.1	10.9	22.0

		% within Accommodation Type	13.2%	1.4%	7.4%
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Figure 44: Supportive management towards employee: Expectation

The above bar chart shows the guest expectation and perception towards the LSQUAL factor of the supportive management towards accommodation employees.

Perception:

The table below displays the hotels and shared accommodation guests’ perception of the management support towards accommodation employees. As per the table, it can be seen that the response from the hotel guest’s perception on the question ‘management support towards employees’, around 15% agreed that they found some sort of support the employees are receiving from both types of accommodation. Most of the shared accommodation guest’s (89%) response count was neither agreed nor disagreed to find that employees were receiving appropriate support from the hotel management, while this proportion for the hotel guest is 51%. Among the hotel guests, 34% disagreed that they found any management support that employees are receiving from the hoteliers.

Table 54: Supportive management towards employee: Perception

P RS3 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Supportive management towards employee			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P RS3	Strongly Disagree	Count	1	2	3
		Expected Count	1.5	1.5	3.0
		% within Accommodation Type	0.7%	1.4%	1.0%
	Disagree	Count	51	6	57
		Expected Count	28.9	28.1	57.0
		% within Accommodation Type	33.8%	4.1%	19.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	77	131	208
		Expected Count	105.4	102.6	208.0
		% within Accommodation Type	51.0%	89.1%	69.8%
	Agree	Count	22	8	30
		Expected Count	15.2	14.8	30.0
		% within Accommodation Type	14.6%	5.4%	10.1%

Total	Count	151	147	298
	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 45: Supportive management towards employee: Perception

Employee performance to complete any service:

Expectation:

The final question of the LSQUAL scale was about the employee performance to complete the service appropriately. From the questionnaire survey, it was found that most of the hotel and shared accommodation guests expect that accommodation employees should be efficient enough to complete the task effectively. Almost all of the hotel guests expected the employees to be capable of performing their tasks appropriately. The count as agreeing was 48.3% and strongly agree was 49.37%. Similarly, the proportion for the shared

accommodation guest expectation count was 65% as agree and 27.2% as strongly agree towards employee efficiency.

Table 55: Employee performance to complete any service: Expectation

E RS4 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation					
Employee performance to complete any service			Accommodation Type		Total
			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
E RS4	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	3	12	15
		Expected Count	7.6	7.4	15.0
		% within Accommodation Type	2.0%	8.2%	5.0%
	Agree	Count	73	95	168
		Expected Count	85.1	82.9	168.0
		% within Accommodation Type	48.3%	64.6%	56.4%
	Strongly Agree	Count	75	40	115
		Expected Count	58.3	56.7	115.0
		% within Accommodation Type	49.7%	27.2%	38.6%
Total		Count	151	147	298
		Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
		% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Figure 46: Employee performance to complete any service: Expectation

The bar chart above shows the proportion of the guests' expectations on the employee performance to serve the accommodation guest.

Perception:

The questionnaire survey has revealed a mixed experience that the accommodation has found the accommodation employee's service. Almost half of the accommodation guests could not decide and remained neutral to answer the question about employee's performance. 36% of the hotel guest agreed and 32% of the shared accommodation guest agreed that they found the accommodation employees were efficient enough to serve the purpose. 7.3% of the hotel guest strongly agreed and 2.7% of the shared accommodation guests strongly agreed that the employees performed very well during their stay in the accommodation. Just below 5% of the guest from both accommodation types strongly disagreed and responded as the employees were inefficient to perform the specific task.

Table 56: Employee performance to complete any service: Perception

P RS4 * Accommodation Type Crosstabulation		
Employee performance to complete any service:	Accommodation Type	Total

			Hotel	Shared Accommodation	
P RS4	Strongly Disagree	Count	7	5	12
		Expected Count	6.1	5.9	12.0
		% within Accommodation Type	4.6%	3.4%	4.0%
	Disagree	Count	5	19	24
		Expected Count	12.2	11.8	24.0
		% within Accommodation Type	3.3%	12.9%	8.1%
	Neither agree nor disagree	Count	74	72	146
		Expected Count	74.0	72.0	146.0
		% within Accommodation Type	49.0%	49.0%	49.0%
	Agree	Count	54	47	101
		Expected Count	51.2	49.8	101.0
		% within Accommodation Type	35.8%	32.0%	33.9%
	Strongly Agree	Count	11	4	15
		Expected Count	7.6	7.4	15.0
		% within Accommodation Type	7.3%	2.7%	5.0%

Total	Count	151	147	298
	Expected Count	151.0	147.0	298.0
	% within Accommodation Type	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

The bar chart below shows the guest evaluation of the accommodation employee performance.

Figure 47: Employee performance to complete any service: Perception

4.4 Research findings on service quality gap:

The following section discusses the customer gap between the hotel and shared accommodation.

4.4.1 Gap on tangibility dimension:

Presence of modern equipment:

The table below displays the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) on the presence of modern equipment for the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation means for the presence of modern equipment is 4.61 and the guest's perception mean for the presence of modern equipment stands as 3.30 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 1.31.

The expectation mean on the presence of modern equipment for the shared accommodation is 4.66, and the perception means for the presence of modern equipment stands as 3.52. Consequently, the customer gap for the presence of modern equipment for the shared accommodation is 1.14.

Table 57: Gap comparison-Presence of modern equipment

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Presence of modern equipment	4.61	3.30	1.31	4.66	3.52	1.14

The attractiveness of the physical features:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) on the attractiveness of the physical features for the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for the attractiveness of the physical features is 4.30 and the guest's perception mean for the attractiveness of the physical features stands as 3.08 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as - 1.22.

The expectation mean for the attractiveness of the physical features for the shared accommodation is 4.43, and the perception means for the attractiveness of the physical features stands as 3.31. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 1.12.

Table 58: Gap Comparison-The attractiveness of the physical features

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
The attractiveness of the physical features	4.30	3.08	-1.22	4.43	3.31	-1.12

Presence of safety and security equipment:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) on the presence of safety and security equipment for the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation means for the presence of safety and security equipment is 4.57 and the guest's perception mean for the presence of safety and security equipment stands as 3.75 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.81.

Thy expectation means for the presence of safety and security equipment of the shared accommodation is 4.7, and the mean of the perception for the presence of safety and security equipment stands as 3.87. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.83.

Table 59: Gap Comparison-Presence of safety and security equipment

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Presence of safety and security equipment	4.57	3.75	-0.81	4.7	3.87	0.83

Employee's appearance with professional attire:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) on employee's appearance with professional attire of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for employee's appearance with professional attire is 3.73 and the guest's perception mean for employee's appearance with professional attire stands as 3.40 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.33.

Thy expectation mean for employee's appearance with professional attire of the shared accommodation is 3.61, and the perception average for employee's appearance with professional attire stands as 3.43. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.18.

Table 60: Gap Comparison: Employee's appearance with professional attire

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Employee's appearance with professional attire.	3.73	3.40	-0.33	3.61	3.43	-0.18

4.1.2 Gap on reliability dimension:

Commitment completion effectiveness:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) on commitment completion effectiveness for the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for commitment completion

effectiveness is 4.03 and the guest's perception mean on commitment completion effectiveness stands as 3.50 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.53.

Thy expectation mean on commitment completion effectiveness for the shared accommodation is 4.25, and the perception mean on commitment completion effectiveness stands as 3.54. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.71.

Table 61: Gap Comparison-Commitment completion effectiveness

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Commitment completion effectiveness	4.03	3.50	-0.53	4.25	3.54	-0.71

Accurate bookkeeping:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for accurate bookkeeping for the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for accurate bookkeeping is 4.20 and the guest's perception mean stands as 3.52 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.68.

Thy expectation mean for accurate bookkeeping of the shared accommodation is 3.63, and the perception mean for accurate bookkeeping stands as 3.53. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.10.

Table 62: Gap Comparison-Accurate bookkeeping

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation	Perception	Gap (P-E)	Expectation	Perception	Gap

	Mean	Mean		Mean	Mean	(P-E)
Accurate bookkeeping	4.20	3.52	-0.68	3.63	3.53	-0.10

Working condition of the equipment:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for the working condition of the equipment of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for working condition of the equipment is 4.65 and the guest's perception mean for working condition of the equipment stands as 3.84 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.81.

Thy expectation mean for the working condition of the equipment of the shared accommodation is 4.51, and the perception mean for the working condition of the equipment stands as 3.46. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 1.05.

Table 63: Gap comparison-Working condition of the equipment:

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Working condition of the equipment	4.65	3.84	-0.81	4.51	3.46	-1.05

Secured payment service:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for the Secured payment service of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for secured payment service is 4.40 and the guest's

perception mean stands as 3.5 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as -0.85.

Thy expectation mean for the Secured payment service of the shared accommodation is 4.59, and the perception means for secured payment service stands as 3.58. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 1.01.

Table 64: Gap Comparison-Secured payment service

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Secured payment service	4.40	3.55	0.85	4.59	3.58	-1.01

Safe and secure environment:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for the safe and secure environment of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for a safe and secure environment is 4.73 and the guest's perception mean for a safe and secure environment stands as 3.95 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.77.

Thy expectation mean for a safe and secure environment for the shared accommodation is 4.72, and the perception mean stands as 3.47. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 1.25.

Table 65: Gap Comparison-Safe and secure environment

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Safe and secure	4.73	3.95	-0.77	4.72	3.47	-1.25

environment						
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4.4.3 Gap on reliability dimension:

Appropriate cleanliness:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for the Appropriate cleanliness of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for appropriate cleanliness is 4.50 and the guest's perception mean for appropriate cleanliness stands as 3.56 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.94.

Thy expectation mean for appropriate cleanliness of the shared accommodation is 4.63, and the perception mean for appropriate cleanliness stands as 3.38. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 1.26.

Table 66: Gap comparison-Appropriate cleanliness

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Appropriate cleanliness	4.50	3.56	-0.94	4.63	3.38	-1.26

Comfortable bed:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for the Comfortable bed of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for a comfortable bed is 4.70 and the guest's perception mean for a comfortable bed stands as 3.55 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 1.15.

Thy expectation mean for the comfortable bed of the shared accommodation is 4.66, and the perception mean for a comfortable bed stands as 3.39. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 1.27.

Table 67: Gap Comparison-Comfortable bed:

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Comfortable bed	4.70	3.55	-1.15	4.66	3.39	-1.27

The efficiency of the physical features as per the service offered:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for the efficiency of the physical features of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for the efficiency of the physical features is 4.56 and the guest's perception mean stands for the efficiency of the physical features as 3.45 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 1.11.

Thy expectation mean for the efficiency of the physical features of the shared accommodation is 4.36, and the perception mean stands as 3.33. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 1.03.

Table 68: Gap comparison-The efficiency of the physical features as per the service offered:

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
The efficiency of the physical features as per service offered.	4.56	3.45	-1.11	4.36	3.33	-1.03

Convenient operating hours:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for the Convenient operating hours of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean is 4.56 and the guest's perception mean for Convenient operating hours stands as 3.45 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 1.11.

Thy expectation mean for Convenient operating hours of the shared accommodation is 4.36, and the perception mean stands as 3.33. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 1.03.

Table 69: Gap Comparison-Convenient operating hours

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Convenient operating hours	4.56	3.45	-1.11	4.36	3.33	-1.03

4.4.4 Gap on empathy dimension:

Personalised attention:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for personalised attention for the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for personalised attention is 3.45 and the guest's perception mean for personalised attention stands as 2.74 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.71.

Thy expectation mean for personalised attention for the shared accommodation is 3.02, and the perception mean stands as 2.94. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.08.

Table 70: Personalised attention: Gap Comparison

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Personalised attention	3.45	2.74	-0.71	3.02	2.94	-0.08

Employee attitude:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for employee attitude of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for employee attitude is 4.32 and the guest's perception mean for employee attitude stands as 2.72 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.6.

Thy expectation mean for employee attitude of the shared accommodation is 3.64, and the perception mean for employee attitude stands as 2.72. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.42.

Table 71: Gap Comparison-Employee attitude

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Employee attitude	4.32	2.72	-0.6	3.64	3.23	-0.42

Reliability of the employees:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for the reliability of the employees of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean v is 4.23 and the guest's perception mean

for reliability of the employees stands as 3.45 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.78. Thy expectation mean for reliability of the employees for the shared accommodation is 4.23, and the perception mean for reliability of the employees. stands as 3.46. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.77

Table 72: Gap Comparison-Reliability of the employees:

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation	Perception	Gap (P-E)	Expectation	Perception	Gap (P-E)
	Mean	Mean		Mean	Mean	
Reliability of the employees	4.23	3.45	-0.78	4.23	3.46	-0.77

Individual need recognition:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for individual need recognition of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for individual need recognition is 3.37 and the guest's perception mean for individual need recognition stands as 2.72 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.65

Thy expectation mean for individual need recognition of the shared accommodation is 2.97, and the perception mean for individual need recognition stands as 2.89. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.08.

Table 73: Gap comparison-Individual need recognition

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation	Perception	Gap (P-E)	Expectation	Perception	Gap (P-E)
	Mean	Mean		Mean	Mean	

Individual need recognition	3.37	2.72	-0.65	2.97	2.89	-0.08
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Feelings towards customers:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for Feelings towards the customer of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean is 3.11 and the guest's perception mean feelings towards customer stands as 2.87 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.24.

Thy expectation mean for feelings towards the customer of the shared accommodation is 2.82, and the perception mean stands as 3.14. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.33.

Table 74: Gap Comparison-Feelings towards customer:

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Feelings towards customer	3.11	2.87	-0.24	2.82	3.14	-0.33

4.4.5 Gap on responsiveness dimension:

Flexibility to respond to customer queries:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for flexibility to respond to customer queries of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the

questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean flexibility to respond to the customer is 4.07 and the guest's perception mean flexibility to respond to customers stands as 3.41 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.66.

Thy expectation mean flexibility to respond to the customer of the shared accommodation is 4.00, and the perception mean stands as 3.18. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.82.

Table 75: Gap Comparison-Flexibility to respond to customer queries:

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Flexibility to respond to customer queries	4.07	3.41	-0.66	4.00	3.18	-0.82

Employee's approach to help:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for employees' approach to the help of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean is 3.97 and the guest's perception mean employee's approach to helping stands as 3.05 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.91.

Thy expectation mean of employee's approach to help of the shared accommodation is 3.90, and the perception mean employee's approach to help stands as 3.42. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.48.

Table 76: Gap comparison: Employee's approach to help

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)

						E)
Employee's approach to help	3.97	3.05	-0.91	3.90	3.42	-0.48

Supportive management towards employees:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for supportive management towards an employee of the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for supportive management towards an employee is 3.48 and the guest's perception mean for supportive management towards employee stands as 2.79 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 0.68.

Thy expectation mean for supportive management towards the employee for the shared accommodation is 3.38, and the perception mean for supportive management towards employee stands as 2.98. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 0.40.

Table 77: Gap Comparison-Supportive management towards employee

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Supportive management towards employee	3.48	2.79	-0.68	3.38	2.98	0.40

Employee performance to complete for any service:

The table below shows the customer gap (Perception - Expectation) for employee performance to compete for any service for the hotel and shared accommodation. As per the findings from the questionnaire survey, the guests' expectation mean for employee

performance to compete any service is 4.48 and the guest's perception mean for employee performance to compete any service stands as 3.38 for the hotel accommodation. Therefore, the customer gap is calculated as 1.10.

Thy expectation mean for employee performance to compete for any service of the shared accommodation is 4.18, and the perception mean stands as 3.15. Consequently, the customer gap for the shared accommodation is 1.03.

Table 78: Gap Comparison-Employee performance to compete for any service

Factor	Hotel			Shared accommodation		
	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)	Expectation Mean	Perception Mean	Gap (P-E)
Employee performance to compete for any service	4.48	3.38	-1.10	4.18	3.15	-1.03

4.5 Results of the hypothesis test:

The following section discusses the testing of the hypothesis for this study and presents the results of the hypothesis test.

Hypothesis 1- Test:

- H1-1: There exists a variation in the service quality gap between hotels and shared accommodation.
- H1-0: There is no variation in the service quality gap between hotels and shared accommodation.

One-way ANOVA:

To test the hypothesis, a one-way ANOVA was used. to find whether there is a service quality gap between the hotels and shared accommodation. The findings of the one-way Anova test are described in the next section.

Means:*Table 79: Anova-Case Processing Summary*

Case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Included		Excluded		Total	
	N	Per cent	N	Per cent	N	Per cent
GAP * Accommodation Type	296	99.3%	2	0.7%	298	100.0%

Included:

N is the total number of observation and their per cent is also given.

Excluded:

2 numbers of observations are excluded in the data sets.

Table 80: Anova- mean comparison

Report			
GAP			
Accommodation Type	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Hotel	.7793	151	.35479
Shared Accommodation	.6655	145	.48389
Total	.7236	296	.42609

N – The number of valid observations for the variable is shown below. So, in this analysis total number of valid observations is 151 for the hotel and 145 for the shared accommodation.

Mean – The arithmetic mean of all the observations is this. It is the most commonly used central tendency measure. It's frequently referred to as the average. Extremely high or tiny numbers have a big impact on the mean. In this analysis mean of all observations are .78 for the hotels and 0.67 for the shared accommodation.

Std. – The square root of the variance is the standard deviation. It calculates the spread of a collection of data. The higher the standard deviation, the more evenly distributed the data is. So, our STD value is 0.355 and 0.484 for the hotel and shared accommodation respectively.

Table 81: Anova- Hypothesis 1 test result

ANOVA					
GAP					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.958	1	.958	5.357	.021
Within Groups	52.599	294	.179		
Total	53.558	295			

The ANOVA test provides the result of whether there exists a significant difference between the means of two or more levels of a variable. The value of F is found in the Between Groups row and whether this reaches a significant level. The result was found to be significant in this survey because the p-value is (0.021) less than the F value (5.35).

As the result from the Anova table suggest that the p-value is less that we reject the null hypothesis since the significance threshold is 0.05. and accept the alternative hypothesis, that is there exist a variation in service quality gap between hotels and shared accommodation.

Hypothesis 2- test:

- H2-1: There is a variation in the guest's expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation.
- H2-0: There exists no variation in the guest's expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation.

To test the hypothesis to find whether there is a variation in the guest expectation towards the hotels and shared accommodation, a one-way Anova was conducted. The outcomes of the one-way Anova test are described in the next section.

Table 82: Anova- Hypothesis 2 case processing summary

Case Processing Summary						
	Cases					
	Included		Excluded		Total	
	N	Per cent	N	Per cent	N	Per cent
EXPECTATION * Accommodation Type	298	100.0 %	0	0.0%	298	100.0%

Table 83: Anova-Hypothesis 2 -mean comparison

Report			
EXPECTATION			
Accommodation Type	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Hotel	4.1755	151	.24433
Shared Accommodation	4.0405	147	.21787

Total	4.1089	298	.24095
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N – The number of valid observations for the variable is shown below. So, in this analysis total number of valid observations is 151 for the hotel and 147 for the shared accommodation.

Mean – The arithmetic mean of all the observations is this. It is the most commonly used central tendency measure. It's frequently referred to as the average. In our analysis mean of all observations for the expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation is 4.18 and 4.04 respectively.

Std. – Std. – The square root of the variance is the standard deviation. It calculates the spread of a collection of data. The higher the standard deviation, the more evenly distributed the data is. So, our STD value is 0.244 and 0.218 for the hotel and shared accommodation respectively.

Table 84: Anova- Hypothesis 2 test result

ANOVA Table				
			Sum of Squares	df
EXPECTATION * Accommodation Type	Between Groups	(Combined)	1.357	1
	Within Groups		15.885	296
	Total		17.242	297

Table 85: Anova- Hypothesis 2 test result

ANOVA Table			
	Mean	F	Sig.

			Square		
EXPECTATION * Accommodation Type	Between Groups	(Combine d)	1.357	25.292	.000
	Within Groups		.054		
	Total				

The ANOVA test provides the result of whether there exists a significant difference between the means of two or more levels of a variable. The value of F is found in the Between Groups rows and whether this reaches a significant level. In this research, the result was found to be significant because the p-value is (0.00) less than the F value (25.29).

As the result from the Anova table, the p-value (.000) is less, we reject the null hypothesis since the significance threshold is 0.05. and accept the alternative hypothesis, that is there exist a variation in guest expectation between hotels and shared accommodation.

Hypothesis 3- Test:

- H3-0: There is a variation in the guest's perception of the hotel and shared accommodation.
- H3-1: There exists no variation in the guest's perception towards the hotels and shared accommodation.

One-way Anova:

To test the hypothesis to find whether there is a gap in the guests' perception of service quality towards the hotels and shared accommodation, a one-way Anova was conducted. The outcomes of the one-way Anova test results are described in the next section.

Table 86: Anova- Hypothesis 3 test result

ANOVA					
PERCEPTION					
	Sum of	df	Mean	F	Sig.

	Squares		Square		
Between Groups	.037	1	.037	.164	.686
Within Groups	67.086	294	.228		
Total	67.124	295			

Table 87: Anova- Hypothesis 3- Mean comparison

Report			
PERCEPTION			
Accommodation Type	Mean	N	Std. Deviation
Hotel	3.3961	151	.46540
Shared Accommodation	3.3737	145	.49016
Total	3.3851	296	.47701

N – The number of valid observations for the variable is shown below So, in this analysis total number of valid observations is 151 for the hotel and 145 for the shared accommodation.

Mean – The arithmetic mean of all the observations is this. It is the most commonly used central tendency measure. It's frequently referred to as the average. In this analysis mean of all observations are 3.4 for the hotels and 3.37 for the shred accommodation.

Std. – The square root of the variance is the standard deviation. It calculates the spread of a collection of data. The higher the standard deviation, the more evenly distributed the data is. So, our STD value is 0.465 and 0.490 for the hotel and shared accommodation respectively.

N – So, in this analysis total number of valid observations is 151 for the hotel and 147 for the shared accommodation.

Mean – In our analysis mean of all observations for the expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation is 4.18 and 4.04 respectively.

Std. – Std. –. So, our STD value is 0.244 and 0.218 for the hotel and shared accommodation respectively.

Table 88: Anova- Hypothesis 3 test result

ANOVA Table					
			Mean Square	F	Sig.
PERCEPTION * Accommodation Type	Between Groups	(Combine d)	.037	.164	.686
	Within Groups		.228		
	Total				

The ANOVA test provides the result of the Anova test whether there is a considerable variation in means between two or more levels of a variable. The value of F is found in the Between Groups rows. and whether this reaches a significant level. In our findings, the p-value is (0.686) and the F value (0.164).

As a result of the Anova table, the p-value (0.686) is more than the significance level of 0.05; therefore, we reject the alternative hypothesis and accept the null hypothesis. There is no variation in the guest’s perception towards the hotels and shared accommodation.

Hypothesis 4- Test:

- H4-1 Choice of future accommodation significantly depends on the satisfaction level
- H4-0: Choice of future accommodation does not depend on satisfaction level.

Table 89: Test of hypothesis 4 - Spearman's rho

Correlations: Satisfaction level and Likelihood to recommend				
			Satisfaction	LTR
Spearman's rho	Satisfaction	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.921**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.000
		N	298	298
	LTR	Correlation Coefficient	.921**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	298	298

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.001 level (2-tailed).

To assess the link between the two, a Spearman's rank-order correlation was used for 298 respondents' satisfaction levels and likelihood to recommend for future stays. So, in this case, the results show that there exists a strong positive correlation of .921 between "satisfaction level " and "likelihood to recommend" and that this relationship was statistically significant at the .000 level. The p-value of 0.00 is less than alpha level 0.05. The null hypothesis is thereby rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. From this Spearman rank correlation test, it can be concluded that recommendation for the accommodation significantly depends on the satisfaction level.

Hypothesis 5- Test:

- H5-1- There exist a negative correlation between the gap of the service quality factors and the satisfaction level.

- H5-0: There exists no correlation between the gap of the service quality factors and the satisfaction level.

Table 90: Test of hypothesis 5 - Spearman's rho

Correlations: Service quality gap and satisfaction level				
			GAP	Satisfaction
Spearman's rho	GAP	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.850**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	296	296
	Satisfaction	Correlation Coefficient	-.850**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	296	298

To assess the link between the two, a Spearman's rank-order correlation was used for the 298 respondent's satisfaction level and the gap of the customers' expectation and perception level. So, in this case, the results show that there exists a negative correlation of $-.850$ between "satisfaction level " and the gap of the service quality factors. The result also shows that this relationship was statistically significant at the $.00$ level. The p-value of 0.00 is less than alpha level 0.05 . The null hypothesis is thereby rejected, and the alternative hypothesis is proven to be correct. From this Spearman's rank correlation test, it can be concluded that there exists a negative correlation between the gap of the service quality factors and the satisfaction level.

There was a strong negative correlation between satisfaction level and accommodation, which was statistically significant ($r = -0.850$, $p = .000$). The p-value is less than the alpha level. Therefore, the null hypothesis cannot be accepted, and the alternative hypothesis is

accepted. That is there exists a negative correlation between the gap of the service quality factors and the satisfaction level.

Conclusion:

To analyse the service quality gap between the hotel and shared accommodation, the primary data revealed there exist discrepancy in guest's expectation and perception for both of the traditional hotels and shared accommodations. According to the findings of all of the demographic groups studied, there has been a significant shift in the travelling patterns by guests staying in hotels or shared apartments in central London. The accommodation users overall expectation is comparatively higher than the accommodation users perception.

The results also found that there exist a variation in service quality between the traditional hotel and the shared accommodation. Accommodation users expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation also varies in different dimensions, although the results found that the perception of the accommodation guest's do not differ towards the two type of the accommodation.

As per the test of Spearman's rank correlation test for assessing the relation between the satisfaction level and choice of future accommodation, it was found that choice of the future accommodation significantly depend on the satisfaction level. The results of the statistical analysis also established that there exist a strong negative corelation between the gap of the service quality gap and the satisfaction level.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION ON RESEARCH FINDINGS

5.1 Introduction:

This chapter discusses the empirical findings and relate the discussion in the literature review by aligning with the research objectives and research questions sequentially. According to the research objectives the discussion continues to the empirical findings on the service quality gap, customers expectation and perception, satisfaction level and recommendation for the future visits in sequential and links up the findings on the literature review.

5.2 Service quality gap:

This study has measured the gap on the service quality factors between the conventional hotels and shared accommodation in central London. Previous studies, Akbaba (2006); Petrick, (2014); Tsang and Qu (2000); Priporas et al (20017); Ladhari (2009) have measured the gap on the service quality factors either in the hotel sector or shared accommodation sector in different countries or cities like Turkey, China, Australia, Mauritius, Crete, etc. Their study found that there exist gap between the customer's expectation and perception. Like the previous studies, this study has also found the gap between the customer's expectation and perception. One of the key objectives was to identify the extent of the service quality gap between the hotel and shared accommodation. To figure out the gap between the hotel and shared accommodation the following hypothesis were tested

- H1-1: There exists a variation in the service quality gap between hotels and shared accommodation.
- H1-0: There is no variation in the service quality gap between hotels and shared accommodation.

The one-way Anova was conducted to test the hypothesis. The p value of the one-way Anova test was .021 which is way below the significance threshold of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis H1-0 was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis H1-1 was accepted. The results identified that there exists gaps on the service quality between the hotel and shared accommodation. The following section discusses on the gaps from the according to the service quality dimensions from the survey findings.

5.2.1 Tangibility gap:

The graph below illustrates the general gap between hotel and shared accommodation in terms of tangibility characteristics. The results has revealed that conventional hotels have slightly higher gap comparing to the shared accommodation for the for the modern equipment and its appearance factors. Both of the accommodation types have similar service quality performance in terms of the safety and security equipment.

According to the figure below, the customer gap for modern equipment, beautiful physical characteristics, and staff appearance is less for shared accommodation than for hotel accommodations. Both kinds of housing have a nearly identical gap in terms of the presence of safety and security devices.

Figure 48: Tangibility Gap

5.2.2 Reliability Gap:

According to the research result, there is a significant gap in the reliability factors for hotel and shared accommodation. Customer gaps for commitment fulfilment effectiveness, functioning state of equipment, secured payment services, and other factors are smaller for hotel accommodations as compared to shared accommodations, as seen in the graph. The findings also revealed a significant discrepancy in the accuracy of record-keeping between the hotel and shared accommodation.

Figure 49: Reliability Gap

5.2.3 Empathy Gap:

The Empathy factors for hotel and shared accommodation differ significantly. As seen in the graph, customer gaps for personalised attention, staff attitude, and individual need acknowledgement are lower for shared accommodations than for hotel accommodations. There was also a substantial difference in feeling toward consumers between the hotel and shared accommodation, according to the results. There exists a gap in the reliability of the employees for both of the accommodations, however, this gap is similar for both of the accommodation types.

Figure 50: Empathy Gap

5.2.4 Responsiveness Gap:

The research results have revealed that hotel employees are doing well in responding to customer queries, while shared accommodation employees' responsiveness was better on helping the customers and performing any other service requested by the customers.

Figure 51: Responsiveness Gap

5.2.5 Assurance gap:

The Assurance factors for hotel and shared accommodation also differs. As seen in the graph, customer gap for cleanliness, comfortable bed and operating hours are lower for hotel accommodations than for shared accommodations. The customer gap in the efficiency of the physical features is almost the same.

Figure 52: Assurance Gap

The overall service quality score and the mean aggregated score of the revised SERVQUAL factors gap, the findings suggest that accommodation guests are more unhappy with the overall services offered by the accommodation. Based on the total overall customer satisfaction and the mean aggregated modified SERVQUAL dimensions gap score, shared accommodation guests are more dissatisfied than hotel guests.

5.3 Expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation:

One of the key objectives of this study was to evaluate customer's expectation for both the traditional hotel and shared accommodation guests and in relation to the research question 2 identified in chapter 1 which is as follows

- Do the hotels and shared accommodation have the same level of the customer's expectation?

In the literature review chapter, it was pointed out that service quality is subjective in nature and difficult to quantify (Cheng, 2008), and it need to be measured from the viewpoint of

consumers (Zhang, 2013). Several other researcher also demonstrated that service quality can be measure through evaluating the gap between the customers expectation and perception. Previous researchers have also figured out that there exists gap between the service quality factors. This study has found that there exists a gap between guest’s expectation and perception. In addition to the service quality gap analysis, this study has also analysed whether hotel and shared accommodation guest possess same level of expectation or not.

The following table represents the gap that exists between the accommodation providers on guest expectation.

Table 91: Expectation gap between hotels and shared accommodation

Expectation			
Tangibility	Code	Hotel	Shared Accommodation
Presence of modern equipment	E T1	4.61	4.63
Attractiveness of the physical features	E T2	4.30	4.37
Presence of safety and security equipment	E T3	4.57	4.66
Employees appearance with professional attire.	E T4	3.73	3.61
Avg.		4.30	4.32
Reliability	Code	Hotel	Shared Accommodation
Commitment completion effectiveness	E RE1	4.03	4.18
Accurate bookkeeping	E RE2	4.20	3.60
Working condition of the equipment.	E RE3	4.65	4.51
Secured payment service	E RE4	4.40	4.58
Safe and secure environment	E RE5	4.73	4.73
Avg.		4.40	4.32
Assurance	Code	Hotel	Shared Accommodation

Appropriate cleanliness	E A1	4.50	4.63
Comfortable bed	E A2	4.70	4.69
Efficiency of the physical features as per service offered	E A3	4.56	4.35
Convenient operating hours	E A4	4.42	4.27
Avg.		4.54	4.48
Empathy			
	Code	Hotel	Shared Accommodation
Personalised attention	E E1	3.45	3.03
Employee attitude	E E2	4.32	3.60
Reliability of the employees	E E3	4.23	4.23
Individual need recognition	E E4	3.37	3.02
Feelings towards customer	E E5	3.11	2.82
Avg.		3.70	3.34
Responsiveness			
	Code	Hotel	Shared Accommodation
Flexibility to response customer queries	E RS1	4.07	3.94
Employees approach to help	E RS2	3.97	3.89
Support of management towards employee	E RS3	3.48	3.37
Employee performance to compete any service	E RS4	4.48	4.19
Avg.		4.00	3.85
Overall (Avg)		4.19	4.06

According to the table above it can be found that the accommodation guest's overall expectation towards the hotel is 4.19 while the average expectation towards the shared

accommodation 4.06. To find the overview, the following hypotheses were tested using the one-way Anova.

- H2-1- There is a variation in the guest’s expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation.
- H2-0: There exists no variation in the guest’s expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation.

The p value of the one-way Anova test was below the significance level of 0.5 and therefore the null hypothesis was rejected. In summary there exist a gap on guests’ expectation towards the hotel and shared accommodation.

5.4 Perception towards the hotel and shared accommodation:

The second objective of this study was to evaluate perception for both the traditional hotel and shared accommodation guests and in relation to the research question 3 identified in the chapter 1 which is as follows

- Do the hotels and shared accommodation have the same level of the customer’s perception?

The table below represents the accommodation guest’s perception towards the hotel and shared accommodation.

Table 92: Expectation gap between hotels and shared accommodation

Perception			
Tangibility	Code	Hotel	Shared Accommodation
Presence of modern equipment	E T1	3.30	3.54
Attractiveness of the physical features	E T2	3.08	3.31
Presence of safety and security equipment	E T3	3.75	3.84
Employees appearance with professional attire	E T4	3.40	3.46
Avg.		3.38	3.54

Reliability	Code	Hote 1	Shared Accommodation
Commitment completion effectiveness	E RE1	3.50	3.55
Accurate bookkeeping	E RE2	3.52	3.54
Working condition of the equipment.	E RE3	3.84	3.48
Secured payment service	E RE4	3.55	3.59
Safe and secure environment	E RE5	3.95	3.50
Avg.		3.67	3.53
Assurance	Code	Hote 1	Shared Accommodation
Appropriate cleanliness	E A1	3.56	3.39
Comfortable bed	E A2	3.55	3.44
Efficiency of the physical features as per service offered	E A3	3.45	3.33
Convenient operating hours	E A4	4.13	3.82
Avg.		3.67	3.49
Empathy	Code	Hote 1	Shared Accommodation
Personalised attention	E E1	2.74	2.94
Employee attitude	E E2	3.72	3.19
Reliability of the employees	E E3	3.45	3.48
Individual need recognition	E E4	2.72	2.90
Feelings towards customer	E E5	2.87	3.18
Avg.		3.10	3.14
Responsiveness	Code	Hote 1	Shared Accommodation

Flexibility to response customer queries	E RS1	3.41	3.20
Employees approach to help	E RS2	3.05	3.44
Support of management towards employee	E RS3	2.79	2.99
Employee performance to compete any service	E RS4	3.38	3.18
Avg.		3.16	3.20
Overall (Avg)		3.40	3.38

From the above table, the overall customer's perception towards the hotel is 3.4 and the perception towards the shared accommodation is 3.38. The following hypotheses were evaluated using the one-way Anova to answer the research question

- H3-1: There is a variation on the guest's perception towards the hotel and shared accommodation
- H3-0: There exists no variation in the guest's perception towards the hotels and shared accommodation

According to the one-way Anova test for the above hypothesis the significance level (p value) for the for the guest perception towards the hotel and shared accommodation was 0.686. As per the one-way Anova rules the alternative hypothesis need to be rejected and the null hypothesis should be accepted. As a result, the conclusion was drawn that accommodation customer's perception does not differ towards the hotel and shared accommodation.

5.5 Reliability of the LSQUAL model:

The third objective of the DBA research was to develop a framework for measuring service quality of lodging industry through identifying the industry specific factors and performing data collection method. The original SERVQUAL developed by Parasuraman et al. (1988) was the basis to develop the LSQUAL framework, however the dimensional factors were considered as per the lodging industry service quality factors through in-depth content analysis in the hotel and shared accommodation reservation portal like booking.com, TripAdvisor, Airbnb etc. (discussed in the literature review section). As suggested by

Bedradina (2019), Ladhari (2010) the service quality factors need to be determined as per the context of the service industry. Andreani, Winata and Halim (2018), O'Cas and Carlsson (2011) have also supported the amendment of the SERVQUAL framework as per the industry setting. Therefore, these proposals were considered as the basis of this DBA research and constructed the LSQUAL model for measuring the service quality gap in lodging industry through questionnaire survey. The questionnaire for collecting the primary data was developed on the basis of the factors of LSQUAL model using a five-point Likert scale. The reliability of the content was tested using the SPSS. Churchill (1979) pointed out that Cronbach Alpha coefficient need to be 0.80 or higher to consider the contents of a questionnaire suitable for scientific studies. De Vellis, (2012) has also supported this claim that anything above 0.80 indicates the reliability of the scale. In this DBA study the Cronbach Alpha coefficient of the questionnaire content was 0.84 indicating the consistency and the reliability of the scale.

5.6 Customer gap, satisfaction level and choice of future accommodation:

The discussion on the literature review established that service quality is complicated to measure and hard to manage. This claim was supported by Tontiset and Ittarat, (2014), Leisen Pollack (2008). Satisfaction level is determined through the extent of the perceived service quality. Satisfaction level can also be increased through providing higher quality service can be kept minimised through practicing higher customer service (Caruana, 2012). Similarly, recommendation for any accommodation highly depends on the satisfaction level. This DBA research has tested the hypothesis 4 and 5 formulated in the literature review section answered the following questions a

- How does the gap of the service quality factors influence the choice of future accommodation?
- Which factor do guests consider most for choosing accommodation?
- How does the customer gap influence the satisfaction level?

By finding the answers for the above questions the following objectives were met for this research.

- To establish the impact of the satisfaction level on future recommendation.
- To establish the correlation between the customer gap and satisfaction level.

A Spearman's rank-order correlation was performed to examine the association between the two for 298 respondents' overall satisfaction and likely to suggest future stays. So, in this situation, the findings reveal that "satisfaction level" and "probability to recommend" have a strong positive correlation of .921 and that this correlation is statistically significant at the .000 level. The 0.00 p-value is less than the 0.05 alpha thresholds. As a result, the null hypothesis is dismissed, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. Based on the results of the Spearman rank correlation test, it can be inferred that the degree of satisfaction has a substantial impact on the recommendation for the accommodation. As discussed in the literature review section regarding the satisfaction level and the future recommendation, Batt and Tong (2020) have also concluded satisfaction level indirectly plays a stronger role to the future revisit intention indirectly. The results of this study supports the claim of Yeo (2017) that a drop in the satisfaction level may lead the customers move their future expenditure in accommodation to alternative options. The findings also supports the claim of Mohsin and Lockyer (2010) the better satisfaction level optimistically results in the customer's recommendation for the future visits.

According to Lan (2017) as discussed in the literature review section that the gap that exist between the guests expectation and perception determines the level of satisfaction. This study has also found that there was a statistically significant negative correlation between satisfaction level and accommodation ($r = -0.850$, $p = .000$). The cronbach's alpha is smaller than the p-value. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected, whereas the alternative hypothesis is accepted. That is, there is a negative relationship between the service quality factor gap and the level of satisfaction. An increase in the gap of the service quality factors will decrease the satisfaction level.

5.7: Conclusion:

The empirical findings were discussed in this chapter, and the discussion in the literature review is linked to the study objectives and research questions in a sequential manner. According to the research goals, section 5.2 above addressed the service quality discrepancy between the hotels and shared accommodations, as well as responds to research question 1.

The section 5.3 answers the research question no. 2 by discussing the consumers' expectations of the hotel and shared accommodation. The section 5.4 unravels the research question no. 3 by discussing the consumers' perceptions of hotels and shared accommodations. According to the study aim no. 4 stated in the introductory chapter, section 5.5 addresses the LSQUAL framework's dependability. Finally, in order to achieve the study objectives 5 and 6 described in the introductory chapter, section 5.6 analysed the customer gap, satisfaction level, and future recommendations for accommodations.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION

6.1 Introduction:

The final section of this paper summarise the study, followed by a recommendation to the hotels and shared accommodation providers to minimise the customer's expectation and perception gap. In addition, the limitation of this research and the contribution to the body of knowledge are also discussed.

6.2: Summary of the paper:

This study was aimed to measure the service quality gap between the traditional hotels and the shared accommodation. In doing so, the study was designed in the following style

- The first chapter gives a summary of the research article. This chapter covers the study's objective and goal, as well as the research questions and methods. It also analyses the study's significance to the current body of knowledge.
- The second chapter is split into two halves. The first chapter of the article is devoted to a thorough review of the literature on hotels and shared accommodation. The tourist market in London and the hotel industry in the U.K. were both examined in this section. The second section of the literature study focused on service quality factors, customer loyalty, service quality frameworks, the SERVQUAL model, and its application in the hotel industry.
- The methods used to perform the study are discussed in detail in Chapter 3. This chapter focused on research strategy, research philosophy, study design, sampling, and main and secondary data collection techniques, as well as questionnaires and statistical analysis tools..
- The conclusions of the survey were examined in the fourth chapter. The outcomes of the service quality gap and the hypothesis test were the main emphasis points.
- The fifth chapter contains a full explanation of the empirical findings.
- Chapter six summarises the whole work, as well as the research limits, future research prospects, and addition the contribution to the body of knowledge.

6.3: Research outcome:

To address the key research question “**How does the gap of the service quality gap in the hotels differ from shared accommodations?**” along with the sub-questions, the research answers the following questions and met the following objectives.

Research sub-questions:

1. How does the service quality differ between the conventional hotel and shared accommodation?
2. Do the hotels and shared accommodation have the same level of the customer’s expectation?
3. Do the hotels and shared accommodation have the same level of the customer’s perception?
4. How does the gap of the service quality factors influence the choice of future accommodation?
5. How does the customer gap influence the satisfaction level?

Research objectives:

1. Find out the gaps in the service quality factors between traditional hotels and shared accommodation.
2. To evaluate the expectation for both the traditional hotel and shared accommodation guests.
3. To evaluate the perception for both the traditional hotel and shared accommodation guests.
4. To test the reliability of the LSQUAL model for hotels and shared accommodation.
5. To establish the impact of the satisfaction level on future recommendation.
6. To establish the correlation between the customer gap and satisfaction level.

Summary of findings:

- There exist a service quality customer gap between the traditional hotels and shared accommodation. This finding met the above research question no 1 and met the research objective no. 1

- The research found that there is no gap on guest's expectation towards the traditional hotel and shared accommodation. This findings answers the above research question no. 2 and met the research no 2.
- The research found that there exists a gap on guest's perception towards the traditional hotel and shared accommodation. This findings answers the above research question no. 2 and met the research no 2.
- This research formulated the LSQUAL framework to measure service quality gap and found the is instrument is reliable to measure customer gap. This findings met the research objective no 4.
- This study revealed that future recommendation for the choice of the accommodation significantly depend on the customer's satisfaction level. This findings answer the research question no 4 and met the research objective no 5.
- This research finally established that there exist a negative correlation between the service quality gap and the satisfaction level. This findings answers the above research question no 5 and met the research objective no 6.

6.4 Recommendation to the Hotel and Shred accommodation providers:

The research has found that there exist service quality gaps between the hotels and shared accommodation. Hotels have managed to keep the gap lower in the tangibility dimensions; however, the gap is not significant enough so the shared accommodations can take necessary steps to close the gap and maximise customer satisfaction. According to the research finding shared accommodation is more reliable to the accommodation guest compared to the hotels although a significant gap is found inaccurate record keeping. Shred accommodation needs to address the issue to be more reliable to the customers. In the assurance, dimensions shared accommodation managed to keep the gap lower in cleanliness, bed comfort and efficient physical features. Although hotels seem to be more convenient to the guest in terms of operating hours, hoteliers need to address the other issues in this dimension to stay in competition with the shared accommodation. Most of the factors in empathy dimensions shared accommodation guest's expectation and perception gap is significant. In the responsiveness dimension, although there exists a gap, the gap is comparative between the hotel and shared accommodation. Therefore, both hotel and shared accommodation need to

work on minimising the gap to stay ahead in the competition and maximise customer satisfaction. Hotels and shared accommodation can take the suggestion from this research established in the literature review chapter as guidelines to keep the gap as minimum as possible. These are as follows

6.4 Research limitations:

Research limitations are those aspects of the technique that impacted or influenced how the results of your research were interpreted. They are the limitations on generalisability, applicability to practise, and value of data that are a consequence of the research design or the approach used to demonstrate reliability and validity that were initially selected.

This study certainly has certain limits, which is to be expected. Throughout the study process, however, it is vital that necessary steps were taken to reduce the range of area of restrictions.

6.4.1 Methodological formulation:

In this DBA research, only hotel guests' views have been considered to analyse the service quality gap. Initially, accommodation managers and employees along with the accommodation guests were considered to be surveyed to construct the service quality factors. But due to the pandemic, there was a lockdown in presence in London. Therefore, an extensive content analysis through filtering the accommodation guests reviews and accommodation providers fine prints from online sources like booking.com, TripAdvisor, Expedia, Airbnb were conducted.

6.4.2 Measure used to collect the primary data:

For this DBA research, only a quantitative questionnaire survey was conducted to gather the primary data. As there was a time limitation to complete the research, and an only a quantitative survey was considered. In addition, due to the current pandemic situation and restriction on travelling the questionnaire findings could not be validated following a qualitative interview or focus group discussion. During the final stages of the research, the following restrictions were in practice in London

- Restrictions on domestic travel
- Restrictions to keep distance
- Restrictions on international travel

- Restrictions on social mixing
- Traffic signal based international travel.
- Additional measures for international travellers (Covid tests certificates)
- Permitted events

However, to overcome the limitation, bigger sample size has been considered so that the result represents the actual thoughts of the accommodations guest.

6.4.3 Time restrictions:

London has faced a tough lockdown restriction for more than a year and a half. Most of the hotels and shared accommodations needed to be kept closed according to the government rules to prevent the spread of the corona virus. Because of the restrictions, primary data collection was delayed. Therefore, the researcher has only limited time to gather and analyse the primary data. The research was also bound to the visa restrictions to complete the research in a restricted time frame. However, the researcher has cancelled the annual holiday and worked on the project additional 4 to 6 hours daily to finalise the thesis.

The objective of this research is to analyse the customer gap in service quality factors. Therefore, only the customer gap was analysed in this research without considering the reason for the gap.

6.5: Contribution to the research body:

This study on the service quality gap analysis between the hotel and shared accommodation will contribute to the current body of knowledge in the hospitality industry in a variety of ways. The contributions are as follows

- Since the aim of the research was to analyse the service quality gap between the traditional hotels and the shared accommodation, this study proposed industry specific modified SERVQUAL model named as LSQUAL framework to measure the service quality gap in the lodging industry, which is a contribution to the research body.
- The LSQUAL framework developed for this research to undertake a questionnaire survey in the accommodation sector can be used for further research in service industry; however, the factors need to be amended according to the service sector

- Service quality gap between conventional hotels and shared accommodation has been identified in this paper using the LSQUAL framework. Stakeholders in the accommodation industry can use the outcome of this paper to address the service quality gap and take essential steps to balance customer's expectation and perception.
- The expectations and perceptions of hotel and shared accommodation guests were measured in order to achieve the research goals. Accommodation providers may use the information in this paper to address the guest expectations and perceptions gap and build a promotional plan that addresses the customer gap in order to stay ahead of the competition

6.6 Outlines for further research:

Previous literature was used to identify the characteristics of questionnaire design in this DBA study. Future research will need a more customer-focused qualitative approach to gather a clear understanding from target consumers. The objective of this research is to analyse the customer gap in service quality factors. Therefore, only the customer gap was analysed in this research without considering the reason for the gap. Future research can deeply look for potential reasons for the customer gap.

As various age, gender, and income groups may have varied needs and criteria for evaluating quality, this approach may be further expanded by utilising demographic data as a foundation to determine the distinct key characteristics for each target client's group. This kind of data may be very useful in developing market segmentation-based strategies for certain target consumers.

Future studies may include applying the approach to other service industries such as transportation, to test its universality. The areas in the approach that need to be modified may be recognised based on experience and input from different sectors.

Future research may concentrate on finding the differences in expectations and perceptions across various consumer profiles and cultures, which was not done in this study. Furthermore, the statistical applications employed on the information were limited to determining centrality measures, evaluating the Anova test and calculating the SERVQUAL gap model. Analytical features, such as multiple regressions, linear regression analysis, could be applied

to analyse the data to define and correlate parameters across survey participants, define and correlate survey participants across factors, and illustrate disparities between components.

Qualitative research can be conducted to determine this expectation and perception. Whatever the reasons, a change in approach on the part of the employees and visitors, who would be happier and more likely to promote the hotels and shared accommodation that might result in increased revenue and minimised customer gap.

When determining the discrepancies between expectations and perceptions, the participants have given the values of the variables lived experiences. As a consequence, the values for the anticipation ratings may have been heavily affected by their direct previous experiences and may not reflect the same value as they would have given before the service encounter. Perception levels could therefore be an indication of a respondent's unhappiness with a parameter, rather than a fair value as related to the other attribute.

6.7 Conclusion:

In a thorough analysis utilising the modified service LSQUAL, this research study aims to examine and assess the current level of customer gap service quality in conventional hotels and shared accommodation. The customer gap is a measurement for assessing service quality. As a result, both consumer expectations and actual experiences, referred to as the customer gap, are evaluated through a questionnaire survey to determine the customer gap between the hotel and shared accommodation.

To conduct the study, the relevant literatures on service quality elements were examined, a conceptual framework was established, and a methodology was created to analyse the consumer gap on service quality aspects from the customers' viewpoint. First and foremost, the study will assist the host of the accommodation service providers in gaining a better understanding of the customer gap that exists in terms of service quality factors. Second, a better knowledge of the customer's expectations and perceptions would aid accommodation service providers in minimising the service quality gap. Finally, Hotels and shared accommodations need to pay special attention to service quality factors to remain competitive in the hospitality industry. This analysis on the customer gap in service quality factors for both conventional hotels and shared economy accommodation will aid in the advancement of knowledge and the creation of extra value in the tourism and hospitality industries.

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APPENDIX:

Questionnaire Consent form

Questionnaire Consent Form

Primary Researcher:

Name: Emdadul Haque

Email: [REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Purpose of Study:

Academic.

Research Title:

“Analysing the service quality gaps between traditional hotels and shared accommodation: a study on customers’ experience in Central London”

I _____, hereby confirm that I have read and understand the research topic and considered the opportunity to take part in this research.

I understand that the research work is for academic purpose and my participation is voluntary. In addition, I have the full right to withdraw my participation from this study and I am free to decline any questions that I do not want to answer.

I understand that there is no risk associated to take part in this survey. I also waive any claim for copyright to this material should the researcher ever publish in a scholarly journal either in paper or electronic format.

I also understand that my anonymity will be maintained about the responses to the questionnaire items and the researcher will take every effort like data encryption, secured storing to preserve confidentiality. I also understand that according to the data protection act I have the right to access the information that I had provided. I can also request to exclude and destroy any information I had provided by contacting the researcher named above.

I hereby give my consent to participate in this survey.

Participant's Signature:

Date:

Questionnaire:

Questionnaire

Part 1:

1. Your Name:
2. Your Age:
3. Your Gender:
4. Nationality:
5. Name of the accommodation:

Part 2:

The questions in this section relate to the Service Quality Factors based on LSQUAL scale: Please tick (✓) your response to the questions according to the following LSQUAL scale:

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
1	2	3	4	5

1a. You expected the presence of modern equipment in this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

1b. You found the presence of modern equipment in this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

2a. You expected the physical features to be visually appealing in this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

2b. You found the physical features to be visually appealing in this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

3a. You expected the physical features to comply with the offered service in this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

3b. You found the physical features complying with the offered service in this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

4a. You expected the presence of security and safety equipment in this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

4b. You found the presence of security and safety equipment in this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

5a. You expected the successful completion of the commitment made by this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

5b. You found the successful completion of the commitment made by this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

6a. You expected accurate record keeping in this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

6b. You found the hotel/shared accommodation keeping accurate records.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

7a. You expected all the equipment in working condition in this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

7b. You found the equipment in working condition in this hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

8a. You expected secured payment service from the hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

8b. You found secured payment service from the hotel/shared accommodation.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

9a. You expected safe and secure environment on this hotel/shared accommodation premises.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

9b. You found safe and secured environment on this hotel/shared accommodation premises.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

10a. You expected this hotel/shared accommodation to be cleaned appropriately.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

10b. You found this hotel/shared accommodation to be cleaned appropriately.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

11a. You expected comfortable bed in this hotel/shared accommodation room.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

11b. You found comfortable bed in this hotel/shared accommodation room.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

12a. You expected this hotel/shared accommodation to provide you personal attention.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

12b. You found this hotel/shared accommodation providing you personal attention.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

13a. You expected this hotel/shared accommodation to have convenient opening hours.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

13b. You found this hotel/shared accommodation to have convenient opening hours.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

14a. You expected the employees of this Hotel/shared accommodations to wear professional attire.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

14b. You found the employees of this Hotel/shared accommodations to wear professional attire.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

15a. You expected the employees of this Hotel/shared accommodation to be polite.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

15b. You found the employees of this Hotel/shared accommodation to be polite.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

16a. You expected the employees of this Hotel/shared accommodation to be reliable.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

16b. You found the employees of this Hotel/shared accommodation to be reliable.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

17a. You expected the employees of this hotel/shared accommodation to recognise your individual needs.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

17b. You found the employees of this hotel/shared accommodation to recognise your individual needs.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

18a. You expected the employees of this hotel/shared accommodation to have soft feelings towards you.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

18b. You found the employees of this hotel/shared accommodation to have soft feelings towards you.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

19a. You expected the employees of this hotel/shared accommodation to be flexible to respond your queries.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

19b. You found the employees of this hotel/shared accommodation to be flexible to respond your queries.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

20a. You expected the employees of this hotel/shared accommodation to be willing helpful.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

20b. You found the employees of this hotel/shared accommodation to be willing helpful.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

21a. You expected the employee to receive adequate support from the hotel/shared accommodation management.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

21b. You found the employee to receive adequate support from the hotel/shared accommodation management.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

22a. You expected the employees of this hotel/shared accommodation to complete any service promptly.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

22b. You found the employees of this hotel/shared accommodation to complete any service promptly.

1	2	3	4	5
---	---	---	---	---

Part 3:

1. What was the primary reason for staying in this hotel/shared accommodation?

- Leisure
- Business
- Attending events
- Others: Please mention.....

2. Which factor did you consider most for choosing this hotel/shared accommodation?

- Price
- Location
- Brand Reputation
- Trip Purpose
- Others (Please mention)....

3. How satisfied you were on your stay in this hotel/shared accommodation? (on a scale of 5)

- Very dissatisfied
- Dissatisfied
- Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied
- Satisfied
- Very satisfied

4. How likely are you to recommend this hotel/shared accommodation? (On a scale of 5)

- Extremely likely
- Very likely
- Moderate
- Unlikely
- Very Unlikely

Thank you for your participation

3.Criteria to choose hotel and shared accommodation:

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Screenshot of Booking.com. Please contact the author for more details.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Screenshot of Airbnb.com. Please contact the author for more details.

4. Table: Summary of literature on the service quality, satisfaction, and revisit intension in the accommodation industry.

Title & Author	Research Question	Research Methodology	Conclusion & Recommendations	Gap for further research
Service quality,	How does service	The researcher	The researcher	Sophisticated

<p>customer satisfaction, and behavioural intentions in the service factory. (Olorunniwo, Hsu and Udo, 2006)</p>	<p>quality is related to customer satisfaction and behavioural intention?</p>	<p>has adopted a modified version of the SERVQUAL scale to collect data and used descriptive statistics to analyse the data.</p>	<p>has identified the dominant service quality factors, which are Tangibles, Recovery, Responsiveness, and Knowledge. The influence of service quality and behavioural intention is significant; however, the indirect effect of satisfaction plays a stronger role to drive future behavioural intention.</p>	<p>statistical tools like nonparametric correlation can be used to correlate customer satisfaction level and likelihood to recommendation.</p>
<p>Service quality and customer satisfaction: qualitative research implications for luxury hotels (Lu, Berchoux, Marek and Chen,</p>	<p>Is there a common concept of service quality and customer satisfaction among luxury hotel managers and their customers?</p>	<p>: An inductive research approach was used to conduct the research. Interviews were conducted with hotel managers and guests. Qualitative</p>	<p>Management and visitors exhibited similar understandings of luxury; nevertheless, the two groups had different ways of describing luxury, service quality,</p>	<p>.</p>

2015)	Is there a disconnect between the services provided by luxury hotels and the manner in which their clients actually experience those services?	analysis has been carried out to comprehend the definitions and perceptions of luxury, service quality and satisfaction.	and overall happiness with the experience. Managers prefer to assess customer happiness in terms of the services given, while customers evaluate customer satisfaction in terms of the value obtained considering the price.	
A Structural Analysis of Value, Quality, and Price Perceptions of Business and Leisure Travellers (Kashyap and Bojanic, 2000)	To what extent does the gap exist between value in the decision processes of business and leisure travellers.	A deductive approach was taken, and descriptive statistics were used to analyse the questionnaire data. The researcher has used a structural equation modelling for investigating the relationships among price, quality, and value	The researcher has found the differences in value perceptions of business and leisure travellers. Value is associated with both comparative ratings and revisit intentions. Service quality factors also have an influence on revisit intention. Both value and	There exist opportunities for accommodation providers to learn from customer experience for gaining competitive advantages

		<p>and in order to figure out the confluence on travellers' comparative ratings and revisit intentions.</p>	<p>quality influence the revisit intention directly. This suggests that travellers encode perceptions of value as a synopsis of relevant product information. These value perceptions are instrumental in helping travellers make choices, emphasising the need for firms to focus on value enhancement strategies. Firms may add value by improving perceived or lowering perceived prices.</p> <p>The key recommendation by the researcher is that hotel management should consider</p>	
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			minimising the gap between perceived value and quality for developing value enhancement strategies.	
Analysing changes in hotel customers' expectations by trip mode (Liu et al., 2013)	How do satisfaction and expectations vary for customers with the same backgrounds but with different trip modes?	The researcher has used secondary data from the customers' review websites.	The result of this research demonstrates that customers expectation and satisfaction vary according to the trip mode.	Gap for further research: The researcher has used guest reviews to collect the data. Consequently, direct interaction with guests presents an opportunity for improving processes for gathering their opinions regarding service quality aspects.
The accommodation experiencescape:	When it comes to hotels and sharing economy	This investigation was conducted using a deductive	Using Pine and Gilmore's eight-dimensional	Post consumption decision-making process yet to be

<p>a comparative assessment of hotels and Airbnb (Mody, Suess and Lehto, 2017)</p>	<p>providers, what aspects of the experience economy are driving consumers' experiential engagement with them?</p> <p>How do hotels and providers of the sharing economy do in terms of performance on these metrics?</p> <p>Customers' exceptional and unforgettable experiencing results are influenced by the aspects of the experience economy to what degree they do so.</p> <p>What is the difference between hotels and sharing</p>	<p>method. The information was gathered via the use of a survey questionnaire.</p>	<p>architecture, the researchers have verified and extended its functionality (1998). Airbnb seems to be utilising these eight characteristics to a larger degree than the hotel sector, according to the authors.</p> <p>Respondents who stayed at an Airbnb reported having a substantially better experience across all eight aspects – entertainment, education, escapism, aesthetics, serendipity, localness, communities, and personalisation – than those who stayed at a hotel,</p>	<p>examined.</p>
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	economy providers in terms of their capacity to provide exceptional, unforgettable experiences for their customers?		according to the research. Researchers have shown that Airbnb beats hotels in terms of community and sense of place.	
Unravelling the diverse nature of service quality in a sharing economy: A social exchange theory perspective of Airbnb accommodation (Priporas, Stylos, Rahimi and Vedanthachari, 2017)	How do customers value the perception of the service quality in shared economy accommodation?	The research approach was deductive. The required data were collected through a self-administered multi-item structured questionnaire	The researcher has evaluated the interrelationship between customers' perceptions of the service quality factors and the social exchange theory of Airbnb guests.	There exists an opportunity to compare guests' experience at Airbnb accommodation with their experience at hotels. Particular location, amenities along with shared accommodation hosts and guests' perceptions of service quality can also be considered for future research.
Exploring international	What are the dimensions of the	The data was collected via the	The researcher has concluded that	The researchers have suggested to

<p>tourists' perceptions of hotel operations by using a modified SERVQUAL approach – a case study of Mauritius.</p> <p>(Devi Juwaheer, 2004)</p>	<p>hotel service quality?</p> <p>How do the service quality factors influence the overall satisfaction?</p>	<p>use of a self-administered questionnaire, and the results were analysed through the use of regression analysis.</p>	<p>9 service quality out of 39 factors determines the level of guest satisfaction.</p>	<p>consider whether the factor structure proposed in this study is valid in other classes of accommodation such as guesthouses and private bungalows, as well as whether the perceived quality levels differ by location.</p>
<p>Service quality, emotional satisfaction, and behavioural intentions: A study in the hotel industry.</p> <p>(Ladhari, 2009)</p>	<p>What are the ramifications of consumers' opinions on the quality of a product or service?</p> <p>What works as a predictor of a customer's future behavioural intentions is unknown.</p>	<p>The information was gathered via a questionnaire survey, and descriptive statistics were utilised to analyse the information.</p>	<p>The suggested and tested cognitive-affective-behavioural model of the connections between the dimensions of service quality, emotional satisfaction, and behavioural intents has been developed and tested in this</p>	<p>There exists a lack of knowledge regarding service quality by testing and refining the proposed model in other service sectors</p>

			research.	
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